

**NERC Centres for
Atmospheric Science**

NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

NCAS Science Management Audit

September 2004

NCAS Documents responding to the Terms of Reference

<http://ncas.nerc.ac.uk>

NCAS
NERC Centres for Atmospheric Science

NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

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Welcome to NCAS

NERC Centres for Atmospheric Science

The NERC Centres for Atmospheric Science (NCAS) is a Natural Environment Research Council (NERC) Collaborative Centre.

The role of NCAS is to provide the UK with national capability (i.e. stable, long-term and broad) in atmospheric science research. NCAS also provides research outcomes for government policy-making and for the wider UK science base.

NCAS achieves this through its research and support programmes. These address the key scientific and technical challenges currently faced by the UK atmospheric science research community and include: climate change science; weather processes; atmospheric composition (including air quality) and state-of-the-art technologies for observing and modelling the atmosphere.

NCAS is not based in one location. It is a "Collaborative Centre" and, as such, is made up of a set of seven centres and facilities distributed across many UK universities and related institutions.

Latest News

- [The Convective Storm Initiation Project \(CSIP\) completes pilot campaign \(02/06/04\)](#)
- [Posts Available: Head of FAAM and Technical Manager of FAAM - closing date 19th August 2004 \(02/06/04\)](#)
- [The Intercontinental Transport of Ozone and Precursors - ITOP - programme begins: Press release, media coverage, London Science Museum exhibit and photo gallery available here Gone with the Wind? Over a hundred scientists take to the skies to track global air pollution \(12/07/04\)](#)
- [UGAMP Annual Conference, 8-10 September 2004 \(15/07/04\)](#)
- [NCAS Scientists Hit the Headlines - The Observer; The Guardian; The Telegraph; the BBC... \(03/06/04\)](#)
- [Professor John Pyle \(ACMSU\) elected Fellow of the Royal Society \(FRS\) \(03/06/04\)](#)
- [Two NCAS PhD Studentships Still Available \(02/06/04\)](#)
- [HIGEM website goes live \(03/06/04\)](#)
- [CGAM Annual Report and Research Highlights Available \(03/06/04\)](#)
- [Unified Model RPM files available from BADG \(03/06/04\)](#)
- [Progress Towards Start of Service for BAe Research Aircraft \(03/06/04\)](#)
- [Photos of new BAe Research Aircraft Available \(air-to-air and in the Cranfield hanger\) \(03/06/04\)](#)
- [Research Aircraft - Security Clearance required for all personnel flying with FAAM \(03/06/04\)](#)
- [Report on Aerosol Workshop, November 2003, now available \(03/06/04\)](#)
- [Report on UK-Japan Climate Model Workshop, March 2004, now available \(03/06/04\)](#)

More news is available on the NCAS News pages

NCAS Documents responding to the Terms of Reference

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The NERC Centres for Atmospheric Science comprises:

ACMSU: *Atmospheric Chemistry Modelling Support Unit*

BADC: *British Atmospheric Data Centre*

CGAM: *Centre for Global Atmospheric Modelling*

DIAC: *Distributed Institute for Atmospheric Composition*

FAAM: *Facility for Airborne Atmospheric Measurements*

UFAM: *Universities' Facility for Atmospheric Measurement*

UWERN: *Universities' Weather Research Network*

**Summary of the Contents of the SMA documentation
provided by NCAS**

Summary of the Contents of the SMA documentation provided by NCAS

The following is a list of the documents submitted by NCAS in response to the 11 Terms of Reference for the Science Management Audit. Note that in ToR No. 1 we provide a description of the organisation of NCAS, by way of introduction to the other ToRs. It therefore needs to be read first as the other ToR documents assume that the reader is familiar with the organisation of NCAS.

ToR No. 1 - NCAS as a National Capability and Source of Advice to Government

An overview is provided of: the overall structure of NCAS; its role in providing a national capability and in coordination in UK atmospheric science; and some examples of the various ways in which NCAS has provided advice to the UK Government.

ToR No. 2 – NCAS Scientific and management leadership, long-term vision/mission and strategy

In this document the following aspects of NCAS are described: the various contracts NERC has concerning NCAS; an overview of NCAS scientific and management leadership; the NCAS mission; the NCAS research strategy; examples of agendas and minutes from NCAS Management Group meetings.

ToR No. 3 – NCAS Procedures for Setting Research Aims, Monitor Progress and Evaluate Output

In this document we describe: the procedures NCAS uses to monitor annual aims and progress, including, as an example, the introduction to the 2003-2004 Annual Report; details about the NCAS Advisory Group including its membership, terms of reference and an example of the minutes of its 2004 meeting.

ToR No. 4 – Reports on NCAS Programmes

In this section reports are provided of the various outputs of NCAS programmes, including full publications lists. These programme reports, which form the most substantial part of the documentation, are provided in a separate document containing a set of annexes. Some are full SMA reports whilst others are progress reports. They are listed in the following way:

Climate Processes and Change

I: CGAM – a full report is provided as **Annex A** on activities from Oct 2001 to present

II: ACMSU – a full report is provided as **Annex B** on activities from Oct 2001 to present

Hazardous weather

UWERN – a full report is provided as **Annex C** on activities from Oct 1997 to present

Atmospheric Composition

DIAC – a progress report is provided as **Annex D** for information

Data Stewardship

BADC – a full report is provided as **Annex E** on activities from Jan 2001 to present

Observational Facilities

I: FAAM – a progress report is provided as **Annex F** for information

II: UFAM – a progress report is provided as **Annex G** for information

ToR No. 5 – NCAS National and international links; technology expensive projects; coordinating distributed major programmes; fostering multi-disciplinary approaches

In this document the following aspects of NCAS activities are described: national linkages including the NCAS Affiliated Institutions (including a membership list and minutes of the last meeting in 2004) and the link with the Met Office; international links; statistics on co-authorship of NCAS publications; membership of committees by NCAS staff; the NCAS regional role; examples of collaborative research and coordination of programmes by NCAS.

ToR No. 6 – Knowledge Transfer; users; data and advice

In this document the following NCAS activities are summarised: major customers/users of NCAS research/facilities; research that benefits policy-makers, including as communicated via the Forum for Atmospheric Science and Technology; knowledge transfer and uptake of services/facilities; NCAS science communications.

ToR No. 7 – Management of NCAS budgets and infrastructure

In this section the following NCAS activities are discussed: the management of NCAS budgets; measures of the value-for-money of NCAS research; financial summary for NCAS including the pre-2002 allocation, the outcome of the NCAS I proposal, the Council decision on UFAM and the Earth Simulator project in 2003, the NCAS synchronisation in 2003 and the Capital Equipment Round award in 2004. A spreadsheet of the total funding awarded to NCAS by NERC and the total staff and student numbers in 2004 are provided. The Director's response to the Staff Survey is given.

ToR No. 8 – Investment in Capital equipment, facilities, services and support

In this section the following NCAS activities will be described: capital equipment investments, usage of services and facilities.

ToR No. 9 – External Funding

In this section a summary is provided of the external funding awarded to NCAS as a result of proposals submitted to a variety of funding bodies.

ToR No. 10 – Processes of Change; flow of new ideas; career paths

In this section various ways in which new ideas lead to changes in the NCAS programme are described. Also issues relating to training of research students and career development of NCAS staff are discussed.

ToR No. 11 – Funding Duration and Frequency of Bidding for New Funds

The (short) history of how NCAS has been funded by NERC is provided and also the planning for the next phase of funding for 2006 to 2011, NCAS II, is described.

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**ToR No. 1 – NCAS as a National Capability and Source of
Advice to Government**

ToR No. 1 – NCAS as a National Capability and Source of Advice to Government

In this document an overview is provided of: the overall structure of NCAS; its role in providing a national capability and in coordination in atmospheric science; and some examples of the various ways in which NCAS has provided advice to the UK Government.

1. Organisation and National Capability

NCAS is a Natural Environment Research Council, NERC, Collaborative Centre that was established in April 2002 and funded by NERC, in the first instance, for four years until March 2006. It builds upon and incorporates various atmospheric science research activities funded previously by NERC but without overall coordination.

NCAS is the kernel of expertise and facilities at the heart of UK academic research in atmospheric science (<http://ncas.nerc.ac.uk>). It provides the UK with national capability and excellence in atmospheric science research that is stable, long-term and broad. It contributes to NERC's mission in Earth System Science. NCAS consists of the following six components:

- *Research programme*
- *Services and facilities support programme for the wider academic community*
- *Science communications function*
- *Partnerships with key organisations, such as particularly the Met Office*
- *Affiliated Institutions*
- *Training programme - research students and staff*

The wider UK academic community is heavily involved in NCAS via the 26 universities that are NCAS Affiliated Institutions and, for this community, NCAS is inclusive and provides: leadership; modelling and observational support; a framework for collaboration; critical mass; catalysis of community-wide projects (fuller details about the NCAS Affiliated Institutions are provided under ToR No. 5). NCAS research is policy-relevant with outcomes used by the wider UK and international science base.

The NCAS research and services/facilities support programmes each receive approximately equal allocations of the total NCAS budget. The latter programme enables UK atmospheric scientists to carry out research in the priority areas by the maintenance of a kernel of national expertise and excellence in developing and using the underpinning methodologies needed for atmospheric science research. The research programme is structured to allow the key scientific challenges described in the Atmospheric Science Strategy (see ToR No. 2) to be addressed in an effective and efficient way. These challenges are related to the following strategic research areas:

- *Atmospheric composition*
- *Small-scale processes and weather*
- *Climate variability and change*
- *Technologies for observing and modelling the atmosphere*

They map onto all the NERC priority areas in Earth System science and also utilise fully the underlying atmospheric science research methodologies: *modelling, laboratory measurement, theory, field measurement and data analysis.*

The research, support and training programmes carried out by NCAS involve a distributed network of researchers across UK universities and related institutions. NCAS aims to be as inclusive as possible given the directed and managed nature of the programme. Currently this involves funding of scientists in 18 UK institutions, as well as a significant number of research studentships (for student numbers see ToR no. 7 and discussion of training in ToR No. 10). Whilst being inclusive NCAS cannot by

itself provide funding to all UK atmospheric science researchers. Much of the supporting role of NCAS is to facilitate the wider community to better exploit opportunities for research funded from outside of NCAS. A proportion of NCAS funding is allocated by open competition. The research and support programmes of NCAS are structured within a set of seven distributed centres and facilities, each being centres-of-excellence.

The NCAS centres and facilities are grouped into “climate modelling centres”, the “weather research network”, the “atmospheric composition institute” and finally “facilities”. Most NCAS centres and facilities also carry out significant training of research students and this is described separately in ToR No. 10. These various activities within NCAS can be summarised in the following way:

(i) *Climate modelling centres*

The UK universities’ Global Atmospheric Modelling Programme, UGAMP, is the oldest of the UK academic atmospheric science research networks and it traces its history back to the 1970s when a spectral global model was devised that then became the core of the first ECMWF weather forecast model. The NCAS Centre for Global Atmospheric Modelling (CGAM), based in the Department of Meteorology at the University of Reading, and the NCAS Atmospheric Chemistry Modelling Support Unit (ACMSU), in the Department of Chemistry at the University of Cambridge, specialise in research on climate variability (particularly on seasonal-to-decadal timescales) and global chemistry-climate modelling respectively. CGAM/ACMSU were established in 1992 and 1994 respectively. Also they both provide climate-modelling support to the UK community and as such are the core units supporting the wider UGAMP community. CGAM and ACMSU both use the Hadley Centre climate model as the main top-of-the-range model for their research. A key aspect of climate modelling is the need for extensive use of national supercomputing facilities and NCAS manages the usage of these facilities for NERC on behalf of the atmospheric science community. In addition increasingly Grid-enabled technologies, such as are becoming available with the national e-Science programme, are being used.

(ii) *Weather research network*

The NCAS Universities’ Weather Research Network (UWERN) was established fully in 1998 building on previous research activities in this area. It carries out research in various aspects of regional and small-scale atmospheric processes and is distributed across several UK universities. The mission of UWERN is to harness expertise from within UK universities, and exploit facilities within universities, research institutes and the Met Office to advance the knowledge and prediction of atmospheric behaviour on regional and smaller scales. It has a close association with the Met Office staff in the Joint Centre for Mesoscale Meteorology, located at the University of Reading. A variety of numerical models are used by UWERN including regional and global versions of the Met Office’s Unified forecast model. It is developing a new microscale model to carry out research on small-scale atmospheric phenomena. UWERN provides support for the wider community on modelling and data assimilation at regional and small-scales. The use of national supercomputing facilities is required for the modelling research in UWERN.

(iii) *Atmospheric composition institute*

The NCAS Distributed Institute for Atmospheric Composition (DIAC) was established in 2003, building upon a number of related activities including NERC’s Core Strategic Measurements for Atmospheric Science, COSMAS, programme. It carries out research to understand how atmospheric composition is changing and its effect on the Earth System. DIAC activities involve: coordinating and undertaking field experiments making use of expertise throughout the community; developing and implementing ideas for new instruments for laboratory, field and earth observation measurements; developing a modelling capability for field applications, using links with ACMSU and UWERN; determining the rates and mechanisms of key chemical processes occurring in the gas and aerosol/droplet phases in the atmosphere; undertaking long-term monitoring of atmospheric

composition and its changes. The two main scientific foci of DIAC at present are: formation, transformation and removal of aerosols; production, transport and removal of photochemical oxidants. DIAC aims also to build partnerships with a range of NERC and other research groups in areas such as surface exchange and radiative transfer.

(iv) *Facilities*

NCAS provides a group of supporting facilities to allow UK atmospheric scientists to utilise latest technologies and techniques. The NCAS British Atmospheric Data Centre (BADC) at the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory, RAL, is one of NERC's designated data centres and it was established in 1995. Observational and model data are managed and curated by BADC for and on behalf of the community. BADC is at the forefront of e-Science developments in this area being the leader of the NERC DataGrid project. These data include: observations obtained during field campaigns, operational meteorological observations, numerical model output, Earth observations and re-analysis data. The NCAS Universities' Facility for Atmospheric Measurement (UFAM) operates a set of specialized atmospheric measurement instruments for use from the ground and from research aircraft and was established fully in 2001. UFAM instruments are distributed in university centres of expertise and are developed and supported by instrument scientists who are experts in the various types of measurement techniques. These instruments are used by the community in research field campaigns. In addition the NCAS/Met Office Facility for Airborne Atmospheric Measurements (FAAM) operates a BAE 146 research aircraft from Cranfield University in partnership with the Met Office. FAAM is only now becoming established fully, building on preparatory development work over the last three years. FAAM has a set of core meteorological instruments and scientists can deploy a range of UFAM and other specialized instruments on board the aircraft during campaigns. The UFAM instruments can measure a wide range of physical and compositional characteristics of the atmosphere.

In supporting a disciplinary area, NCAS is distinct from other centres, which only address particular research problems of current topical interest. It acts for atmospheric science to support the relevant disciplinary science base and to nurture the academic community. NCAS is organised as a distributed set of research centres and facilities located in various universities and at RAL. The centres/facilities are managed to group expertise around the four science and technology themes referred to earlier. This allows the necessary critical mass to exist in each of these science and technology areas. Each has a director with an international reputation in their field to provide scientific leadership. The centres/facilities provide the support services to the wider community in their own specialist area. All staff in NCAS centres/facilities are employed by host institutions under contract to NERC. A key benefit of this distributed structure is that NCAS staff have access to a wide range of complimentary skills and disciplines within their host universities and departments. NCAS has four centres/facilities that are each located within a particular institution: ACMSU (Cambridge), BADC (RAL), CGAM (Reading) and FAAM (Cranfield). It also has three centres/facilities that are themselves distributed across several university and other sites exploiting expertise and excellence where they are available (DIAC, UFAM and UWERN). To summarise, NCAS comprises a set of seven hubs, some of which have, in addition, multiple spokes to groups across the academic community.

The Directors of NCAS centres and Heads of NCAS facilities are:

Director of NCAS: Professor Alan Thorpe, Department of Meteorology, University of Reading

Director of ACMSU: Professor John Pyle FRS, Department of Chemistry, University of Cambridge

Head of BADC: Dr Bryan Lawrence, Space Science and Technology Department, Rutherford Appleton Laboratory

Director of CGAM: Professor Julia Slingo, Department of Meteorology, University of Reading

- Director of DIAC:** Professor Mike Pilling, Department of Chemistry, University of Leeds
- Head of FAAM:** Professor Peter Jonas, Department of Physics, UMIST (retired June 2004);
Vacancy – Acting Head is Dr John Foot of the Met Office
- Head of UFAM:** Dr Alan Blyth, School of the Environment, University of Leeds
- Director of UWERN:** Professor Paul Mason FRS, Department of Meteorology, University of Reading (from March 2003; previously Professor Keith Browning FRS)

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with contributing universities (including several within the UGAMP network) and partnership with the Met Office

2. Advice to Government

NCAS provides advice to Government via a variety of routes.

1. The first way NCAS research can be utilised arises because most NCAS research is policy-relevant, and is published freely in the open literature and so is available for use by government scientists and policy-makers. The policy-relevance is perhaps most evident in the area of fundamental research on climate change. This research is used, often in collaborative projects,

by the Hadley Centre, whose mission is policy-directed prediction of climate change. The Hadley Centre provides the direct advice to government via the Department of the Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (Defra), resulting from climate change predictions using a model that has benefited from improvements introduced as a result of research including that carried out by NCAS. In addition some NCAS research has been funded directly by Defra and the Department for Trade and Industry aimed at answering specific issues, for example relating to aviation and the environment.

2. A second route for advice is that many senior staff, funded by NCAS, are members of government department committees and science advisory boards. Examples include: Alan Thorpe's membership of Defra's Science Advisory Council and of the HECToR Management Board to procure the next national supercomputing service; Mike Pilling's chairmanship of Defra's Air Quality Expert Group; Paul Mason's chairmanship of the Global Climate Observing System (funded in part by Defra); Julia Slingo's membership of the supercomputing sub-committee of the Global Environmental Coordination Committee of the Chief Scientific Adviser to the UK Government and her membership of the Met Office Scientific Advisory Committee; Stephen Mobbs (member of UWERN) membership of the "Expert Panel to Sustain Scientific Excellence at the Met Office"; John Pyle's chairmanship of the Stratospheric Ozone Review Group and the Royal Society's Global Environmental Research Committee; Mike Pilling's membership of the review panel for the Third Runway at Heathrow; CGAM and ACMSU staff involvement as lead and contributing authors for IPCC Scientific Assessments.
3. A third route is via the Forum for Atmospheric Science and Technology, FAST, that is chaired by NCAS and brings together many government departments such as the Ministry of Defence, Defra, Department of Health, Department for Transport, Department of Trade and Industry, Environment Agency and the Met Office at annual meetings. These discuss the requirements of government for atmospheric science research and update government departments on NCAS research outcomes (see the FAST terms of reference, membership and example of minutes in ToR No. 6).
4. The fourth route is by the input that NCAS gives, usually through NERC Swindon Office, on consultation exercises that government departments carry out periodically on policy areas or science strategies that have a relationship to environmental science and atmospheric science, e.g., consultation on the Department for International Development's Science Strategy.
5. Finally there are direct requests from government for specific pieces of advice. There have already been many of these. For example, the Department for Transport asked about the potential effect of hydrogen on atmospheric chemistry resulting from leakages that might occur if a move to a hydrogen-based economy were to take place. More recently, in early June 2004, the UK Government Chief Scientific Adviser, Sir David King, asked Alan Thorpe for advice on climate change research for a speech he was making and information about the impact on contrails and consequently on the albedo of the grounding of the US airline fleet post 11 September 2001. Sir John Krebs (Food Standards Agency) asked about the statistics of the skill of rainfall forecasts. John Pyle has given expert witness evidence to the House of Lords Science and Technology Committee's investigation of "International Scientific Agreements". John Pyle was a special adviser, and Alan Thorpe gave comments, to the House of Commons Science and Technology Committee's investigation of "Independent Advice to Government on Climate Change" in 2002. As part of CGAM's programme in crop-climate interactions we have contributed to Defra's UK-China climate impacts programme. CGAM has also provided input to the Department for International Development, DfID, on their new strategy for research funding with regard to seasonal and longer-term prediction for food security in the developing world. ACMSU scientists were consulted about the Royal Commission on Environmental Pollution's special report in 2002 on "The Environmental Effects of Civil Aircraft in Flight".

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**ToR No. 2 – NCAS Scientific and management leadership,
long-term vision/mission and strategy**

ToR No. 2 – NCAS Scientific and management leadership, long-term vision/mission and strategy

1. Introduction

In this document the following aspects of NCAS are described: the various contracts NERC has concerning NCAS; an overview of NCAS scientific and management leadership; the NCAS mission; the NCAS research strategy; examples of agendas and minutes from NCAS Management Group meetings.

2. Contracts

The way NCAS contracts are managed is that the NCAS funds reside at the NERC Swindon Office under the direct responsibility of Andrew Kaye (and Nigel Collins before he retired in 2004). The NCAS Management Group (described below) decides on the need for new or amended contracts. The Director of NCAS requests to NERC that contracts, or amendments to existing contracts, be issued to particular universities and Andrew Kaye executes this. These contracts each have a financial spreadsheet and a technical annex. Universities who receive NCAS contracts claim actual expenditure, up to the agreed budget, from NERC on a quarterly basis. New contracts are styled as: NCAS Reading, NCAS Leeds etc. but some existing contracts that pre-date the establishment of NCAS have different names. In addition the NCAS Reading contract includes the funding provided by NERC for the NCAS Directorate. The only exception to this procedure is for BADC where the contract is via a part of the overall Service Level Agreement, SLA that NERC has with RAL. In that case quarterly reports of progress from RAL are submitted to the Director of NCAS who agrees to accept, or not, each of these prior to NERC releasing funds under the SLA. Details and examples of the various NCAS contracts are available from NERC Swindon Office.

3. NCAS Scientific and Management Leadership

NCAS research and support are delivered by seven **centres/facilities**, designed to provide critical mass in each area of expertise in atmospheric science. Each centre/facility is directed by an eminent research-active senior scientist and involves staff with cognate expertise and state-of-the-art facilities. They are located in UK universities or allied institutions; several of the centres/facilities operate with a hub-and-spoke distributed structure (see diagram in ToR No. 1). The centres/facilities deliver the research, technology, support and facilities provided by NCAS and they benefit from partnership with researchers and allied-projects in the wider national and international communities, key stakeholders such as the Met Office and also from co-funding attracted by NCAS staff. The Director of NCAS provides the overall scientific and administrative leadership, including responsibility for: financial allocations within NCAS to the centres/facilities as well as to additional small initiatives considered as of strategic importance; managing the interaction between the centres/facilities as well as with the wider community, including the stakeholders; scientific strategy development; interaction with NERC Swindon Office. The Director of NCAS therefore delegates management responsibility for all the centres or facilities to their own directors and heads respectively. In addition he is research-active but that research (on the predictability of weather and climate) is externally funded and so he receives no research support from NCAS. This means that the Director of NCAS has no conflict of interest in allocating budgets to the centres and facilities. The Director and his secretary's salary, overheads and travel, minor office equipment and subsistence are paid by NERC.

Each of the seven centres and facilities that comprise NCAS has a specialist director or head managing the operation. These directors and heads are internationally recognized experts in their own field, including two Fellows of the Royal Society, and they carry out research in their own right. They are managed in turn by the Director of NCAS, who resides at the University of Reading in the same location as two of the NCAS units. The Director of NCAS has overall responsibility for NCAS and reports directly to the Chief Executive of NERC including via a regular quarterly meeting. NCAS has a Management Group that comprises: the Director of NCAS (chair); the directors and heads of all

seven NCAS centres and facilities; Andrew Kaye. The NCAS Management Group has, as well as frequent informal contacts, a one-day more formal meeting (sometimes by Access Grid) at quarterly intervals to review progress. Additionally the Director of NCAS makes visits to the various NCAS units between the quarterly Management Group meetings to discuss the operation of NCAS with the directors, heads and their staff. The costs implied by this management team represent about 11% of the total NCAS budget. (The financial contributions made to universities to compensate them for the NCAS role of the directors/heads, varies for each NCAS centre/facility. For NCAS Director, BADC, CGAM, FAAM and UFAM the contribution is nominally 100% time, for ACMSU it is 10% and for DIAC and UWERN it is 50%.) However it should be noted that the seven directors/heads and the Director of NCAS are all research-active and so they contribute not only to management of NCAS but also they contribute substantially to the NCAS research outputs. The distributed character of NCAS means that it is essential to have this level of coordination and management.

In addition the observational facilities, which have been provided by JIF support in the first instance, have specific management committees to enable effective utilization and organization of the facilities. In the case of the FAAM aircraft, the facility is a partnership with the Met Office and the FAAM management committees are therefore jointly constituted. The Director of NCAS is the Chairman of the FAAM Board. Some NCAS centres/facilities also have informal groups that their directors and heads have constituted to assist in the management and strategic direction of their particular activities. NCAS provides management of the usage by atmospheric scientists of national supercomputing facilities for NERC and involvement in the process of procurement of new services.

To provide overall scrutiny on the scientific progress there is an NCAS Advisory Group of independent scientific experts, including international and non-academic representation, advising NCAS on its development (see fuller details of the NCAS Advisory Group under ToR No. 3). NCAS also chairs a Forum for Atmospheric Science and Technology of key stakeholders in government and other departments, which meets annually to discuss the linkages and synergies between the NCAS programme and those in the stakeholder organisations (see fuller details under ToR No. 6).

In a widely geographically distributed research organisation it is essential to ensure that the community have ample opportunities to meet together for scientific exchange. NCAS organises a number of such opportunities. The primary mechanism is that the three large NCAS research themes of climate processes; small-scale processes and weather; and atmospheric composition have, individually, an annual conference. The largest of the individual conferences on climate processes attracts over 100 scientists. Every other year these annual conferences are co-located within the Royal Meteorological Society's Biennial Conference, which is co-sponsored by NCAS. This latter Conference provides the opportunity for interaction and collaboration across the whole of the NCAS remit to occur. The RMetS Biennial Conference currently involves a total of about 400 UK atmospheric scientists attending the five-day conference. In addition NCAS organises a number of one or two-day workshops focused in different areas of atmospheric science. For example, in 2003 these included a meeting on Framework 6 for atmospheric scientists, a Royal Society workshop on "Future chemical threats to the environment" and urban meteorology and air quality workshops and in 2004 they included a workshop on "Representation of convection in weather and climate models".

4. Mission statement

The mission of NCAS is: *to provide leadership and act as the focus for atmospheric science research in the UK to enable the academic community to more effectively deliver excellent research for the benefit of UK society.*

NCAS carries out this mission in many ways, including:

- Carrying out a research programme, funded by NERC, to deliver key research outcomes for the overall NERC Earth System Science research strategy (see the NCAS overall research objective described below)
- Maintaining a kernel of broad-based underpinning expertise and a wide range of facilities available to the whole community, including for research carried out using funding from non-thematic and thematic grants
- Organising the NCAS Affiliated Institutions scheme whereby universities and allied institutions with an active interest in atmospheric science research can become affiliated to NCAS. Currently NCAS has 36 Affiliated Institutions (26 universities and 10 NERC research and collaborative centres). By this means NCAS aspires to be an inclusive and representative organisation. The NCAS Affiliated Institutions take an active role in helping to steer future planning and the direction of atmospheric science research in the UK. Representatives of the Affiliated Institutions meet annually at the NCAS Affiliated Institutions' Meeting.
- Facilitating and co-ordinating the development of new NERC thematic programmes for and by the community
- Facilitating the development and exploitation of "external" co-funding opportunities, such as those associated with the European Commission and helping the UK atmospheric science community play a leading role in the emerging European Research Area
- Enabling universities to recruit and train atmospheric research scientists more effectively by actively promoting atmospheric science amongst students and providing funding, where possible, for research studentships and postgraduate training
- Working closely with NERC Research Centres and other NERC Collaborative Centres to increase knowledge of Earth System Science
- Establishing partnerships with the key users of atmospheric science research such as the operational agencies like the Met Office and the Environment Agency. NCAS builds on the good historical relationship with the Met Office. An example of the benefit of collaboration has been the joint synergistic use by the academic community and the Met Office of the same weather and climate model.
- Acting as a conduit and point-of-contact for the potentially wide range of users of the research produced by the atmospheric science community, including the public and the government. The Forum for Atmospheric Science and Technology, bringing together key government departments, NERC and others who are user stakeholders in atmospheric science research, is organised by NCAS
- Promoting communication between UK atmospheric scientists, such as by organising national conferences and workshops.
- Operating an NCAS human resources strategy that attempts to establish best practice amongst the partner universities that employ NCAS-funded staff and address the terms and conditions of employment of fixed-term contract research staff.
- Utilising an NCAS Advisory Group, comprising the NCAS Management Group and a group of environmental science experts from a range of institutions, including stakeholders, to provide independent advice to NCAS on its progress and development.
- Developing accessible science communications describing atmospheric science outcomes to a range of stakeholders including the public and to all levels of education.

As well as a mission, NCAS defines an overall objective for its research programme, and this objective is amplified within the Atmospheric Science Strategy document:

The objective of NCAS research is: to increase scientific knowledge of the atmosphere and of its role in the Earth System, including for improved prediction of global and regional change.

In the next section we describe in more detail the research strategy that NCAS has developed in association with the wider academic atmospheric science community.

5. Research Strategy

NCAS has taken the leading role in consulting with the UK atmospheric science community to produce an Atmospheric Science Strategy. During September and October 2003, an open consultation process occurred with the UK atmospheric science community for feedback on the Atmospheric Science Strategy document initially produced by the NCAS Management Group. This led to 38 separate responses (some on behalf of groups of people) containing 235 distinct comments on the Strategy. The intention is to update the Strategy document, as a consequence of these comments and further development of ideas by the NCAS Management Group, by June 2004. The document will be updated on a regular, probably annual, basis. The updated document is attached here.

“The Future of Our Atmosphere”

Atmospheric Science Research in the UK

- A Strategy updated in 2004 -

Purpose of the Strategy

This document summarises the UK atmospheric science research strategy and has been produced by the NERC¹ Centres for Atmospheric Science (NCAS) on behalf of, and in consultation with, the UK academic community and its stakeholders. It is a living document that captures the evolving scientific challenges in atmospheric science. It will be updated at regular intervals, approximately annually. Its purpose is to act as a stimulus and motivation to the UK academic community as it develops its detailed plans for research programmes and projects.

The Strategy: provides the overall objective of atmospheric science research; lists the main requirements for the research; describes the scientific and technical challenges, including the main outcomes of the research. A companion document describes the implementation of components of this strategy by NCAS and its collaborators.

Overall Objective of Atmospheric Science Research

The overall objective of UK academic research in atmospheric science and technology is:

To increase scientific knowledge of the atmosphere and its role in the Earth System, including for improved prediction of global and regional change

Requirements for UK Atmospheric Science Research

The main drivers of the scientific and technical challenges, determining current and future priorities for the atmospheric science academic community in the UK, are: the strategic requirements of the UK (its government and research councils, particularly NERC) and the needs of operational agencies (the Met Office and the Environment Agency) for atmospheric science research. Satisfying these requirements for atmospheric science research involves using and developing the expertise of researchers and having available excellent facilities for the research.

Science for a Sustainable Future - The Key Atmospheric Science and Technology Challenges

The atmospheric science and technology challenges outlined here result from an analysis of the requirements for this research and a consultation process involving the atmospheric science academic

¹ NERC is the Natural Environment Research Council

community. A critical document in this respect is NERC's "Science for a Sustainable Future: 2002 - 2007", which sets out its strategic scientific priorities for the UK environmental sciences community. These priorities over the next five years fall into three areas: **the Earth's life-support systems, climate change and sustainable economies**. Research in these three priority areas needs to be carried out by scientists whose expertise lie in atmospheric, marine, geological, terrestrial and freshwater sciences. Increasingly environmental science is carried out in a holistic multidisciplinary way linking these component disciplines into "Earth-system science".

Society and the economy are impacted by the variability associated with current climate and in particular severe weather events such as droughts, storms and floods. Therefore atmospheric science plays a vital role in relation to **sustainable economies**. Opportunities for society to mitigate the potential effects of these hazards and for economic exploitation also arise from the ability to predict local weather and episodes of **atmospheric pollution**, with associated deleterious effects on human health, materials, crops and natural ecosystems. **Climate change** is happening and atmospheric science is at the heart of climate system prediction models both in terms of the science needed to represent the weather systems and in terms of processes that determine the atmospheric composition. National objectives match those of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change i.e. *"to achieve stabilization of greenhouse gas concentrations in the atmosphere at a level that would prevent dangerous anthropogenic interference with the climate system. Such a level should be achieved within a time frame sufficient to allow ecosystems to adapt naturally to climate change, to ensure that food production is not threatened and to enable economic development to proceed in a sustainable manner."* Providing the science to enable society to implement sound policy to achieve this objective is a major challenge involving atmospheric science directly and via interactions with other areas of environmental science. A fundamental aspect of climate change is possible changes to the water cycle and the availability and sustainability of water quality. Air quality is of vital importance to human health and the biosphere. Thereby atmospheric science plays a critical role in improved knowledge and management of the **Earth's life-support systems**.

Here we provide a concise description of four interlocking scientific and technical challenges in atmospheric science research, which the UK academic community have identified.

Challenge 1: *To quantify global, regional and local changes to atmospheric composition and increase knowledge of the interaction of atmospheric composition with weather, climate and the biosphere*

Motivation:

Trace gases and aerosols in the atmosphere are central to urban and regional air quality, the oxidising capacity of the atmosphere, stratospheric ozone depletion and climate change. Chemical and physical transformations involving these atmospheric constituents are complex, interactive and non-linear; their impact could change dramatically during this century. Our ability to make predictions of composition changes over days or decades requires accurate observations, which inform and are informed by atmospheric models. Deduction of atmospheric composition in past climate regimes relies on measurement and interpretation of ice core and other records. Measurements and modelling proceed hand-in-hand; the models not only depend on experimental results, but also facilitate the design of experiments and the interpretation of these results. A key facet is the interaction of the biosphere and volatile organic compounds with the atmosphere and how this contributes to the determination of atmospheric composition. Within the Earth System the atmosphere is a critical compartment for biogeochemical cycles, which are themselves critical in climate and other environmental change.

Main Outcomes:

Development of a predictive capability of the risk of harmful compositional changes occurring either directly via effects of air quality on human health or indirectly via

coupling in the chemistry/climate system. This will need new and fundamental knowledge of changes, and effects due to these changes, in atmospheric composition.

These outcomes can be achieved through development of a coordinated and integrated UK network of researchers enabling a programme of research to be carried out that provides field and laboratory measurements relevant to understand atmospheric composition. This knowledge will inform the development of state-of-the-art numerical models. Opportunities for joining international networks must be actively pursued, particularly in the gathering of measurements of global atmospheric composition.

Challenge 2: *To increase knowledge of the small-scale physics and dynamics of the atmosphere so as to enable their accurate representation in climate and weather forecasting models; and to develop environmental prediction applications, such as air quality*

Motivation:

Societal and economic impacts of the environment, including those related to climate change, often involve weather phenomena. These are sometimes called *high-impact weather*. All atmospheric modeling applications ranging from climate, to weather and air pollution, have at their heart a need to represent weather phenomena.

Development of such weather systems involves cloud and rainfall formation, turbulence, radiation, nonlinear transport, mixing, atmosphere-surface interactions and convection. These occur on scales, which are typically less than 10km in the horizontal and 100m in the vertical. Weather forecasting and climate change prediction models represent these *processes* in an implicit way via *parametrization*. In models that predict environmental factors such as air quality they must be described more explicitly. Understanding and representation of these processes is a key limiting factor in successfully developing environmental applications of atmospheric science. This research requires observational campaigns using state-of-the-art instrumentation making direct measurements of processes such as of turbulence, cloud microphysics and aerosol and utilization of comprehensive local prediction models. Together these offer considerable opportunities to advance the science; integration of observations with prediction models via *data assimilation* being critical.

Improved prediction of both severe weather and hazardous local atmospheric conditions relies on scientific knowledge being translated into predictive models that both have as small an uncertainty as possible and that can provide as realistic as possible estimates of the uncertainty range, i.e. the risk of occurrence. The reduction and quantification of uncertainty in the predictive modeling system are key objectives of the research.

Main Outcomes:

Improved capability for skillful prediction of high-impact weather, climate change and air pollution by: better representation of physical and dynamical processes in relevant models and the development of improved data assimilation on process-resolving scales.

This can only be achieved in an integrated programme of field observations, operational observations, theory, regional and small-scale modelling and data assimilation. This research needs to be pursued as much as possible in partnership with the Met Office.

Challenge 3: *To increase knowledge of climate variability and change on timescales of weeks to millennia; to develop the capability to perform comprehensive simulations of the earth system on these timescales; and to establish the utility and skill of climate change predictions at the regional scale*

Motivation:

Climate change, its impacts and the development of strategies to adapt to, or mitigate those impacts, is arguably one of the greatest challenges facing mankind in the coming decades. The potential changes in our climate arise from the effects of human behaviour, and therefore depend on factors hitherto not encountered. Numerical models of the earth system, based on sound physical, chemical and biological principles, must therefore be the prime approach to providing well-founded predictions of climate change. Ecosystems and atmospheric chemistry are intricately coupled to the physical climate system, because they are sensitive to climate and because they control the concentrations of greenhouse gases and aerosols (which themselves affect climate). For this reason the extension of physical climate models to include biological and chemical components is seen as a major frontier in climate research.

The climate system varies naturally on all timescales from weeks to years and beyond. These natural modes of climate variability, such as El Nino and the North Atlantic Oscillation, can have a strong impact on regional climate. One of the key challenges for climate scientists is to determine whether current changes in our climate are part of these natural variations or whether they are signs of human-induced climate change. Furthermore, predicting how these modes of natural variability may be affected by global warming in forthcoming decades is a fundamental question that remains to be answered.

Main Outcomes:

More credible projections of chemistry/climate change at global and regional scales, and improved representation and better understanding of natural climate variability and the potential for climate 'surprises' in the context of a changing chemical environment.

This outcome will be facilitated by integration of earth system modelling activities across the academic community and via partnership between this community and the DEFRA/MoD-funded Hadley Centre to enhance the UK's capability in climate change science.

Challenge 4: *To maintain capability and develop further the fundamental underpinning technologies for observing and modelling the atmosphere, necessary to carry out atmospheric science research*

Motivation:

Methods of measuring and simulating the Earth system are based on development of instruments, numerical methods and software systems, and depend on the skills of the community. Our ability to answer new questions and refine our understanding of the Earth system will depend on strategic improvements in technology, the development of new expertise, and the ability to make the best use of existing and future data.

The UK atmospheric science community has at its disposal a world-class suite of ground-based and airborne observational facilities. It also has expertise in development of satellite instruments and utilisation of these observations. It is essential that we maintain the quality and competitiveness of our measurement infrastructure through the development of novel techniques. New atmospheric instruments are based on techniques that originate both inside and outside the atmospheric science community, in physics, chemistry and engineering laboratories.

It is important to interact closely with these communities, to identify new approaches and to influence and exploit their development in an atmospheric context.

Computational science plays an important role in atmospheric science research - by facilitating the use of state-of-the-art models in a variety of configurations; through the development of new methodologies for the sophisticated analysis of model and observational data; by exploiting the new opportunities afforded by e-Science to revolutionize information services and the sharing of data; by developing advanced numerical methods, such as adaptive mesh refinement. The expertise of atmospheric scientists in advanced modelling techniques is central to the aim of quantifying the Earth System.

Main Outcomes:

To maintain atmospheric science at the cutting edge of technological advances in observing the atmosphere, in the computational science of modelling the environment and in data curation; exploitation of the opportunities afforded by the expected rapid increases in computing power and by emerging e-Science technologies.

6. Examples of Agenda and Minutes from NCAS Management Group

As noted above, the main body in NCAS that provides overall management is the NCAS Management Group, which meets every three months for a whole day meeting. Here we provide examples of agendas and minutes (action items, which are circulated by email after each meeting) from NCAS Management Group meetings – those held on 16 December 2003 and on 1 April 2004.

NCAS Management Group Meeting

10am – 4pm, Tuesday 16 December 2003

Room B, MRC, London

AGENDA

- 10:00 - 10:30 Review of Action Items from previous meeting on 24 September 2003
(document #1 attached)
- 10:30 - 11:00 Decision on allocation of NCAS research studentships
(document #2 attached)
- 11:00 – 11:45 Discussion on AS Strategy document and community consultation
(documents #3 and 4 attached)
- 11:45 – 12:30 SMA and preparation of relevant paperwork
(document #5 attached)
- 12:30 – 13:00 Lunch
- 13:00 – 14:00 NCAS II Bid: structure and topics
- 14:00 – 14:30 Timetable for preparation of NCAS II Bid
(document #5 attached)

- 14:30 – 14:45 NCAS logo
(document #6 attached)
- 14:45 – 15:30 Discussion of operational issues for NCAS centres/facilities
- 15:30 – 15:45 NERC programme developments
- 15:45 – 16:00 Any Other Business (next meeting on Thursday 1 April 2004)
- 16:00 Meeting ends

**NCAS Management Group Meeting
16 December 2003: Action Items**

1. Action remains for Alan Thorpe to write to Directors of Personnel and Heads of Department concerning the NCAS HR Policy. It was also agreed he will also aim to meet HoDs to discuss the issues. **Action: Alan Thorpe**
2. A meeting on GCOS and monitoring will be arranged with senior management at NERC (John Lawton and/or David Lynn), Defra, Bryan Lawrence, Duncan Wingham (UCL, Chair of NERC's Earth Observation Expert Group). **Action: Paul Mason**
3. Dates for diaries: Convection workshop 6-8 January 2004; DIAC launch 27 January 2004; FAAM launch 23 April 2004.
4. List of potential organizers for RMS Conference 2005 in Exeter to be sent to the RMS by AJT (Note: Mike Pilling has a contact in chemistry department at Exeter who is interested in atmospheric science). **Action: Alan Thorpe**
5. The production of a UWERN brochure is needed and given the inevitable production time involved, this is becoming urgent. **Action: Paul Mason**
6. All NCAS Directors/Heads need to send information to Nicola Bray at CGAM to populate the NCAS Co-funding Database. **Urgent Action: All**
7. NCAS Research studentships. It was agreed to award these to the following proposers: DIAC funded (Hewitt, Reid), NCAS funded (Shine), CGAM funded (Graf, Chappell, Carslaw, Marshall, Shallerross), UWERN funded (ApSimon). **Action: Alan Thorpe (to inform applicants of outcome)**
8. Alan Thorpe will raise with John Lawton the difficulty some areas of atmospheric science have in finding CASE partners for research studentships. **Action: Alan Thorpe**
9. The AS Science Strategy will be updated with significant changes and associated input as follows:
 - (i) remove dates and re-label as a "Framework". **Action: Alan Thorpe**
 - (ii) in the preamble a few sentences are needed on EO, GCOS, GMES etc. **Action: Paul Mason**
 - (iii) include reference to EO (for verification not monitoring) in challenge 1. **Action: Mike Pilling**
 - (iv) include detection and attribution of climate change in challenge 3. **Action: Julia Slingso**
 - (v) the international dimension needs strengthening – research feeds into international context not just UK. **Action: Alan Thorpe**
 - (vi) a fuller mention of anthropogenic sources/sinks in challenge 1. **Action: Mike Pilling**

10. It was agreed that the NCAS SMA would be held in Reading (and may be also Cranfield) on 14 and 15 September 2004 (team to assemble on evening of 13 September). Action to include **FIRMLY** in all diaries of any likely NCAS participants. **Action: All**
11. The NCAS publications database (in CGAM website) needs populating. Any assistance to be provided by Katherine Bouton at CGAM. She will investigate linking this database to the NERC RoD database. **Action: All**
12. BADC will carry out a survey of users in preparation for the SMA. **Action: Bryan Lawrence**
13. Remote site research students/postdocs will take part in the SMA via Access Grid.
14. Material for SMA to be submitted by 15 July 2004. AJT will revise the SMA and NCAS II Bid timetable document and circulate in the light of these revisions. **Action: Alan Thorpe**
15. A new, and NERC-approved, NCAS logo has been created. Louisa Watts will be assisting NCAS Director/Heads and websites to become brand compliant over the next few weeks. **Action: Louisa Watts (via Alan Thorpe)**
16. Capital equipment round: it was agreed that Bryan Lawrence, Mike Pilling and Paul Mason will each submit a proposal to Alan Thorpe in January. Mike and Paul need to liaise to amalgamate ideas as appropriate. **Action: Bryan Lawrence, Paul Mason, and Mike Pilling**
17. Peter Jonas announced his intention to stand down at FAAM Head in June 2004. The new Head needs to be a full-time internationally respected scientist who works an average of 50% on FAAM headship.
18. A date for an extraordinary NCAS Management Group meeting on the NCAS II Bid will be sought for late February or early March (not Access Grid). **Action: Linda Tse**
19. Discussion on the NCAS II Bid resulted in several structural issues being raised.
 - (i) Aspects of NCAS II that are needed (here given in random order): new science strategy to include integrating topics and centre-specific focussed topics; management and development of services and facilities; core skills including prime movers and training.
 - (ii) Various integrating topics were discussed and their relationship to the already published 4 key challenges in the AS Strategy considered.
 - (iii) It was thought that NCAS II Bid ought to involve a 50% uplift (over 5 years) covering a 25% real increase and 25% inflationary rise.
 - (iv) It was agreed that by the end of January all members of Management Group (except Nigel Collins) would provide input to Alan Thorpe of up to 3 pages each under four-section headings. Alan Thorpe will circulate the template for this asap. **Action: All**

NCAS Management Group Meeting

10am – 15.45pm, Thursday 1 April 2004

Access Grid at Reading, Cambridge, UMIST

AGENDA

10:00 - 10:30 Review of Action Items from previous meeting on 16 December 2003
(document #1 attached)

- 10:30 - 11:30 Discussion of developments at NCAS centres/facilities
- 11:30 – 12:00 SMA and preparation of relevant paperwork
(documents sent previously)
- 12:00 – 12:30 Timetable for preparation of NCAS II Bid
(document #2 attached)
- 12:30 – 13:30 Lunch
- 13:30 – 14:30 NCAS II Bid: further discussion on structure and topics
- 14:30 – 15:00 Discussion on revised AS Strategy document and community consultation
(document #3 attached)
- 15:00 – 15:30 NERC programme developments
- 15:30 – 15:45 Any Other Business (next meeting on Wednesday 16 June 2004)
NCAS Affiliated Institutions meeting – 20 April 2004
Advert for NCAS Research Studentships
- 15:45 Meeting ends

**NCAS Management Group Meeting
1 April 2004: Action Items**

1. Action remains for Alan Thorpe to write to Directors of Personnel and Heads of Department concerning NCAS HR policy issues. **Action: Alan Thorpe**
2. A GCOS meeting with Defra and NERC is an ongoing action. **Action: Paul Mason**
3. Paul Mason will be producing a UWERN brochure by the end of 2004. **Action: Paul Mason**
4. BADC will be carrying a survey of its users prior to the SMA. **Action: Bryan Lawrence**
5. NCAS co-funding database is being populated. ACMSU has yet to do this. **Action: John Pyle**
6. NCAS research studentships: if they are not filled for October 04 entry, the PI can roll them forward by one year. Then if still unfilled they will be reallocated. We will go ahead with a block NCAS advert for currently unfilled studentship. **Action: Alan Thorpe**
7. John Lawton is to review the CASE rules regarding atmospheric science topics. This needs to be followed up with John Lawton. **Action: Andrew Kaye**
8. A science meeting/workshop on “aerosols in global models” is needed, with John Pyle as organizer. **Action: John Pyle**
9. There is a need for an information sheet to inform NERC and others of the rapidly developing UK portfolio in atmospheric composition research, emphasising areas of strength. **Action: Mike Pilling (with Louisa Watts)**
10. Bryan Lawrence will write to SOLAS Steering Committee (and BODC) about the role of BADC in data management in SOLAS. **Action: Bryan Lawrence**
11. There is an urgent need to finalize the job description of the Head of FAAM so that the post can be advertised. Alan Thorpe, John Foot, Peter Jonas and Nigel Collins need to meet. **Action: Nigel Collins**

12. SMA: COSMAS is not included; item 10 in ToRs need some rewording, but not to lose reference to the issue of staff career development. **Action: Alan Thorpe**
13. Alan Thorpe will check with Ally Lewis about the thinking on the use of “extreme” in the title of the integrating programme linking extreme weather to air quality. **Action: Alan Thorpe**
14. Julia Slings will ask Dave Frame if he will draft a Science and Society (one page) for the NCAS II Proposal. **Action: Julia Slings**
15. We have decided that the NCAS II Proposal themes would each involve several projects with a description of about 2 pages for each project. The deadline for receipt of these inputs is 16 April. Alan Thorpe will email a template of the document making it clear what is required as input. **Action: All**
16. It was agreed that we would split the Atmospheric Science Strategy document into two – one that is general for the whole community and one that describes the NCAS implementation plan. Input on changes to the document should be provided to Alan Thorpe by 11 June. **Action: All**
17. Andrew Kaye needs to raise with Phil Newton the issue of data management for QUEST and in particular the role of BADC. **Action: Andrew Kaye**

NCAS Science Management Audit

September 2004

The NERC Centres for Atmospheric Science comprises:

ACMSU: *Atmospheric Chemistry Modelling Support Unit*

BADC: *British Atmospheric Data Centre*

CGAM: *Centre for Global Atmospheric Modelling*

DIAC: *Distributed Institute for Atmospheric Composition*

FAAM: *Facility for Airborne Atmospheric Measurements*

UFAM: *Universities' Facility for Atmospheric Measurement*

UWERN: *Universities' Weather Research Network*

**ToR No. 3 – NCAS Procedures for Setting Research Aims,
Monitoring Progress and Evaluating Output**

ToR No. 3 – NCAS Procedures for Setting Research Aims, Monitoring Progress and Evaluating Output

1. Introduction

In this document we describe: the procedures NCAS uses to monitor annual aims and progress, including, as an example, the introduction to the 2003-2004 Annual Report; details about the NCAS Advisory Group including its membership, terms of reference and an example of the minutes of its 2004 meeting.

2. Procedures for Monitoring Annual Progress

NCAS has in place a variety of procedures to set research aims, monitor progress and evaluate output. A key aspect of these procedures is the annual reporting system that has various components. Each year the Directors/Heads of the seven centres/facilities within NCAS submit to the Director of NCAS their Annual Report. The deadline for receipt of this report is 1 April. The format of the report is the same for all centres/facilities with the following headings:

Section 1: Introduction

to include

- brief summary of scientific goals set at start of year
- changes that had to be made to programme/goals during the year, including staffing/funding
- other strategic developments of relevance affecting progress

Section 2: Scientific and Technical Outcomes

to include

- summary of main outcomes/progress from each of the projects listed in the NCAS activities spreadsheet
- prizes, awards, media activity and outreach by staff

Section 3: Goals for following year

to include

- summary of the main scientific goals being set for the next year
- discussion of how these follow-on from those during the current year
- note any substantive changes to the NCAS activities spreadsheet (updated spreadsheet applicable for following year to be provided in Annex)

Section 4: Highlights of current year

to include

- up to 4 highlights (up to a paragraph each) suitable for inclusion in the consolidated NCAS Annual Report or NCAS OPM returns. These will be a précis of aspects of the material in section 2.

Section 5: Publications

to include

- peer reviewed papers published
- contributions to book and monographs
- other outputs

Annex: Spreadsheet of NCAS activities

to include

- updated Spreadsheet of activities for the centre/facility for which this is the individual Annual Report

Annual Reports are not unduly long but they need to be sufficiently detailed so that when the Science Management Audit, SMA, of NCAS is carried out towards the end of each funding period, the SMA panel will be able to follow the logic of how priorities were set and evolved during the programme. A typical length of an individual Annual Report from each centre/facility may be between 5 and 10 pages, depending on the size of the overall activity. It is also envisaged that the text and publications can be used for the individual OPM returns, for inclusion in the NERC Research Outputs Database, and any other reporting material NERC may require. The Annual Reports of each centre/facility are amalgamated into the consolidated reports on the various research activities provided to the NCAS SMA process as part of the input to ToR No. 4.

The Director of NCAS reviews these reports to monitor progress and outputs. In addition the Director produces an overall NCAS Annual Report with an introductory section and the individual centre/facility reports as annexes, for submission to the NCAS Advisory Group. They review the report at their May annual meeting providing feedback. The introductory section of the consolidated NCAS Annual Report for 2003-04 is provided below at the end of this section.

Throughout the year, the quarterly NCAS Management Group meetings also monitors progress and outputs and from each of these meetings there is a written summary of action points. In addition the Director of NCAS also visits the various centres/facilities on an informal basis to monitor activity. Clearly the Director of NCAS is heavily reliant on the Directors/Heads of the centres/facilities in the setting of research aims and objectives. This is why it is critical that these senior NCAS staff are leaders in their field.

Research aims and objectives are also particularly scrutinised prior to the 4/5 yearly NERC SMA and re-bidding for a further period of NCAS funding. Part of this process is the development and updating of a UK Atmospheric Science Strategy. This Strategy is closely linked to NERC's overall strategy and is developed in consultation with the whole UK academic research community. For example during September and October 2003, an open consultation process occurred with the UK atmospheric science community for feedback on the Atmospheric Science Strategy document initially produced by the NCAS Management Group. This led to 38 separate responses (some on behalf of groups of people) containing 235 distinct comments on the Strategy. The intention is to update the Strategy document, as a consequence of these comments and further development of ideas by the NCAS Management Group. The document will be updated on a regular, probably annual, basis (see the current version reproduced in ToR No. 2). The NCAS Affiliated Institutions play a key role in setting the overall research agenda and at their annual meeting there is about half of the time devoted to discussion of this area (see ToR No. 5).

Finally the Forum for Atmospheric Science and Technology, of government department stakeholders meets annually and provides feedback to the Director of NCAS on their needs for atmospheric science research (see further information under ToR No. 6).

An example of the introductory section of the NCAS Annual Report is provided here:

NCAS Annual Report 2003-2004

1. Introduction

The NERC Centres for Atmospheric Science was established in September 2001 as a NERC Collaborative Centre to coordinate and manage the core-strategic atmospheric science research funded by NERC. This

NCAS Annual Report for 2003-04 also contains Annexes 1 to 6 that provide detailed annual reports for each of the component centres/facilities.

During September and October 2003, an open consultation process occurred with the UK atmospheric science community for feedback on the Atmospheric Science Strategy document initially produced by the NCAS Management Group. This led to 38 separate responses (some on behalf of groups of people) containing 235 distinct comments on the Strategy. The intention is to update the Strategy document, as a consequence of these comments and further development of ideas by the NCAS Management Group, by June 2004 (current draft of updated document is Annex 7). The document will be updated on a regular, probably annual, basis.

The Strategy and the feedback received, are assisting the NCAS Management Group in developing a first draft of the NCAS II proposal to be submitted to NERC by 31 October 2004 to extend NCAS funding from 1 April 2006 to 31 March 2011. A summary of the draft NCAS II proposal will be presented to the NCAS Advisory Group at its third meeting on 17 May 2004.

2. Scientific, Technical and Management Developments

2.1 Key strategic developments across NCAS during the year

The second meeting of the NCAS Advisory Group was held on 1 May 2003. The membership of the NCAS Advisory Group has undergone changes during this year. Dr Jim Wallace and Dr Alan Apling have both retired and have left the Advisory Group. From its third meeting on 17 May 2004, the NCAS Advisory Group membership will be extended to include Dr Martin Williams (Air Quality Division, Defra) and Professor David Fowler (CEH Edinburgh).

The Director of NCAR, Dr Tim Killeen, visited NCAS at the Universities of Reading and Cambridge, from 6-9 May 2003 to be appraised of the science being carried out in NCAS and to explore opportunities for collaboration. An area of special interest was the NERC DataGrid project led by Bryan Lawrence from BADC, which is already benefiting from dialogue between NCAR and BADC.

The Forum for Atmospheric Science and Technology, FAST, held its Seventh Annual Meeting, on 26 August 2003, of key government department and other stakeholders in atmospheric science.

Towards the end of 2003 a group of six Hadley Centre scientists moved to the Department of Meteorology, University of Reading to work with CGAM on various topics such as regional climate modelling and the detection and attribution of climate change. In addition Professor John Mitchell (Chief Scientist, Met Office) has an office at Reading and works there for one or two days per week. Ongoing discussions are taking place with the Hadley Centre concerning climate-modelling collaboration with CGAM. A regular series of bilateral discussions between senior members of the UK atmospheric science academic community and the Met Office have been initiated to occur every six months.

During this year the Director of NCAS continued as an *ad hominem* member of NERC's Science and Innovation Strategy Board, SISB, which makes recommendations to NERC Council on the direction and funding of NERC's scientific programmes. He has been made "SISB champion" for NERC's climate change theme. In February 2004, he also became a member of Defra's newly appointed Science Advisory Council, which replaces the Science Advisory Group. He has also been appointed to the EPSRC HECToR Management Board, which is responsible, on behalf of Research Councils UK, for the procurement of their next-generation national supercomputer facilities called HECToR (High End Computing Terascale Resources).

Discussions with the Met Office to ensure that a fast computer link between the NCAS academic community and the Met Office is available in Exeter have been successful. The plan, to be implemented in the next few months, is for a SuperJANET link initially at 100 Mbit/s, rapidly being upgraded to 500 Mbit/s. In addition the Met Office will install Access Grid rooms in Exeter.

Adequate availability of supercomputing resources remains a serious issue for NCAS. NERC is currently re-organising its national supercomputing allocation procedures and NCAS continues to be heavily involved in that process. NCAS was successful in persuading NERC to support strongly a proposal to the Government Spending Review 2004 for an upgraded national High-Performance Computing provision (HECToR). This proposal has been accepted by Research Councils UK as a commitment within its Large

Facilities funding line. We have been heavily involved in successfully arguing the case for a partnership to be established between Defra, the Research Councils and the Met Office to explore the potential for aligning supercomputer resources and procurements. A possible outcome would be a dedicated node for climate modelling shared between NCAS and the Hadley Centre.

The NCAS Management Group have put in place a new fully integrated observing facility, as a re-organisation of UFAM. This manages the NCAS specialised instruments within centres of expertise distributed across the community hosting instrument scientists with expertise in various observing techniques. This incorporates the previous ground-based instruments as well as new airborne specialised instruments (see Annex 6a). These instruments have been funded under the JIF and will be fully managed and funded by NERC when the JIF period is completed. Partnership with other groups is a vital part of both UFAM and FAAM; e.g., the Chilbolton Radar Facility (with the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory, Ofcom and the EPSRC) and the FAAM aircraft (with the Met Office). Links with the Met Office's Cardington facility will be explored in 2004-05.

A new FAAM Board has been established under the chairmanship of the Director of NCAS (first meeting on 2 February 2004) to provide oversight of the operation of the new joint NCAS-Met Office BAe 146 research aircraft. The refurbishment of the aircraft by BAe Systems has progressed slowly with some continuing difficulties (see Annex 6b).

The official launch of DIAC took place in London on 27 January 2004 with 130 attendees from the UK atmospheric composition science community and associated media coverage.

A new post of NCAS Science Communications Manager was established in September 2004. Dr Louisa Watts has taken up this (currently half-time) position and she is based partly at NERC Swindon and at the University of Reading. The post is to develop all aspects of communication of NCAS science including websites, web pages, brochures, press releases, liaison with stakeholders and learned societies, branding etc. A new NCAS logo compatible with NERC guidelines has been produced (see top of page 1 of this document) and an entirely new user friendly NCAS website has been designed and is about to be launched. Press releases in support of the Earth System Modelling Workshop (October 2003) and the launch of DIAC (January 2004) were issued and received significant visibility including via items on the BBC website. To improve our methods of communication, the NCAS Management Group met by Access Grid for two of its five meetings in 2003-04 (nodes available at Reading, RAL, Cambridge, Leeds and Manchester).

It was decided that as part of training the next generation of NCAS staff, we would commit funds to a set of nine NCAS research studentships to be openly competed for by the community. The requirement was that the research would explicitly be linked to an aspect of the research programme of an NCAS centre/facility. Awards were made to the Universities of Bristol, Cambridge, Imperial College, Lancaster, Leeds and Reading. The NCAS centres involved are: CGAM (five), DIAC (three) and UWERN (one). It is intended that the studentships commence at the start of the 2004-05 academic year in September/October 2004.

2.2 NCAS Funding

In a letter received on 30 July 2003, the Chief Executive of NERC agreed to the request of the Director of NCAS to "synchronise" NCAS funding so that all components of NCAS will end their current funding allocations on 31 March 2006. This required an additional allocation of a total of £2.45M to be made divided between UWERN, UFAM, BADC and the NCAS Directorate over the two years 2004/05 and 2005/06.

In addition NERC Council agreed to commit an additional £0.85M (until 31 March 2006) to support the specialised instruments, to be used on the new aircraft (as part of the newly re-organised UFAM), and their associated instrument scientists. It also allocated a further £0.5M to increase the NERC-held supercomputer budget, allocated to the NCAS consortium, for 2003-04. As part of its new funding line supporting international activities, NERC agreed to fund a proposal by NCAS/CGAM to support a dedicated project, and associated new staff, concerning climate modelling on the Japanese Earth Simulator. This funding which runs to 31 March 2006 is a total of £0.68M. The project is a joint one with the Hadley Centre – see Annex 1.

These substantial additions to the NCAS funding previously allocated to start in April 2002 means that the total budget is profiled as: £4.13M (2002-03), £5.90M (2003-04), £5.51M (2004-05) and £6.00M (2005-06). This can be compared to the pre-NCAS allocation to atmospheric science core-strategic programmes in

2001-02 of £3.63M (including £1M for the first phase of the Core Strategic Measurements for Atmospheric Science, COSMAS, programme that ends in 2004-05).

In summary, the annual funding from NERC available to the various components of NCAS during the period 2003-2004 has been approximately:

CGAM £1.36M, ACMSU £0.27M, UWERN £0.5M, DIAC £0.56M, BADC £0.63M, UFAM £0.71M, FAAM £0.5M, Directorate & initiatives £0.33M, others (including COSMAS) £1.04M

Two further proposals have been submitted to NERC to supplement NCAS funding further. The first of these is to create a DIAC Atmospheric Aerosols Network (see Annex 4) within the knowledge transfer funding line and the second is for new equipment for computing and for atmospheric measurements.

The NCAS II proposal for funding of NCAS from 31 March 2006 to 31 March 2011 has to be submitted to NERC by 31 October 2004 for final consideration by the Science and Innovation Strategy Board at its meeting in February 2005.

2.3 Significant Research Initiatives from NCAS

Successful Framework 6 proposals submitted by NCAS scientists either as coordinators or as contributors include: Integrated Projects on stratospheric chemistry (SCOUT) coordinated by Professor John Pyle from ACMSU and on climate change (ENSEMBLES) by Professor Julia Slingo from CGAM; a Network of Excellence on atmospheric composition (ACCENT) by Professor David Fowler, CEH Edinburgh, in association with DIAC; a STREP on the dynamics of the coupled climate system (DYNAMITE) by staff from CGAM.

A consortium grant proposal to NERC led by Alan Blyth, manager of UFAM - the Convective Storms Initiation Project – was successful. This will entail a set of projects linking several university groups and the Met Office. It includes an extensive field campaign centred at the Chilbolton radar area. A consortium grant proposal to NERC led by Julia Slingo - the UK-HiGEM Project – was successful and will involve collaboration with the Hadley Centre on high-resolution climate modelling. The Flood Risk from Extreme Events, FREE, thematic project proposal was submitted to NERC in October 2003 and the Director of NCAS was a lead author of the proposal. NERC have reviewed the proposal and have asked for some small changes to be made before finally deciding whether or not to fund the proposal at SISB's May 2004 meeting.

Three further initiatives in collaboration with the Met Office have started this year. The first is to develop a next-generation chemistry-climate model; UK Chemistry and Aerosols model UKCA, managed by NCAS/ACSMU. This involves, Olaf Morgernstern, a research assistant funded by NCAS/ACMSU and, Fiona O'Connor, a postdoctoral scientist employed by the Hadley Centre. The second project concerns aerosol modelling for climate and is funded by NCAS and involves a research assistant working for Dr Ken Carslaw at the University of Leeds working with the Hadley Centre. John Pyle also coordinates this project. (A linked consortium grant application was made to NERC in January 2003 in this area and narrowly failed to be funded and it will be re-submitted this summer. The community is considering developing an aerosols thematic programme proposal to submit to NERC.) The third initiative is to create a DIAC Atmospheric Aerosols Network and we are seeking NERC knowledge transfer funding for this.

Another project that has developed much further during this year is the UK-Japan collaboration on global climate modelling. Two collaborative projects are being pursued in parallel with the UK side being a jointly managed activity between NCAS/CGAM and the Hadley Centre. The first project is with the climate-modelling group at the University of Tokyo (funded by the Japanese research council MEXT) and the second is direct with the Director-General of the Earth Simulator, Professor Sato. Appointment of two new CGAM staff based full-time at the Earth Simulator and a further one at Reading is in the final stages of completion. Visits by the UK team to Japan have thus far led to the new Hadley Centre model, HadGEM1, being successfully installed and run on the Earth Simulator.

2.4 Meetings organised by NCAS

The "RMS Conference 2003" was organised by the Royal Meteorological Society, in association with NCAS, and held from 1 to 5 September 2003 at the University of East Anglia in Norwich. This

incorporated the annual UWERN and UGAMP conferences within sessions devoted to: Climate Processes and Climate Change; Weather and Small-scale Phenomena; Atmospheric Composition; Data Assimilation for Weather Forecasting & Climate Research; Earth Observation and Satellite Meteorology; Media Meteorology; Societal and Economic Impacts. NCAS provided considerable financial support for students and post-doctoral research assistants to attend the meeting. The conference was very successful and attended by 416 people. There were 25 UK universities with atmospheric science research contributions to the conference, accounting for 69% of the attendees. This conference, intended as a series of biennial conferences, represents a significant investment by NCAS in building and strengthening the UK research community.

NCAS organised three experts' workshops this year. The first was an Earth System Modelling workshop was held from 1-3 October 2003 co-organised by NCAS and the National Institute for Environmental eScience at the University of Cambridge. Invited speakers included those from NCAS, DARC, Hadley Centre, Tyndall Centre, Earth Simulator (Japan), NERC and MPI-Hamburg. The workshop was very well attended and publicised and was also an opportunity to further develop the UK-Japan climate-modelling project.

The second experts' workshop was "Aerosol Modelling for Climate Research", 13-14 November 2003 at Cosener's House, Abingdon, UK. Its primary aim was to solicit expert advice from the UK community on what aerosol quantities and processes need to be incorporated in the UKCA model. A secondary, though important, aim was to strengthen links between the detailed aerosol, cloud and radiation work in the UK and the expertise with climate models and climate change that exists in the Hadley Centre. It brought together 25 UK scientists and one from Canada to identify the most pressing aerosol-climate interactions and to develop a strategy for representing aerosol processes in the UK's next-generation climate model.

The third experts' workshop was "Convection Experts workshop", 6-8 January 2004 at Farnham Castle, UK. This reviewed the performance of convective parametrisations in climate and global weather prediction models, to consider the current state of convective parametrisation and suggest how convection schemes might be further developed to address the major problems in current models. The 29 experts who attended were from France, Germany, USA, ECMWF, Met Office and the NCAS (UWERN and CGAM) community.

The Director of DIAC organised a DIAC Launch event around a one-day scientific discussion meeting with 130 participants on 27 January 2004 in London.

2.5 Strategic Developments at NCAS centres and facilities

The individual annual reports from each of the NCAS centres and facilities are included as Annex 1 (CGAM), 2 (ACMSU), 3 (UWERN), 4 (DIAC), 5 (BADC), 6a (UFAM) and 6b (FAAM) attached to this NCAS Annual Report. Here we highlight some strategic developments in the NCAS centres/facilities that took place this year.

Professor Lesley Gray and Dr Jonathan Gregory were appointed as CGAM senior scientists during this year. Jonathan Gregory is part funded by NCAS (80%) and part by the Hadley Centre (20%) as a joint appointment to investigate aspects of climate change including sea-level rise. Lesley Gray is leading CGAM research on stratospheric climate processes. A CGAM Brochure was published this year "Climate in a Changing World" to showcase the climate science that CGAM is involved in.

The following metrics give an indication of BADC usage in 2003-04: 1300 identifiable users downloaded 10 TB of data in 6 million files over this period; 1116 users have registered this year bringing the total to 4898; the number of users registered for one or more datasets or services is 2724 and the number of users actively using the datasets and services was 1293; approximately 1100 queries were answered this year.

A UWERN mesoscale modelling workshop was held on 13 February 2004 to review the status of community mesoscale modelling in the UK. The event attracted 40-50 researchers from across the UK. Also the UWERN Unified Model support web pages have been re-written and improved. UFAM has been re-organised, under Alan Blyth as manager, and overseen by the newly formed UFAM Management Team under the alternating chairmanship of the Directors of UWERN and DIAC. The UFAM Management Team had its first meeting on 9 March 2004.

The Head of FAAM, Professor Peter Jonas, is retiring in June 2004 and plans to advertise for his replacement are advancing. The University of Cambridge is to receive additional funding from NCAS so that the Head of ACMSU, Professor John Pyle, will be released from 10% of his university duties, thus allowing him more time to devote to NCAS activities.

DIAC has awarded funding to Principal Investigators at the Universities of Birmingham, Cambridge, Leeds, UEA, UMIST and York to deliver its Science Plan.

2.6 NCAS Affiliated Institutions

The second annual meeting of the NCAS Affiliated Institutions will be held on 20 April 2003. The aim of affiliation is to provide a "greater NCAS" and a forum to discuss the coordination of UK atmospheric research and to enable NCAS to become an inclusive organisation. The current Affiliated Institutions include 26 universities and 10 NERC research centres and each has nominated a lead and a deputy contact senior scientist.

3. Strategic Goals for following year

It has been decided by NERC that NCAS will have a Science Management Audit on 13/14 September 2004. The NCAS Management Group has had opportunity to nominate members of the SMA team and to comment on the terms of reference. Two major strategic goals for 2004–05 are to contribute to a successful SMA of NCAS in September 2004 and to be successful with the NCAS II proposal to NERC.

A critical goal during 2004-05 is to further encourage excellent research to be carried out across NCAS. Special attention will be paid to making the new aerosols and chemistry-climate projects with the Hadley Centre a success and to accelerate progress on the UK-Japan climate-modelling project. Partnerships will continue to be the critical aspect of the NCAS strategy with that with the Met Office being of special importance. The EC Framework projects that NCAS scientists take part in are vital to the NCAS response to the European Research Area. Continued effort will also be devoted to developing partnerships with other NERC centres. The successful utilisation of the FAAM facility is a major goal for 2004-05.

During 2004-05 we intend to explore a set of measures to provide improved employment contracts and career development for NCAS contract research staff.

4. Scientific and Technical Highlights of current year

In order to give a flavour for the scientific results that have been produced this year we mention four of the highlights taken from those in Annexes 1 to 6 from the individual centres and facilities in NCAS.

Threatened loss of the Greenland Ice-Sheet

In collaboration with the Hadley Centre, CGAM has shown that the Greenland Ice-sheet is likely to be eliminated as a result of anthropogenic climate change unless much more stringent reductions in emissions are made than those expected by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). Based on the range of model results from the IPCC Third Assessment and for various emission scenarios, it has been shown that temperatures over Greenland, particularly during summer, will exceed the critical temperature of 2.7°C (where melting exceeds snowfall) before 2100 and, in some scenarios, within the next few decades. Over the next millennia it is possible that the whole Greenland Ice-sheet may be lost, except for a few inland glaciers, leading to a catastrophic sea level rise of 7 metres. This research also suggests that once the ice-sheet is lost, the chances of it reforming are much reduced due to a lower and less reflective surface over Greenland.

Interaction of ENSO and tropospheric ozone content

Results from a 12-year simulation, carried out by ACMSU, covering 1990-2001 show that El Nino and La Nina events have strong impacts on the year-to-year cycle of tropospheric ozone. It is found that there are close dependencies between ENSO signals and stratosphere-troposphere exchange (STE). Changing patterns of circulation and meteorology in El Nino and La Nina years result in significant changes of ozone-rich air transporting from the stratosphere to the troposphere. We calculate a large increase of STE in a typical El Nino year followed by an increase of lower stratospheric ozone abundance. This phenomenon is most evident following the 1997-1998 El Nino event. In contrast, La Nina events result in a decrease in

STE. STE is a driving force in determining chemical lifetimes of ozone in the troposphere and is essential for ozone budgets in both the stratosphere and troposphere.

Urban turbulence and dispersion

Measurements of concentration fluctuations have been made by UWERN in wind tunnel simulations of pollution emission in street canyons. These high frequency data were filtered to simulate the output of the slower response instruments used in field studies of concentration statistics in street canyons. Strong low frequency correlations across the street canyon on a time scale of minutes were found. This indicates the importance of bulk variability within the street canyon flow (i.e. build-up and ejection of pollutants). Similar low frequency characteristics were also found in new numerical model simulations of boundary layer flow over groups of buildings that have been completed recently. The simulations have also been shown to be direct numerical simulations of laboratory measurements made at ENFLO, so that all scales of the motion are computed explicitly. The results offer unique insights into the complicated flow field, and will help understand dispersion in urban areas.

Surface ozone and hot weather

A temperature of 100°F (38°C) was recorded for the first time in August 2003 in the UK, and ozone levels were the highest recorded for over a decade, possibly the highest since 1976. As part of a detailed study into photochemical air pollution, DIAC scientists within the TORCH campaign made extensive measurements near London in August 2003 of many chemical species which either cause the production of ozone or are produced simultaneously. The highest ozone concentration recorded (153 ppbv) was well above the brief exposure threshold for human health. It occurred on the hottest day and may have been partly caused by emissions of a natural hydrocarbon (isoprene) from vegetation, particularly oak trees. These emit large amounts of isoprene when temperatures reach 35°C. Research is ongoing to understand the interaction between weather and tropospheric chemistry leading to such extreme ozone concentrations.

5. Publications

These are provided within the Annexes from each centre and facility.

3. NCAS Advisory Group – Example of Minutes

The NCAS Advisory Group comprises 8 external members, who have expertise across the range of atmospheric science, and the NCAS Management Group. The Advisory Group has annual meetings in May. The membership in 2004 is as follows:

External members:

Professor Huw Davies (Chair)	ETH Zürich
Professor David Fowler	CEH
Mr Trevor Guymer	SOC
Dr Andrew Kaye	NERC
Dr John Mitchell	Met Office
Dr Tim Palmer	ECMWF
Professor Geraint Vaughan	University of Wales, Aberystwyth
Dr Martin Williams	Defra

NCAS Management Group members:

Dr Tony Cox	University of Cambridge
Professor Peter Jonas	NCAS/FAAM, UMIST
Dr Bryan Lawrence	NCAS/BADC, Rutherford Appleton Laboratory
Professor Paul Mason	NCAS/UWERN, University of Reading
Professor Mike Pilling	NCAS/DIAC, University of Leeds

Professor John Pyle
Professor Julia Slingo
Professor Alan Thorpe

NCAS/ACMSU, University of Cambridge
NCAS/CGAM, University of Reading
NCAS, University of Reading

The Terms of Reference for the NCAS Advisory Group are as follows:

Terms of Reference for the NCAS Advisory Group

1. To advise the Director of NCAS on the core atmospheric science research programme and the allocation of resources.
2. To monitor the overall NCAS programme and programme management.
3. To monitor the progress, and evaluate the results, of individual projects in order to provide feedback to NCAS.
4. To recommend to NERC the membership of a review group to undertake an independent audit of the programme, at the appropriate times.
5. To monitor the implementation of data management plans for the programme in accordance with the NERC Data Policy.
6. To provide reports on the progress of NCAS when requested by NERC.
7. To monitor the requirements of NCAS for resources and, if appropriate, advise and/or assist NCAS scientists to assemble and present a case for additional investment.
8. To encourage NCAS to:
 - a. develop and maintain close links with other groups involved in atmospheric science research, both in the UK and internationally; and
 - b. publicise NCAS activities ensuring as far as possible that its work is fully recognised.

An example of the minutes of the NCAS Advisory Group are as given below:

Third NCAS Advisory Group Meeting

Monday 17 May 2004
CGAM, Department of Meteorology, University of Reading

DRAFT MINUTES

Present: Professor Huw Davies (Chair) (ETH Zurich),
Mr Nigel Collins (NERC), Dr Tony Cox (Cambridge),
Professor David Fowler (CEH), Mr Trevor Guymer (SOC),
Professor Peter Jonas (NCAS/FAAM, UMIST),
Dr Andrew Kaye (NERC), Dr Bryan Lawrence (NCAS/BADC, RAL),
Professor Paul Mason (NCAS/UWERN, Reading),
Dr John Mitchell (Met Office), Dr Tim Palmer (ECMWF),
Professor Mike Pilling (NCAS/DIAC, Leeds),
Professor John Pyle (NCAS/ACMSU, Cambridge),
Professor Julia Slingo (NCAS/CGAM, Reading),
Professor Alan Thorpe (NCAS), Professor Geraint Vaughan (Aberystwyth),
Dr Martin Williams (Defra)

Apologies: Dr Robin Bidwell, (Environmental Resources Management) - who has decided to resign from the Advisory Group.

1. Matters Arising

- 3(a) A meeting between AQEG/Defra/SORG is being arranged for Oct/Nov 2004.
- 3(h) Web-based co-funding and publication databases have been put in place.
- 3(i) A poll of BADC users has been carried out.
- 3(k) A new post of NCAS Science Communications Manager has been created and carried out (50%) by Louisa Watts since September 2003. Louisa has developed a new logo and website and is working on the NCAS PR strategy.
- 3(l) NERC SISB has been made aware of NCAS successes in FP6.
- 4(e) New terminology replacing "high-impact weather" has been devised for the NCAS II Proposal.
- 5 The Chairman had written to John Lawton about the need for synchronization of NCAS funding. This was subsequently agreed to by NERC resulting in an award of £2.45M to synchronize NCAS activities to a common renewal date of 31 March 2006.

2. NCAS Strategic Development 2003-04

- (a) The emerging linkage between BADC and NEODC needs to be monitored to ensure no dilution of BADC activities/excellence.
- (b) The new UWERN microscale modelling project will be discussed in more depth at the next meeting of the Advisory Group. **Action: Chairman**
- (c) Discussion took place on the commissioned (co-funded) research in NCAS and of possible contracts with government departments such as Defra. An appropriate initial way forward would be for NCAS funded projects to work in collaboration with Defra projects.
- (d) The point was made that field programmes such as NAMBLEX and TORCH had been very effective in bringing the community together.
- (e) Certification of the BAE 146 aircraft is still pending with some unresolved issues with CAA (that are being actively pursued).

3. CGAM Science Programme

A presentation by 2 research students and 2 senior scientists of ongoing research on climate science by CGAM was made to the Advisory Group. Various detailed points on the science were discussed.

4. NCAS II Proposal Discussion

All items to be considered as action items for the NCAS Management Group

- (a) The general structure of science (S) and technology (T) themes and an integrating activity (I) with a set of associated workpackages was thought to be appropriate.
- (b) NERC were urged to provide as soon as possible the different evaluation criteria needed for the S, T and I themes. **Action: Andrew Kaye**
- (c) In the Introduction it would be useful to bring out the complementarity and differences between NCAS research and that of the Met Office.

- (d) The point should be made in the Introduction that NCAS is new, there is no alternative structure that will work and that it has a strong community buy-in.
- (e) In describing “why NCAS”, the mixture of delivery of near term priorities and the capability to react to future developments needs to be brought out.
- (f) The strong international dimension of NCAS research, e.g. in FP6, must be stressed.
- (g) The nature of the connection between CGAM research and that of the Hadley Centre needs to be clearly described (in a form acceptable to all parties).
- (h) NCAS is encouraged to consult Defra with a draft of the proposal.
- (i) It was felt that there should be just one workpackage labelled “integrating activity” with a number of examples of immediate priorities being provided. These will need to be pursued with other stakeholders. A further priority, with existing UK academic sector strength, is stratospheric-tropospheric exchange processes. The issue of how best to describe the integrating activity within the Proposal and how it links with the other workpackages was discussed.
- (j) An outcome of the research in the weather area is the development of advanced parametrizations (process research being perceived of as a strength of NCAS). A critical area involves rainfall and other water component information and how this is brought into the data assimilation process
- (k) S12 and S15 on urban air quality need to be amalgamated. Defra felt that it was very good to see NCAS bringing the meteorological and chemical components together for the first time.
- (l) The T2 theme should include instrument development but laboratory measurement should be moved into the science themes.
- (m) Each S workpackage needs to stress its relationship to the overall science challenges (in the AS Strategy).

5. Any Other Business

- (a) The format of the next meeting was discussed. It was thought that a meeting with an overnight stay might be worth trying and with an agenda that more explicitly asked questions of the Advisory Group. A possible venue is the University of Leeds with a focus on UWERN science.
- (b) The Chairman will write to: Alan Apling, Jim Wallace and Robin Bidwell thanking them for their contributions to the Advisory Group. **Action: Chairman**
- (c) The Chairman thanked Peter Jonas and Nigel Collins for their significant contributions to NCAS over the years, as this was their last meeting before retirement.

6. Date of Next Meeting

It was agreed that mid to late May is a good time of the year for the Advisory Group meeting. A suitable date will be arranged. **Action: Linda Tse**

4. NCAS Research Management Team Minutes

The NCAS Management Group also acts as the NCAS research management team. Therefore examples of its minutes are given in the input to ToR No. 2.

NCAS Science Management Audit

September 2004

The NERC Centres for Atmospheric Science comprises:

ACMSU: *Atmospheric Chemistry Modelling Support Unit*

BADC: *British Atmospheric Data Centre*

CGAM: *Centre for Global Atmospheric Modelling*

DIAC: *Distributed Institute for Atmospheric Composition*

FAAM: *Facility for Airborne Atmospheric Measurements*

UFAM: *Universities' Facility for Atmospheric Measurement*

UWERN: *Universities' Weather Research Network*

ToR No. 4 – Reports on NCAS Programmes

ToR No. 4 – Reports on NCAS Programmes

1. Management Summary

In this section reports are provided of the various NCAS programmes. The NCAS I proposal agreed for funding by NERC, and which is the subject of this SMA, set out a research and services/facilities programme to be delivered over the period of the funding from 1 April 2002 to 31 March 2006. This overall NCAS programme was described in that proposal under three research headings: climate processes and change, hazardous weather and atmospheric composition. In addition the proposal referred to the provision of data stewardship services and observational facilities for the community.

In this section we provide reports under each of the headings described in the NCAS I proposal. The contributions that have been made to the delivery of the proposed research and services by the contributing centres/facilities are described. These reports presented here from each of the centres/facilities have been compiled predominantly from the individual Annual Reports produced by each of the centres/facilities.

2. Climate Processes and Change

In the area of climate processes and change, research and services are provided by CGAM at the University of Reading and for chemistry-climate interactions, they are provided by ACMSU at the University of Cambridge. Both CGAM and ACMSU were the subject of an SMA during September 2001. The combined report of the SMA 2001 team noted that: “The science and mode of delivery were excellent”; “The team was very impressed with the science ... and ... that all objectives had been fully met”; “The proposed science was ... of the highest quality and in an area of rapid development”; “The panel strongly recommend that NERC support the continuation of CGAM/ACMSU at the requested value”. In summary, the SMA 2001 report was extremely complimentary about the outcomes achieved by these two centres over the previous 5-year period.

I: CGAM – a full report is provided as **Annex A** on activities from Oct 2001 to present

II: ACMSU – a full report is provided as **Annex B** on activities from Oct 2001 to present

3. Hazardous weather

In the area of small-scale processes and weather, labelled in NCAS I as “hazardous weather”, research and services are provided by UWERN, which is distributed amongst several universities.

UWERN – a full report is provided as **Annex C** on activities from Oct 1997 to present

4. Atmospheric Composition

As explained under ToR no. 10, the aspirations outlined in the NCAS I proposal in the area of atmospheric composition had to be curtailed because of the reduced funding level awarded. However a new set of research activities and services in atmospheric composition was initiated by setting up the new Distributed Institute for Atmospheric Composition, DIAC. As this is a new activity there are as yet few outcomes of this programme – the official launch of DIAC being in January 2004. However for completeness we provide here a progress report on these activities provided by DIAC, which is distributed amongst several universities.

DIAC – a progress report is provided as **Annex D** for information

5. Data Stewardship

In the area of data stewardship (now called “data curation”), research and services are provided by BADC at the Rutherford-Appleton laboratory. BADC was the subject of an SMA during October 2000. The report of the SMA 2000 team included the following comments: “An excellent service for the level of resources invested”; “BADC has been at the forefront on online data access and provision, and has taken the lead in NERC data cataloguing in this area”; “The panel were very impressed by the level of achievement attained by BADC, with limited resources. A grade of Excellent had only been missed by the narrowest margin, mainly because of two weaknesses: data archaeology and promotion of the centre’s work”. In summary the report of the SMA 2000 team was very complimentary about the outcomes achieved by BADC over the previous period.

BADC – a full report is provided as **Annex E** on activities from Jan 2001 to present

6. Observational Facilities

In the area of field measurements NCAS has had the role of establishing a structure for these activities following the end of the period of Joint Infrastructure Funding (a separate government funding initiative to re-furbish UK academic laboratories and related infrastructure). Specialised instruments for measurements made from the ground or on-board an aircraft are maintained and developed by UFAM, which is distributed across several universities. The new joint facility with the Met Office, providing a research aircraft (the BAE 146) for the community, has been established as FAAM, which is located at Cranfield University. As these activities are only just beginning progress reports on both UFAM and FAAM are provided here for completeness.

I: FAAM – a progress report is provided as **Annex F** for information

II: UFAM – a progress report is provided as **Annex G** for information

7. Summary Publication Data

In Table 1 the number of publications in internationally peer-reviewed journals produced by staff at NCAS is provided. These figures are calculated from the NCAS publications database, which can be viewed and searched on the following website:

http://www.cgam.nerc.ac.uk/publications/ncas_pubs.php

On average over the three full years 2001, 2002 and 2003, the annual number of papers for the three research-dominated centres that are involved in this SMA is 78 (that is an average of 26 per centre), for service-dominated facilities it is 8 (an average of 4 per facility) and so overall there are **86 papers per year for NCAS**. (Note that is compared with the funding received by each centre/facility as a measure of value-for-money in ToR No. 7.)

(As UWERN reports on its science output since 1998 in Annex C, we here note that for the previous years not given in Table 1, the total papers published in international peer reviewed journals by UWERN were as follows: 1998 - 3, 1999 - 16, 2000 - 21.)

NCAS Publications

	2001	2002	2003	2004	Total
Centres					
ACMSU	18	12	18	10	58
CGAM	50	39	41	29	159
UWERN	17	17	22	32	88
Total Centres	85	68	81	71	305
Facilities					
BADC	4	2	6	3	15
UFAM	3	0	8	11	22
Total Facilities	7	2	14	14	37
TOTAL NCAS	92	70	95	85	342

Table 1: NCAS Publications 2001-2004

Note 1: DIAC and FAAM not included as they have only recently been established

Note 2: Publication figures for 2004 include information available up to July

8. Latest ISI Publications

The complete list of peer-reviewed papers is provided in the relevant section of each Annex of ToR No. 4 describing the outputs of each research and facility programme in NCAS. In addition the peer-reviewed publications can be viewed and searched at the following website address:

http://www.cgam.nerc.ac.uk/publications/ncas_pubs.php

**NERC Centres for
Atmospheric Science**
NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

NCAS Science Management Audit

September 2004

The NERC Centres for Atmospheric Science comprises:

ACMSU: *Atmospheric Chemistry Modelling Support Unit*

BADC: *British Atmospheric Data Centre*

CGAM: *Centre for Global Atmospheric Modelling*

DIAC: *Distributed Institute for Atmospheric Composition*

FAAM: *Facility for Airborne Atmospheric Measurements*

UFAM: *Universities' Facility for Atmospheric Measurement*

UWERN: *Universities' Weather Research Network*

**ToR No. 5 – NCAS National and international links;
technology expensive projects; coordinating
distributed major programmes; fostering
multi-disciplinary approaches**

ToR No. 5 – NCAS National and international links; technology expensive projects; coordinating distributed major programmes; fostering multi-disciplinary approaches

1. Summary

In this document the following aspects of NCAS activities are described: national linkages including the NCAS Affiliated Institutions (including a membership list and minutes of the last meeting in 2004) and the link with the Met Office; international links; statistics on co-authorship of NCAS publications; membership of committees by NCAS staff; the NCAS regional role; examples of collaborative research; examples of coordination of programmes by NCAS.

NCAS aspires to be an inclusive organisation involving as many of the UK national academic community as possible in as many aspects of its operations as is appropriate and feasible. The NCAS Affiliated Institutions represent the formal end of these linkages and involvement. Also NCAS is a distributed organisation with about 18 UK universities receiving funding from NCAS. This distributed structure means that NCAS has excellent national links and in fact its structure was designed with that in mind.

NCAS encourages universities, and allied organisations, to become Affiliated Institutions of NCAS. The benefits of affiliation involve active participation in the strategic planning and execution of the UK's atmospheric science research programme. Representatives from the Affiliated Institutions meet annually at the NCAS Affiliated Institutions' Meeting. The existence of the NCAS Affiliated Institutions:

- Provides coordination where appropriate and adds value for atmospheric science research in the UK
- Creates a forum for discussion of issues that are either obstacles to progress or opportunities for synergy between parts of the atmospheric science research community
- Enables regular review of the UK atmospheric science research portfolio to identify gaps and areas needing additional support
- Provides a mechanism to report to funding agencies, such as NERC, on strategic issues of importance
- Contributes to the organisation, via the Royal Meteorological Society, of their biennial conferences on atmospheric science
- Facilitates and stimulates the development of new ideas for thematic and other programmes attractive to funding bodies, such as research councils or the European Commission.

The designation of NCAS Affiliated Institution is given to any academic-related organisation that supports atmospheric science research. Invitations to join the scheme are directed at university vice-chancellors and each university that wishes to join must provide a lead and deputy contact person for their institution, one of whom must attend the annual meeting. The current list of NCAS Affiliated Institutions is as follows:

NCAS Affiliated Institutions

Academic members:

The University of Birmingham
The University of Bristol
CLRC Rutherford Appleton Laboratory
University of Cambridge
Cardiff University
The University of Edinburgh

University of Essex
University of Hertfordshire
Heriot-Watt University
Imperial College, London
Lancaster University
University of Leeds
The University of Leicester
University of Nottingham
University of Oxford
Queen Mary, University of London
University of Reading
The University of Salford
University of Southampton
University of Strathclyde
University of Surrey
University College London
UMIST
University of East Anglia
University of Wales, Aberystwyth
The University of York

NERC Research and Collaborative Centre members:

British Antarctic Survey
British Geological Survey
Centre for Ecology and Hydrology
Centre for Terrestrial Carbon Dynamics
Data Assimilation Research Centre
Environmental Systems Science Centre
Plymouth Marine Laboratory
Proudman Oceanographic Laboratory
Southampton Oceanography Centre
Tyndall Centre

As an example, the Minutes arising from the Second Annual Meeting of the NCAS Affiliated Institutions are reproduced at the end of this section.

The link NCAS has in the UK with the Met Office has a special significance as the Met Office has about 300 scientists involved in atmospheric research and development activities. Individual scientists within NCAS have extensive research collaborations with individual Met Office scientists. As well as these individual links, the Met Office established a group of its scientists at the University of Reading - the Joint Centre for Mesoscale Meteorology, JCMM - in 1988 in the Department of Meteorology with Alan Thorpe as overall Coordinator. This recognised the common interest in weather research and in field measurements. This developed into a strong link between the wider UWERN community and the JCMM particularly after the then Director of Research at the Met Office, Professor Keith Browning moved to Reading to become Director of both the JCMM and then UWERN when it was established in 1998. In addition there are now Met Office scientists from the Hadley Centre (6 staff) working with CGAM in the Department of Meteorology at the University of Reading. This brings the total number Met Office staff working at Reading alongside NCAS scientists to about 30. Soon, there will also be a member of the Met Office, working with ACMSU, in the Department of Chemistry at the University of Cambridge.

In the last year we have initiated a project called UK Chemistry and Aerosols (UKCA) that involves scientists funded by NCAS at Cambridge and Leeds and Hadley Centre scientists. This is proceeding under the project management procedures used by the Met Office for large projects of this nature. The

Earth Simulator UK-Japan collaborative project on climate modelling is again a joint NCAS-Hadley Centre activity. The UK-HiGEM project funded by NERC involves significant collaboration with the Hadley Centre and a range of UK universities. The new aircraft operated by FAAM is a joint activity between NCAS and the Met Office. NCAS is supporting a postdoctoral position at Reading on mesoscale data assimilation to work closely with Met Office staff in the JCMM. That researcher is being line managed by a Met Office staff member. A member of the BADC is working full-time in Exeter at the Met Office's headquarters to facilitate the use of Met Office data by the UK academic community. Many of these projects are technology expensive (using the aircraft and supercomputers for example) and require an organisation with the mission of NCAS to carry them out.

The linkage between NCAS and the Met Office is discussed at regular meetings held every 6 months between Met Office directors and NCAS/academic community scientists. Currently this involves: Dr John Mitchell (Chief Scientist Met Office), Dr David Griggs (Director Hadley Centre), Dr Alan Dickinson (Director NWP), Professor Alan Thorpe (Director NCAS), Professor Paul Mason (Director UWERN), Professor Brian Hoskins (a non-executive director of Met Office) and Dr Andrew Kaye (NERC Swindon). In addition Julia Slingo is a member of the Met Office Scientific Advisory Committee. Stephen Mobbs (UWERN PI) was a member of the MoD Expert Panel on Sustaining Scientific Excellence at the Met Office, during 2001-2004.

International linkage is also very good. A list of international collaboration and projects is provided within the reports of the centres/facilities given in Annexes A to G. As an example only we here mention European linkages in the Framework programmes. NCAS scientists have been particularly successful in winning Framework 6 contracts to collaborate with European colleagues. Successful Framework 6 proposals submitted by NCAS scientists either as coordinators or as contributors include: Integrated Projects on stratospheric chemistry (SCOUT) coordinated by Professor John Pyle from ACMSU and on climate change (ENSEMBLES) by Professor Julia Slingo from CGAM; a Network of Excellence on atmospheric composition (ACCENT) by Professor David Fowler, CEH Edinburgh, in association with DIAC; a STREP on the dynamics of the coupled climate system (DYNAMITE) by staff from CGAM. In February 2004 the Director of NCAS was invited to, and attended, a high-level EU meeting at Dublin Castle to discuss Framework 7 and the concept of a European Research Council.

Minutes arising from the Second Annual Meeting of the NCAS Affiliated Institutions are given here:

**NCAS Affiliated Institutions Meeting
Tuesday 20 April 2004**

Summary of Discussion Points

NCAS Support for the Community

1. HIRDLS measurements when they become available will be an issue for BADC to consider.
2. There is a need to link the work of Wendy Garland at BADC (air pollution data specialist) to the developing discussions within the mesoscale modelling and air pollution group of UWERN.
3. There are no plans at the moment to support data assimilation for climate modelling within CGAM.
4. Data from the Japanese Earth Simulator climate simulations will be a resource for the community. The new Research Council procurement for the next UK supercomputer (HECToR) is making good progress.
5. There is a need to link the research in NCAS on small-scale, regional and global air quality.
6. There is a need for an even better dialogue than at present between measurement programmes (e.g. of atmospheric composition) and modelling including prior to and during field campaigns.

7. The developments of GUIs at CGAM and BADC need to be fully coordinated and integrated.
8. A strategy issue is the extent to which NCAS has funding to support the development and utilisation of the wide range of existing and potential new specialized instruments that exist in the community. At the moment the short-term plan is to spend about 20% of the NCAS budget on this activity.
9. There was a question as to the process that needs to be in place for new specialized instruments to be accepted for and mounted on the FAAM aircraft.
10. Discussion continues to be needed to coordinate the use of different building scale/urban air quality models, especially given the development work by UWERN on a new model. The DAPPLE project will be providing observations of use in evaluation of new models.
11. The Environment Agency pointed out that they have increasing need for fully-interactive nested modelling and that this ability to model across a wide range of scales is becoming increasingly important.
12. It was pointed out that it is important to identify policy users for long-term monitoring. Without this it is hard for Research Councils to sustain funding for such activities.
13. The ACCENT network of excellence in atmospheric composition (funded by FP6) has begun and this should be viewed as a new version of EUROTRAC. It will support travel and meetings etc.
14. When considering the issue of air quality, the involvement of the devolved administration and their agencies (such as SEPA) is important.
15. There is a need to ensure that there are ample opportunities for individual scientists to be actively involved in NCAS. Mechanisms include: attending (and suggesting topics for) NCAS workshops, responding to AOs for research studentships and research projects, contributing to NCAS strategy meetings, using NCAS services and facilities.
16. Whilst NCAS has had significant successes in winning Framework 6 funding, we need to continue to actively get the most out of the EC opportunities.

Atmospheric Science Strategy

17. Opportunities should be sought to use the AS Strategy to influence government directly on the future direction of research funding. It can also be used to assist directed programmes like SOLAS in devising their Science Plan. It should also be used as input to NERC's planning process for its next science strategy.
18. The word "prediction" has multiple meanings such as: forecasting, simulation, attribution etc and these should probably be spelt out in the Strategy document.
19. Much more needs to be introduced on the economic benefits of atmospheric science research to justify the requirements of the research. The potential benefits of skilful seasonal forecasts were noted.
20. Listing scales such as global, regional and small-scale draws attention to possible differences in, for example modelling, approaches whereas the science is increasingly unifying these and bridging across the scales.
21. We need to stress more the multidisciplinary aspects of what we do. It is at the interface between atmospheric science and other disciplines that many research challenges exist. This means that we need to continue to work with other NERC centres and scientists.

22. NCAS is uniquely placed in the breadth of the research it is involved with, to provide independent advice to government and other departments on policy-relevant issues. This is worth developing.
23. Core strategic support for underpinning techniques in Earth Observation seems to be lacking from the EO area of NERC. This impacts on the capability of the atmospheric science community. The new Centre of Earth Observation Instrumentation is an opportunity to help correct this situation.
24. To help focus what is otherwise a very broad overall objective, the AS Strategy should perhaps consider stressing the benefit to the UK of the research more clearly.

NCAS II Proposal

25. We need to be careful to clearly describe the necessarily complex structure of the proposal in simple terms. The word "project" may not be a good one as it implies a time-limited activity with very specific deliverables. "Activities" may be a better word.
26. There is a question whether the services and facilities sub-sections in each theme should be pulled out into a single section.
27. The philosophy behind NCAS research is that it provides a kernel of activity. This should be built upon by also encouraging non-thematic grant applications and thematic programme development in the same areas. Then the total activity in any one of the atmospheric science topics will be greatly increased to make an overall significant programme for the UK. Emerging examples are: aerosols and rainfall leading to flooding.

NCAS Science Communications

28. The linkages between the new NCAS website and the component centres/facilities websites needs careful attention. As much information as possible should be sent from individual centre webmasters to Louisa Watts about new things being placed on their websites that should be mirrored on the NCAS site. The aim is that the central NCAS website will be the portal for external users to gain entry to the community, as well as acting as a resource for the Atmospheric Science community itself.

2. NCAS Co-authoring of papers statistics

In this section we give statistical information in Table 1 on the number of authors of NCAS peer-reviewed publications with the co-authors being partitioned amongst: NCAS, co-academic, industrial and international.

NCAS Publications: co-author statistics 2002, 2003 and 2004

Centre/facility	Pubs	Total authors	Total co-authors	NCAS %	Academic %	Industrial %	International %
ACMSU	40	339	299	5%	40%	6%	49%
BADC	11	33	22	0%	50%	32%	18%
CGAM	106	393	287	24%	36%	13%	27%
UWERN	71	251	180	38%	48%	3%	11%
Total	228	1016	788	17%	44%	14%	26%

Table 1: NCAS Publications, co-author statistics 2002, 2003 and 2004

Note: Statistics provided for ACMSU, BADC, CGAM and UWERN

Co-authors are those in addition to the single lead author

Co-authors are sub-divided into: other NCAS, UK academic, industrial and international

3. NCAS Membership of Committees

The Director of NCAS, Alan Thorpe, is a member of Defra's Science Advisory Council, NERC's Science and Innovation Strategy Board, EPSRC's HECToR Management Board, the steering committee for NERC's directed programme in e-Science, NERC's Earth Observation Expert Group, the Steering Committee for NERC's UTLS Ozone directed programme and a previous member of the national e-Science Steering Committee. He is also chairman of the Steering Committee for NERC's directed programme COAPEC. He is co-chairman of the International Science Steering Committee of the WMO's research programme THORPEX.

ACMSU Staff:

Professor John Pyle (ACMSU) was a member of the NERC Science and Innovation Strategy Board (SISB) and Chair of the NERC Atmospheric Science Peer Review Committee until mid-2003. He is Chair of Defra's Stratospheric Ozone Review Group, a member of the EU DG Research Science Panel on Atmospheric Science (formerly the Science Panel on Stratospheric Research) and a member of the Royal Society Global Environmental Research Committee (GERC). Dr Glenn Carver is a member of the Royal Meteorological Society's Meetings Committee.

BADC Staff:

Bryan Lawrence:

- Member of NERC Data Management Advisory Group (2000 to current)
- Member of the NCAS Management Board (2002 to current)
- Member of NERC steering committees for:
 - Clouds Water Vapour and Climate Thematic Programme (2001 to current)
 - Data Assimilation Thematic Programme (2001 to current)
- Member of the following e-science committees:
 - CCLRC e-science (2000-2001, 2004 to current)
 - NERC ad-hoc e-science committee (2001)
- Programme and Organisation for the All Hands Meeting (2003,2004)
- Member of the:
 - U.K. Joint Infrastructure Systems sub-committee in support of Research (JCSR, 2003 to current)
 - International Commission for the Middle Atmosphere (2000 to current)
 - National Digital Curation Centre Research Committee (2004 to current)
- Co-Organiser: Global Organisation for Earth Science Portal Meetings (2003,2004)

Martin Jukes:

- Member of Organisation Committee for Atmospheric Sciences section of EGU
- Associate Editor for the Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society
- Secretary of the Dynamical Problems specialist group of the RMS

Anne De Rudder:

- Member of URGENT DMQA Committee (2000 to July 2002)
- Member of Polluted Troposphere Steering Committee (2002 to 2004)
- Attend UTLS Ozone Steering Committee meetings (2003 to current)
- Attend RAPID Climate Change Data Management meetings (2003 to current)
- Attend FAAM Operations Committee meetings (2002 to current)

Wendy Garland:

- Member of UFAM Utilisation Committee (2004-present)
- Member of Polluted Troposphere Steering Committee (2004-present)

Ag Stephens:

- Member of UFAM Utilisation Committee (2002-2003)

CGAM Staff:

- NERC Peer Review College (Lesley Gray, Julia Slingo, Rowan Sutton)
- NERC COAPEC Steering Group (Rowan Sutton)
- NERC RAPID Steering Group (Julia Slingo)
- NERC UTLS Steering Group (Lesley Gray)
- NERC Earth Observation Expert Group (Lesley Gray)
- NERC CPOM Steering Committee (Jonathan Gregory)
- NERC Autosub Under Ice Steering Committee (Jonathan Gregory)
- Vice-President, Royal Meteorological Society (Julia Slingo)
- Associate Editor, Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society (Rowan Sutton)
- Met Office Scientific Advisory Committee (Julia Slingo)
- Met Office Portable Unified Model Project Board (Paul Burton, Lois Steenman-Clark)
- Met Office FLUME Review Panel (Paul Burton)
- Hadley Centre Tiger Teams for development of HadGEM1 (Pete Inness, Julia Slingo)
- Consultant for review of convective parametrization in the UM (Mike Blackburn)
- GECC Supercomputing Subcommittee for development of SR2004 Bid for HECToR (Julia Slingo)
- Working Group for the UK Academic HPC Procurement (Lois Steenman-Clark)
- Chair, CSAR User Liaison Forum (Lois Steenman-Clark)
- HPCx Science and Technology Advisory Committee (Lois Steenman-Clark)
- HECToR Project Working Group (Paul Burton)
- HIRDLS Programme Steering Group (Lesley Gray)
- IAMAS Representative, Royal Society IUGG Panel (Julia Slingo)
- POL Expert subgroup on the Global Sea level Observing System (Jonathan Gregory)
- RCUK Trends and Opportunities Panel (Lois Steenman-Clark)
- Edinburgh Parallel Computing Centre MSc Guest Lecturer (Paul Burton)
- Southeast Climate Change Partnership Panel (Emily Black)
- Co-Chair, CLIVAR Asian/Australian Monsoon Panel (Julia Slingo)
- Chairman of Advisory Group, Physics of Weather and Climate Group, Abdus Salam International Centre for Theoretical Physics (ICTP), Trieste (Julia Slingo)
- Director for International Conference on 'Monsoon Environments: Agricultural and Hydrological Impacts of Climate Change' held at ICTP and attended by 120 scientists from 39 countries (Julia Slingo, Emily Black)
- Course Lecturer and systems support for Helmholtz Institute Summer School on Scientific Supercomputing in Climate Research, Potsdam, August 2002 (Julia Slingo, Andy Heaps)
- Coordination of EU FP5 project on 'Predictability and variability of monsoons: Agricultural and hydrological impacts of climate change (PROMISE)' (Julia Slingo).
- Coordination of EU FP5 project on 'Mechanisms and predictability of decadal fluctuations in Atlantic-European climate (PREDICATE)' (Rowan Sutton)
- Coordination for FP6 Integrated Infrastructure Initiative on 'Coordinated Access to the PRISM Earth Model and Data System (CAPRI)' (Eric Guilyardi)
- Member, CLIVAR Atlantic Panel (Rowan Sutton)

- Chair, Scientific Organizing Committee, International Workshop on 'Role of the Indian Ocean in Climate Variability over India' (Julia Slingo)
- Chair Organizing Committee 'CLIVAR Workshop on Atlantic Predictability', University of Reading (Rowan Sutton)
- Lead Author, Working Group I, IPCC Fourth Assessment Report (Jonathan Gregory)
- Joint coordinator of WGNE Aqua-Planet Experiment (Mike Blackburn)
- Joint coordinator of WCRP CMIP experiment on the THC (Jonathan Gregory)
- Joint author of the CF NetDCF metadata standard (Jonathan Gregory)
- Co-Chair SCOSTEP Climate and Weather of the Sun Earth System (CAWSES) WG1 (Lesley Gray)
- Co-Organiser, European Meteorological Society Conference Session on Middle Atmosphere Variability (Lesley Gray)
- Co-coordination for FP6 Integrated Project on 'Ensemble prediction of climate change and its impacts (ENSEMBLES)' (Julia Slingo)
- ENES Working Group on European Supercomputing (Eric Guilyardi)
- EU PRISM Steering and Executive Committees (Eric Guilyardi)
- Editor, The Journal of Earth Simulation, Earth Simulator Centre, Japan (Julia Slingo)

DIAC:

Professor Mike Pilling (DIAC) is a member of the Steering Committee for NERC's directed programme, SOLAS. He is also involved in the following committees:

(i) Government

Air Quality Expert Group (AQEG), Chairman M J Pilling: AQEG gives advice to Defra on concentrations of pollutants and on likely future exceedences of Air Quality Objectives. It has made one report on NO₂; a second report on Particulate Matter is about to go out for consultation. Defra has commissioned reports on Climate Change and Air Quality and on Urban Ozone.

Air Quality Assessment Group on the third runway at Heathrow, Modelling Group: Chairman M J Pilling. The Government White Paper on Aviation, published in December 2003, stated that the third runway at LHR would only be constructed if questions on future air quality impacts could be resolved. The Department for Transport has established three working groups, on Modelling, Measurements and Emissions that will report on a two-year timeframe.

(ii) Learned Societies

Royal Society of Chemistry (RSC): Professor Mike Pilling is the President of the Faraday Division and a member of RSC Council and of the Science and Technology Board.

(iii) Europe

Steering Group for the European Photoreactor at Valencia

UWERN PIs:

Keith Browning: founder member of World Weather Research Programme, Scientific Steering Committee

Paul Mason: Chairman Global Climate Observing System (GCOS) Steering Committee, Chairman FREE pump priming committee

Chris Collier: Member of the WMO World Weather Research Programme Nowcasting Working Group; coordinator of the EU Framework V MANTISSA (Microwave Attenuation as a New Tool For Improving Stormwater Supervision Administration) Project 2001-2004; an expert on the EU COST-717 Project Assimilating radar data into hydrological and meteorological models 2001-2004, and was a member of the EU COST Committee for Meteorology 2003-2004; member of the Inter-Agency Committee for Hydrological Uses of Radar Data; member of the DEFRA/EA Flood Forecasting Theme Advisory Group; Vice President of the Royal Meteorological Society 2000-2002 and 2003-2004, and was elected President in June 2004 for the next two years.

Stephen Mobbs: Member of the American Meteorological Society Mountain Meteorology Committee 2004-2007; member of the Steering Committee of the T-REX programme (Terrain-induced Rotor EXperiment) - international project based in the USA; UK representative on the MAP Steering Committee; member of the MoD Expert Panel on Sustaining Scientific Excellence at the Met Office 2001-2004; member of the Met Office Scientific Advisory Committee 1996 - present.

Stephen Belcher: Associate Editor Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society Royal Meteorological Society March 2004- present; Associate Editor Boundary-Layer Meteorology Kluwer Academic Publishers, June 2003- present; Co-organiser, Isaac Newton Institute Research Workshop Surface Water Waves; Member Atmospheric Science Peer Review Committee Natural Environment Research Council. October 1999 –September 2003; member of the Scientific Steering Committee of NERC's Programme Surface Ocean Lower Atmosphere (SOLAS) April 2004 – present.

3. NCAS Regional Role

NCAS plays a significant regional role simply because of its structure as a widely distributed organisation spread across the UK universities. NCAS sites are located in the regions covered by the following: North-West, East Midlands, East of England, South West of England Regional, London and South-East England Development Agencies; Yorkshire Forward; Advantage West Midlands; Welsh Development Agency. As yet NCAS has only informal links established with Regional Development Agencies. An example of a recent discussion with a Regional Development Agency concerns UWERN collaborators at Salford and UMIST. A proposal was constructed with several SMEs and companies to submit to the North-West Development Agency Science Fund aimed at delivering a working system for operational air traffic control that will visualise current and near-future aircraft vortex risk based upon sodar measurements and modelling. By bringing university groups together within the NCAS family, atmospheric science is better placed to respond to these types of initiatives. There is also a strong link emerging between DIAC members at the Universities of Leeds and York who are part of the White Rose partnership concerning atmospheric composition research.

4. Examples of Collaborative Research and Coordinating Programmes

NCAS has been involved in a wide range of collaborative research within the UK and internationally and it has also been very active in coordinating such programmes. As these two aspects of collaboration are intimately related we deal with them together here. Also as there have been so many such programmes we give here only some illustrative examples. The highest profile international collaboration is the UK-Japan climate modelling collaboration involving use of the Earth Simulator in Yokohama. The UK contribution itself is collaboration between NCAS, via CGAM, and the Hadley Centre. It arose from Science Ministerial level agreement to collaborate on climate research. Soon there will be three CGAM and three Hadley Centre staff working on the project with four of these staff full-time in Japan. NERC are supporting this activity with a contract to NCAS from its International funding line. The research involves using the Hadley Centre new climate model at higher resolution than has been possible on UK computers.

Alan Thorpe led the development of the science proposal successfully submitted to NERC, and subsequently funded, for a new directed programme in Flood Risk from Extreme Events, FREE. He has also played and continues to play a major role in the development of the WMO's THORPEX research programme on weather predictability. NCAS has sponsored a number of UK community workshops to promote collaborative projects, including on: aerosols, convection, future chemical threats, urban meteorology and urban chemistry. The UK Chemistry and Aerosols project is a collaborative programme that NCAS has initiated with the Hadley Centre. There is also a collaborative project with the Met Office group at Reading on mesoscale data assimilation with NCAS contributions from Reading and Salford.

ACMSU has played a major role in the coordination of research both within the UK and within Europe. In the UK, John Pyle was one of the proposers of the NERC UTLS thematic programme and the programme management is in Cambridge. Dr Kathy Law, formerly ACMSU-supported, was the programme manager until she took up a CNRS appointment in France and now Dr Helen Rogers is the manager. John Pyle is the coordinator of the new EU Framework 6 SCOUT integrated project (~60 partners) as well as the on-going SCENIC project on aviation impacts. ACMSU also has wide-ranging research links, in the UK (e.g. within a number of collaborative NERC UTLS projects), within the EU (partner in: POET, RETRO, HIBISCUS, CANDIDOZ, QUOBI, SCENIC, THALAZ projects during this reporting period) and worldwide (e.g., a new collaboration to study the H₂-economy with NIWA, New Zealand).

The BADC is currently working with the World Data Centre for Climate at the Max Planck Institute for Meteorology (MPIM, Hamburg) on methods to make data held at MPIM and BADC available to users of both data centres. The BADC is currently one of the co-leaders in the development of the Global Organisation for Earth System Science Portals (GO-ESSP). This is a confederation of key software developers and data providers whose main aim is to provide better community access to scientific data. BADC is likely to be a key player in the development of long-term support of data for the European PRISM federation. BADC is a member of the European Network for Earth Simulation (ENES), and was asked recently to present options to the ENES federation on how to use grid technology for Europe-wide access to key simulation and observational data sets. BADC is leading the collaborative NERC DataGrid project. The BADC is providing advice for the Met Office IT re-engineering project. The BADC is providing advice for the National Digital Curation Centre. The BADC was asked to provide advice on the establishment of a data portal for the Marine community.

CGAM has the responsibility for coordinating and supporting the UK Universities' Global Atmospheric Modelling Programme (UGAMP), a network of excellence in climate modelling and research. During this period, the number of institutions affiliated to UGAMP has grown, and there are currently 22 groups spread across 15 institutions. Coordination of UGAMP has involved the organisation, with ACMSU, of the UGAMP Annual Conference in Cambridge in April 2002 and September 2004. Glenn Carver (ACMSU) has continued to edit the annual UGAMP Newsletter, which regularly attracts a large number of contributions covering an enormous breadth of climate science. CGAM supported the participation of UGAMP researchers in the RMS National Conference at UEA in September 2003 at which a special UGAMP session was held to inform UGAMP of the latest developments in modelling, computing and software. CGAM staff have visited various UGAMP sites during the last two years.

Within the wider NERC community, CGAM has provided the leadership for the UK-HiGEM consortium, which seeks to integrate the top-end earth system modelling activities across the NERC Centres and with the Hadley Centre. CGAM is also leading the NERC component of the UK-Japan collaboration to exploit the Earth Simulator for coupled climate-chemistry-ecosystem modelling for predictions of the 21st century. We have also played an important role in the scientific leadership and support for the NERC COAPEC Thematic Programme by serving on the Scientific Steering Group and by hosting two members of the core team.

During the current contract CGAM has built on its earlier success in participating and leading European Union (EU) funded projects. CGAM was coordinator of the EU Framework 5 PROMISE

(*Predictability and variability of monsoon: Agricultural and hydrological impacts of climate change*) and PREDICATE (*Mechanisms and predictability of decadal fluctuations in Atlantic-European climate*) projects, and also has a leading role in the EU PRISM project concerned with the development of the infrastructures for climate modelling in Europe. CGAM has also had a prominent role in the development of successful Framework 6 proposals and will be a key player in the new projects '*Ensemble-based Predictions of Climate Changes and their Impacts (ENSEMBLES)*' and '*Dynamics of coupled models of climate variability (DYNAMITE)*'. Within ENSEMBLES, CGAM will coordinate the Research Theme on '*Understanding the processes governing climate variability and change, climate predictability and the probability of extreme events*'.

CGAM scientists have continued to take a leading role in major international programmes such as WCRP CLIVAR and the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP), and in the SCOSTEP CAUSES programme (see Section 2.2). CGAM has played a leading role in the coordination of the WGNE Aquaplanet Model Intercomparison Experiment (APE), and, in 2005, will host the WGNE-sponsored APE Workshop.

CGAM has hosted several international workshops on focused science topics. Of particular note, in April 2004, was the international CLIVAR workshop on Atlantic Predictability. The context for this workshop includes a new WCRP initiative to renew focus on the importance of predictability. The workshop was seen to be a pioneer within CLIVAR and attracted considerable funding from NOAA and the Met Office as well as NERC. Over 60 scientists from more than 20 countries took part. CGAM has also proposed an international workshop on the mechanisms of solar influence on climate to be held at the International Space Science Centre in Bern, Switzerland in 2005.

Julia Slingo is also strongly involved with coordination of an interdisciplinary project at the University of Reading on "Water, Life and Civilisation" funded by the Leverhulme Trust.

Mike Pilling led the development of the science proposal successfully submitted to NERC and subsequently funded for a new directed programme in Surface Ocean Lower Atmosphere Study, SOLAS. He has also been involved in the following EU Framework 6 programmes: *ACCENT* Network of Excellence on the tropospheric composition; *SCOUT* Integrated Programme; *EUROCHAMP* Integrated Facilities project on Atmospheric Chambers; European Science Foundation Networks on Biogenic Compounds and on Chemical Mechanisms. Tony Cox is scientific coordinator for the NERC directed programmes *COSMAS* and the *Polluted Troposphere*.

The Convective Storms Initiation Project, CSIP, is supported by a consortium grant from NERC with lead PI being Alan Blyth, Head of UFAM and co-investigator being Keith Browning, ex-Director of UWERN.

NCAS coordinates and manages the usage by UK atmospheric scientists of national supercomputing facilities including the CSAR and HPCx services. This involves monitoring usage, providing advice to current and new users, membership of the relevant planning committees and training in the use of certain models by the NCAS community. Lois Steenman-Clark (CGAM) is the NCAS high-performance computing manager. In addition NCAS has taken part, and is doing so currently for HECToR, in the process to procure the next national supercomputing service.

**NERC Centres for
Atmospheric Science**
NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

NCAS Science Management Audit

September 2004

The NERC Centres for Atmospheric Science comprises:

- ACMSU:** *Atmospheric Chemistry Modelling Support Unit*
- BADC:** *British Atmospheric Data Centre*
- CGAM:** *Centre for Global Atmospheric Modelling*
- DIAC:** *Distributed Institute for Atmospheric Composition*
- FAAM:** *Facility for Airborne Atmospheric Measurements*
- UFAM:** *Universities' Facility for Atmospheric Measurement*
- UWERN:** *Universities' Weather Research Network*

ToR No. 6 – Knowledge Transfer; users; data and advice

ToR No. 6 – Knowledge Transfer; users; data and advice

1. Summary

In this document the following NCAS activities are summarised: major customers/users of NCAS research/facilities; research that benefits policy-makers, including as communicated via the Forum for Atmospheric Science and Technology; knowledge transfer and uptake of services/facilities; NCAS science communications.

2. List of major customers and users

- Met Office, including the Hadley Centre
- Other operational weather forecasting centres such as particularly ECMWF
- Other NERC Research and Collaborative Centres (including those that are NCAS Affiliated Institutions)
- UK Government Departments, particularly those that are members of the Forum for Atmospheric Science and Technology (FAST), but also including the Government Chief Scientific Adviser
- UK academic community (including the NCAS Affiliated Institutions) as users of NCAS facilities:
 - Specialised instruments for atmospheric measurement from UFAM
 - BAE 146 research aircraft from FAAM
 - Atmospheric data from BADC
 - Global atmospheric and climate modelling support from CGAM and ACMSU
 - Regional modelling support from UWERN
 - Support in using national, and international, supercomputers from CGAM
 - Support in using chemical mechanisms, databases and models from DIAC
- International Agencies, e.g., World Meteorological Organisation (e.g. WCRP and THORPEX), IPCC, FAO and ICTP

3. Research that benefits policy makers

Much of the research that NCAS carries out is policy-relevant. ACMSU is involved in policy-related research relevant to IPCC and the WMO/UNEP assessments of stratospheric ozone. John Pyle was a lead author in the last WMO/UNEP assessment and is currently convening lead author for an IPCC/TEAP special report on the interactions between chemistry and climate, with special emphasis on ozone-depleting substances and their replacements. In 2003 John Pyle spoke about the WMO/UNEP ozone assessment process at a special seminar for the House of Lords Committee on Science and Technology as part of their investigation into international scientific agreements. ACMSU is currently funded by DTI (and Airbus UK) to look at aspects of the environmental impact of aviation. ACMSU scientists have published work this year on the H₂-economy.

DIAC members work closely with Defra and have direct contracts on tropospheric ozone and on particulate matter. Defra have shown particular interest in the 2003 TORCH campaign in Writtle, Essex, where intensive measurements were made during the August ozone episode.

Communication of NCAS research and its strategy to UK Government departments also occurs via the Forum for Atmospheric Science and Technology, FAST. It was established in 1996 as a

stakeholder group composed primarily of representatives from UK government departments. It has held annual meetings since then and the Director of NCAS became its chairman in 2001.

Role of FAST

To provide a forum for informed interaction between the major stakeholders to discuss top-level objectives and departmental needs and so ensure a full understanding of the directions in which each organisation is moving in the area of atmospheric science.

Terms of Reference of FAST

- To share information on the strategic aims and policy drivers of the participating organisations.
- Map NERC strategic science objectives to the policy drivers of Government Departments
- Identify strategically important areas to which NERC should contribute.
- Identify potential opportunities and threats.
- Examine the directions in which atmospheric science in the UK is moving.
- Take an overview of international programmes in atmospheric science and to comment on potentially valuable interactions.
- Maintain awareness of the extent to which ideas are implemented and collaboration optimised.

From the viewpoint of NERC, such a discussion is beneficial for forming its own priorities for new or continuing research programmes and in providing independent endorsement of its proposals.

Meetings are held once per year, usually in August, but additional meetings can take place if necessary.

Membership of FAST as of 2003:

Professor A J Thorpe, Chairman, Director NCAS
Dr A J Apling, Department for Transport
Dr B Callander, Ministry of Defence
Mr N R Collins, NERC
Professor B J Hoskins, Royal Society's Global Environment Research Committee
Dr J F B Mitchell, Met Office
Dr W Maton-Howarth, Department of Health
Dr H Pilcher-Clayton, EPSRC
Dr J Startup, Department of Trade and Industry
Dr R Timmis, Environment Agency
Mr D A Warrilow, Department of Environment, Food and Rural Affairs
Dr L Watts, NERC (Secretary)

Minutes of FAST meeting held on 16 August 2002:

IN CONFIDENCE

FORUM FOR ATMOSPHERIC SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY (FAST)

Unconfirmed Report of the Sixth Meeting held on 16 August 2002.

The Sixth meeting of FAST was held in Room E at the MRC, 20 Regents Crescent, on 16 August 2002 starting at 1000 hrs and ending 1300 hrs.

Present: Professor A J Thorpe (NCAS, Chair), Dr A J Apling (ODPM), Dr B Callander (MoD), Dr D Griggs (Met Office), Professor B J Hoskins (GERC), Dr A Keddle (DTI), Mr D A Warrilow (DEFRA), Mr N R Collins (NERC, Secretary), Dr L Watts.
Apologies: Dr P J Mason (UK Met Office), Dr W Maton-Howarth (R&D Directorate, DoH).

1 Report of Fifth Meeting FAST 02/01

1.1 The report of the fifth meeting held on 2 August 2001 was **APPROVED**.

2 Matters Arising

2.1 Matters Arising from fourth meeting

5.3 Seasonal Forecasting - Links through the NCAS Advisory Group, which includes Tim Palmer (ECMWF), BJH also working with ECMWF and Hadley Centre. The potential of a one-day seminar for users was discussed. An annual meeting, including users, on a topic of novelty would be valuable (DFT). The NERC-led Research Funders Forum would have NCAS representation. It was noted that Government departments need much information, particularly because of changes, and might need three meetings: Government, industry, and scientists. The importance of NCAS/Department bilaterals was emphasised.

5.4 Access to Earth Simulator opened up. Prof Sumi proposed joint project, DG and Julia Slingo to visit Japan in September. Aim to port HADCM3 with high-resolution ocean and, when stable, HADGEM. NERC and DEFRA (in principle) will be providing support jointly. British Embassy in Japan is facilitating.

5.5 GECC considering national bid for supercomputing. No decision on DEFRA SR 2002 bid for extreme weather with enhanced computing (would enhance Hadley Centre capability by £3m, equivalent to a doubling of computing capability).

6.4 FAST Chair to write to Prof Lawton re cross-RC initiatives. **Action Complete**

2.2 Matters arising from fifth meeting

4.3 AJT to consider how FAST c/should interact with NCAS – dealt with later.

7.1 Mapping Departmental Objectives to NERC's AS Portfolio (*Matrix*). Although FAST needs have a live, accurate, up-to-date information source on what its partners are doing, it was decided that the matrix was not the right mechanism. It was agreed that FAST will gather published information, plans, etc, (eg Science and Innovation Strategies) and draw these together on a single website. Information will be refined through bi-laterals.

ACTION: All to provide appropriate information and/or locations, Science and Innovation Strategies will be particularly useful

3 Terms of Reference and Membership FAST 02/02

Suggestions for new members:

Office of the Deputy Prime Minister (ODPM) - David Fisk is Chief Scientific Adviser.

ACTION: AJT to write to David Fisk for a nomination

Met Office - new Chief Scientist (Dr John Mitchell).

EPSRC – Hugh Pilcher-Clayton (High-end computing). **ACTION: NRC to invite**

Devolved Administrations, eg SEPA,

ACTION: DW to circulate his note of the meeting

4 Summary of NERC Initiatives and Changes FAST 02/03

4.1 The NCAS Advisory Group has some members in common with FAST.

4.2 The new **NERC Strategy, *Science for a Sustainable Future 2002-2007***, was discussed and attention was drawn to NERC's wish to encourage and grow three priority areas over the next five years: *Earth's Life-support Systems; Climate Change; Sustainable Economies*. AJT, with Prof Duncan Wingham, will be giving a presentation to the Science and Innovation Strategy Board (SISB) on Climate Change in May 2003. Although the Strategy was considered to have many

good aspects, it was noted that international programmes, and linkages with programmes of Government Departments could have been given higher profiles. There seemed to be a tendency to move towards the user interface and more applied research. The need to maintain basic research and observations was stressed. The international importance of the ozone-sonde measurements at Lerwick, which are no longer funded, was pointed out.

- 4.3 NCAS - Discussion covered the brochure, the three science foci, (High Impact Weather; Climate Processes: Atmospheric Composition), Distributed Institute for Atmospheric Composition (DIAC) and observation facilities. NERC's current financial position was discussed.
- 4.4 Atmospheric Chemistry Studies in the Oceanic Environment (ACSOE) - Report was welcomed but needed policy makers' summary. It was recommended that in future more effort should be made to communicate with busy officials and a summary for Policy Makers should be included.
ACTION: ACSOE Final report to be sent to all members. Done
- 4.5 An annual NERC-wide "Results Day" and a user review of the usefulness of programmes were suggested.
- 4.6 Quantifying the Earth System (QUEST) - Included in SR 2002, a Working Group has been established (AJT is a member), a Town meeting is planned (13 December 2002). It was thought more focus would be required because funds are likely to be insufficient to achieve everything. The question of whether the programme should concentrate so much on carbon was raised. As models become more complex so the evaluation of their performance and improving them become more difficult processes. It was recommended that the stakeholders represented on FAST should be more influential in developing the programme, and that NERC should actively seek views from Government Departments.
- 4.7 Surface Ocean Lower Atmosphere Study (SOLAS) - the UK component of the international SOLAS programme. An Outline bid will be submitted to SISB in February 2003. The full range of physics, chemistry and biology of the ocean/atmosphere should be included. Peter Taylor should be involved. Need to engage whole of Met Office.
- 4.8 Forecasting Risk from Extreme Events (FREE) - predicting the forcing of flooding with a larger lead-time, and with an Earth system science emphasis. It should lead to increased understanding of how climate change can influence the extent and frequency of flooding events. In due course, the Foresight programme, being led by Prof D King, should provide an important steer for FREE (additional OST contact: Claire Craig). It was agreed that it is important for NERC's contribution to complement what is being done elsewhere (eg EPSRC Consortium).

5 Summary of Departmental Initiatives and Changes

Verbal updates by stakeholder Departments

DTI: Science and innovation is one of three top objectives for DTI. Links with OST are being strengthened through discussions with John Taylor. Looking for better evidence-based policy. There is a need to understand better the necessity to adapt to climate change, not just mitigation. Recognise the need to deal with extreme events that have nothing to do with carbon in the atmosphere. Need to ensure UK business captures the challenges and find a better way of looking for future implications. It was recognised that NERC and Hadley Centre tend to concentrate on natural and anthropogenic climate change, respectively but not exclusively. It was observed that leakage of hydrogen from fuel cells could become a problem. AK expressed a willingness to stimulate dialogue with the Energy side of DTI (eg wind).

ACTION: NERC to contact AK to initiate

DfT: See *Investing in the Future*, Chapter 7. Implementation is progressing slowly. No Chief Scientific Adviser as yet in DfT, or a decision to have one. David Fisk has that role in Office of Deputy Prime Minister (ODPM) but has few resources. In six months the policies of the two departments will be more clearly defined. Science assessments are likely (ie what do we know and what should we know?).

GERCA: jointly supported Royal Society/NERC workshop to reflect on the possible next chemical hazard surprises (cf ozone hole) will be held on 5/6 February 2003.

UKCIP: has asked each Department to review where climate change has an impact on their activities. Report expected by September/October, ministers report in early 2003.

Met Office: the programme is essentially unchanged; new Chief Scientist (John Mitchell) should be in place by end of the year. The new building is progressing. The Hadley Centre will be last to move in October/November 2003.

DEFRA: Aiming to build up the way it funds research in a more open way, eg via horizon scanning. Have to produce a Science and Innovation Strategy early in 2003. The new Chief Scientist is Howard Dalton, chairs GECC. The legacy of Foot and Mouth has affected budgets this year. At the time of the meeting, the SR 2002 outcome was not resolved. A substantial number of NERC scientists are involved in measurement/detection projects, eg sampling the emission of methane from closed mines (use of methane could gain "credits"). Discussions covered: emissions in developing countries; industrial sequestration of carbon dioxide, oceans or other reservoirs (oil fields); ozone as a global pollutant; and the lack of agreement on what the level should be for stabilising greenhouse gases. An Energy White Paper is due by end of 2002. It was noted that NERC is active in trying to predict atmospheric composition. There are many opportunities for NERC.

MoD (PMS): Continuing funding pressures, any cuts are likely to affect PMS equally. Hadley Centre would not be immune. MoD is providing £14m for METOP, polar orbiting satellite, in 2003. The Science and Technology Review recognises that MoD has insufficient funds to support programmes alone: PMS is declining (?). Although Qinetiq has the bulk of funds in the Corporate Research Environment, civil organisations (ie non-Qinetiq) can now bid. Environmental impacts under investigation (eg whales beached after ears damaged by submarine sonar), may inherit some research from civil area, and a paper is in preparation to describe work that can be done. The report on Sustaining Scientific Excellence at the Met Office following relocation is to be released soon (unclassified version), say end of August. It will/may be necessary to restore networks damaged by relocation.

EA: It is changing and needs to be seen to be more efficient and a champion of the environment. In atmospheric science regulation relates to releases/emissions. Two areas in the vision statement: reducing emissions, eg from landfill sites, and ammonia from chicken farms is a potential issue; and implementation of various directives on industrial sources. A draft Air Quality Research in the Agency - Current and Future Needs, had been produced. New staff: Head of Environment Policy, Peter Madden; Head of Environmental Science Prof Michael Depledge.

ACTION: BF to distribute AQ Review to members. Done. All to comment

6 Review of Links between NCAS and Stakeholders

- 6.1 A series of bilaterals will be held. The first with DEFRA had already taken place. Note: NERC has set up an internal project team to facilitate the establishment of Stakeholder Groups within its remit. FAST should be integrated with this activity.

7 Framework VI and European Research area

- 7.1 FP VI projects may be too large (at £20m) for universities to coordinate and it was suggested that NERC might take on the role. Is NERC/OST considering such a role? AJT felt under pressure to take on a coordination role.

ACTION required

Post-meeting Note: NCAS Town meeting arranged for 10 January 2003

- 7.2 Some feeling that focus is on climate change and it is difficult for air pollution researchers to become engaged. Particles are an issue locally, regionally and globally. Those studying local and regional issues have a problem with FP6.

ACTION: BF to supply contact name for the Agency on Framework 6 matters

Lisa Osborn lisa.osborn@environment-agency.gov.uk

8 Date of Next Meeting

8.1 August 2003

9 Any Other Business

None. Meeting closed at 1300 hrs.

4. Knowledge transfer and user uptake of services/facilities

Knowledge transfer of NCAS research outcomes is carried out predominantly via research papers published in the open literature and the full list of these publications is provided under ToR No. 4. Also NCAS works very closely with the Met Office in many areas of research and this transfers knowledge to one of the many users of NCAS knowledge to ultimately improve operational services provided by the Met Office for its customers. In addition NCAS provides a wide range of services and facilities for use by the academic community. It also contributes extensively to research training by supporting research studentships. Here we provide only some examples of knowledge transfer and user uptake of services/facilities; these have been described in more detail in the Annexes to ToR No. 4.

As of June 2004 BADC has over 5000 registered users of whom nearly 3000 have registered for access to restricted datasets. Of those, about half are NERC funded and so half are non-NERC supported. Nearly 1600 BADC users are not from UK institutions. Most users are from university and government laboratories (81% of the total). Also about 60% of the registered users are not atmospheric scientists. The BADC users downloaded 13 TB of data in 10 million files over this period. These user statistics demonstrate that BADC contributes significantly to knowledge transfer from NERC to the wider science and technology community both in the UK and internationally.

The Atmospheric Chemistry Modelling Support Unit provide a wide range of services to a wide user base; ranging from research scientists both here and abroad to school children seeking advice on scientific issues. In this section we briefly detail the facilities and services used and the knowledge and skill transfer between ACMSU funded staff and other scientists.

Modelling facilities and support

At the forefront of the services we provide is access to state-of-the-art scientific research models and software developed and maintained by ACMSU. Access may involve providing the software or model to UK or international scientists, or providing support services by provision of model output and collaborating with scientists for comparison with data products.

In collaboration with the UK Met Office and the University of Leeds, ACMSU staff are developing the UKCA Community Climate Model. This will become one of the leading models for coupled climate-chemistry-aerosol research.

ACMSU have also been actively developing and enhancing the p-TOMCAT offline tropospheric chemical transport model. A new version of this community model was released earlier this year. The model has been used to provide global chemical fields to scientists at Leicester to compare with MIPAS and MOPPITT satellite data. Model output along flight track data from campaigns has been provided by a web interface hosted by the ACMSU and continues to be provided to UK scientists, most recently at the University of Lancaster.

p-TOMCAT has also been used extensively in support of field campaigns for flight planning purposes. In the past model fields were supplied in near-real time for the NAMBLEX and ENVISAT aircraft campaigns. Forecast and near-real time results from ECMWF analyses are being provided for the ITOP project, a joint UK/USA campaign taking place in July 2004.

Scientific software

ACMSU staff also developed the ASAD chemical modelling software, which has been provided to the community for many years. The ASAD code is a core component of both the p-TOMCAT and UKCA models and is used for both tropospheric and stratospheric chemistry. It has been very successful in leading to a knowledge transfer and forming collaborations with other UK and international scientists. The ASAD code has been used in models developed by other groups in countries such as Germany, USA, Japan (Earth Simulator project), New Zealand, Spain and Brazil.

Other examples of knowledge transfer

ACMSU staff are also involved in the IUPAC kinetic database project in collaboration with Dr. Tony Cox of the Centre for Atmospheric Science, University of Cambridge. Easy access to current gas and heterogeneous kinetic data is a crucial element to chemistry/climate modelling and the online IUPAC database is an important component in the services offered to the chemistry/climate community. This activity is soon to be extended as ACMSU staff are involved in the EU ACCENT program (WP5) to develop a web portal providing access to all available kinetic and related databases.

Finally, in collaboration with the other staff at Cambridge, ACMSU staff developed and maintain the 'Ozone Hole Tour'; a website aimed at explaining the science behind the ozone hole in simple scientific terms. This website attracts a high number of visitors, has won numerous Internet awards and the 'Ask-A-Scientist' page on the website is very popular with many school children or University undergraduates who making use of the service to ask questions (often to help with school essays!). Images from the website have been used in numerous magazines and books.

In the area of atmospheric composition two web-based services are widely accessed: the IUPAC database of photochemical and kinetic data for atmospheric chemistry at the University of Cambridge and the master chemical mechanism (MCM) at the University of Leeds.

There are significant links fostered by CGAM with UNESCO via the International Centre for Theoretical Physics at Trieste in training and capacity building for developing countries concerning climate modelling.

The UK Treasury Invest to Save Budget 52 project aims to improve the operational pollution dispersion model of the UK Met Office (NAME). Air quality forecasting relies upon semi-empirical parameterisations within numerical models for the description of turbulent dispersion. There is scope to improve air quality forecasting through improved information about turbulence measured in the urban atmosphere. From the field campaign undertaken in July 2003 a comprehensive data set has been obtained from the UFAM dual Doppler lidar measurements. This data set will enable comparisons of lidar measured atmospheric flow data and turbulence parameters to be made with the output from the NAME and the UK Met Office Unified Model. This data set and the research undertaken within the project will be of benefit to the UK Met Office leading to improved air quality forecasts, and for researchers involved in air quality and pollution dispersion.

UWERN has developed and validated a new numerical model, 3dVOM, designed for gravity wave forecasting. The model is based on the linearised Boussinesq equations with simple first order turbulence closure. The linearised model is now available as a UWERN facility and has been adopted by the Met Office for operational gravity wave and rotor streaming forecasting at several airports including in the Falklands. Within the UWERN urban meteorology theme a model of fluxes from streets has been combined with a model for radiative heat transfer in an urban street, to formulate a model for the thermodynamic interaction of the urban streets with the boundary layer. The Met Office has implemented this model of urban areas into their operational weather forecasting model.

CGAM staff were involved on so-called “tiger teams” at the Met Office’s Hadley Centre to use their specialised knowledge to help address problems emerging in the new dynamics global atmospheric model that will form the basis of the new climate model, HadGEM.

5. NCAS Science Communications

NCAS employs a full-time Science Communications Manager, Dr Louisa Watts. Science Communications includes both internal communications across the distributed network that comprises NCAS and also external communications.

Internal Communications:

- Websites for each centre and facility, linked from the central NCAS site <http://ncas.nerc.ac.uk>
- NERC-Atmos email distribution. This list is used by the NERC Swindon Office atmospheric science team and by NCAS to publicise funding opportunities, vacancies and all other relevant information. Only the NERC atmospheric science team and NCAS director can post to this list, hence the volume of mail is kept as low as possible to maximise the communications impact of such emails. A message archive is kept up-to-date on the NCAS website at <http://www.ncas.ac.uk/pipermail/nerc-atmos/>. Over 400 UK atmospheric scientists subscribe to the NERC-Atmos email distribution.
- Access Grid is used particularly by the NCAS Management Group and is available at the following NCAS locations: Reading, RAL, Leeds, Manchester and Cambridge.
- Technical publications. There are many of these and they include, for example, regular UGAMP and UWERN newsletters; e.g. <http://www.acmsu.nerc.ac.uk/newsletter.html> for the 2004 UGAMP newsletter.
- Conferences and workshops organised by and for NCAS scientists.

External Communications:

- Websites, linked from <http://ncas.nerc.ac.uk>. Note that the NCAS central website visit statistics for June 2004, shown below, indicate an average of 113 visits per day. The individual centres and facilities have websites, which have links from the central site. These will be visited directly as well and those visits are not included in these statistics.
- The Communications page of the NCAS website, <http://ncas.nerc.ac.uk/communications/>, contains links to all the activities under this heading. These are:
 - Communications with the public
 - Publications
 - NCAS Affiliated Institutions
 - Forum for Atmospheric Science and Technology
 - NCAS Advisory Group
 - Atmospheric Sciences Listserver
 - Meetings and events
- Media releases are listed at: http://ncas.nerc.ac.uk/communications/media_coverage.asp
- Brochures are described at: <http://ncas.nerc.ac.uk/publications/> and these include “The Future of our Atmosphere” published in 2002 and “Climate in a Changing World” published in 2004.

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Earth Simulator delights scientists

By Alex Kirby
BBC News Online environment correspondent

A new era in the accuracy of climate prediction has come closer with the presentation of the first results from the largest supercomputer in the world.

The Earth Simulator, housed in Japan, has produced what scientists are calling "very exciting" information.

It is being presented at a three-day climate workshop in Cambridge, UK.

The computer's results hold out the prospect of better predictions of the likelihood of increasing hurricanes, prolonged heavy rain, and heatwaves.

The Earth Simulator, which began work in March 2002, is the world's biggest and fastest supercomputer, and has the job of solving some of the thorniest problems facing the Earth in the decades ahead.

It is ten times more powerful than anything available at the moment to scientists in the UK. The simulator consists of 640 nodes (the equivalent of individual computers) linked together by 83,000 high-speed cables: the building which houses it has a floor space the size of four tennis courts.

New levels of accuracy

One of the organisations behind the Cambridge workshop is the UK's National Institute for Environmental eScience (NIEES), hosted by the university's Centre for Mathematical Sciences.

The other is the Natural Environment Research Council's Centres for Atmospheric Science (NCAS).

Professor Julia Slingo, director of the NCAS Centre for Global Atmospheric Modelling, said: "These results are very exciting."

SEE ALSO:
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US pollution may damage UK health

Polluted air from America could be damaging the health of people in Britain, experts fear.

Airborne chemicals from 8,000km away are being dumped in the UK and western Europe and may be to blame for a rise in lung disease, say UK scientists.

Dr Alastair Lewis, from York University and the Intercontinental Transport of Ozone and Precursors programme, is running a series of tests.

His team will track and sample the air stream across the Atlantic.

About 50 scientists from seven UK universities are to join hundreds of other researchers in the Azores in the middle of the Atlantic Ocean.

Toxic fumes

They will look at how a cocktail of chemicals, emitted from vehicle exhausts and power stations in the US, react together in the air on their way to Europe.

SEE ALSO:
Poor air harms lungs of unborn 23 Jun 04 | Health
New device for asthma sufferers 21 Mar 04 | Health
Heatwaves can make trees pollute 10 May 04 | Science/Nature

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Cut kids' TV 'to protect health'
NHS dental care reform plans due
Stringent hygiene 'cuts out MRSA'

Figure: Web-pages referring to NCAS activities on the BBC Website – Science/Nature section

- Educational material/information packs. An example is the Earth System Modelling information pack which can be found at: <http://ncas.nerc.ac.uk/meetings/past/japan/ESM%20Press%20Pack.pdf>
- Involvement with climateprediction.net as a project in public involvement in science – see <http://climateprediction.net> for details.
- Articles and interviews in the media – such as on the BBC programmes and website:
 - “NCAS Scientists hitting the headlines” at http://ncas.nerc.ac.uk/news/stories/hitting_the_headlines.asp
 - “Gone with the wind” at http://ncas.nerc.ac.uk/communications/media_coverage_gone_with_wind.asp

NCAS central website visits during June 2004 averaging at 113 per day.

**NERC Centres for
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The NERC Centres for Atmospheric Science comprises:

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UFAM: *Universities' Facility for Atmospheric Measurement*

UWERN: *Universities' Weather Research Network*

**ToR No. 7 – Management of NCAS budgets and
infrastructure**

ToR No. 7 – Management of NCAS budgets and infrastructure

1. Summary

In this section the following NCAS activities are discussed: the management of NCAS budgets; measures of the value-for-money of NCAS research; financial summary for NCAS including the pre-2002 allocation, the outcome of the NCAS I proposal, the Council decision on UFAM and the Earth Simulator project in 2003 and the NCAS synchronisation in 2003; staff and student numbers.

The NCAS budget is managed financially at NERC Swindon Office by the Head of Atmospheric Science (Dr Andrew Kaye). The Director of NCAS decides upon the allocation of funding and then NERC Swindon Office awards contracts to the relevant universities. These contracts are styled "NCAS Leeds, NCAS Reading etc" and comprise a financial annex and a technical annex outlining the research or services to be provided. The exception is the contract for BADC, which is managed within the Service Level Agreement that NERC has with the CCLRC. Further details of the methodologies used in issuing contracts etc see ToR No. 2.

The allocation of resources to NCAS over this period has been as follows.

- Existing atmospheric science programmes already had an allocation of funding that was awarded prior to the creation of NCAS and this is described in Table 1 below.
- Following the successful proposal made to NERC in November 2001, an award to NCAS was made by NERC for NCAS I funds to run from 1 April 2002 to 31 March 2006 (see Table 2 below).
- In addition NERC Council awarded NCAS additional funding for the support of specialised instruments within UFAM and to support the UK-Japan project using the Earth Simulator in 2003 (see Table 3 below).
- A request was made to NERC to synchronize NCAS programmes to a common end date on 31 March 2006 and this was agreed in 2003 with funding awarded described in Table 4 below.
- Finally in 2004 a proposal was made by NCAS to the NERC Capital Equipment Round and this led to an award (see Table 5 below).

The sum total of these five awards for NCAS is shown in Table 6 below. This shows that NCAS has an average total budget each year of around £5.4M, with a final year (2005/06) budget of £6.2M.

Note that in addition a substantial amount of external funding is won by NCAS from other sources and this adds a further average annual funding input of about £3.2M, i.e., an additional 59% of the NCAS "core" budget (but with a higher percentage, nearer to 116%, as a proportion of the research-dominated component of the NCAS budget that contributes to these figures from ACMSU, CGAM, DIAC and UWERN) – see discussion of this in ToR No. 9.

Also NCAS manages for NERC a High Performance Computing (HPC) atmospheric science consortium to utilise national supercomputing facilities. The components of this consortium arise from research funded in the following ways: NCAS directly funded, NCAS Affiliated centres, NCAS co-funding from NERC directed programmes, NCAS co-funding from NERC grants and NCAS co-funding from other sources. The NCAS HPC consortium also uses central software, support and training. The costs for this supercomputing, which is essential in delivering the NCAS research programme, are provided from a budget line held in NERC Services and Facilities, i.e., outside of NCAS. The costs of the NCAS HPC Consortium over the last four years have been: 2001 - £1.08M, 2002 - £0.80M, 2003 - £1.11M, 2004 (projected) - £1.13M. The relative constancy of these costs reflects the fact that the increase in the amount of computing being done (as scientific aspirations grow) of about 20% per annum is largely offset by the decrease in unit HPC costs of about 3% per annum and the improvement in computing performance of models by about 13% per annum.

NERC introduced in 2003 a new funding framework containing ten categories. Here we give an indication of the proportion of NCAS funding that is devoted to each of the ten categories.

- Category 1: *Strategic Data and Knowledge* ~ 12% (mostly BADC)**
- Category 2: *Shared Services and Facilities* ~ 25% (all contribute, especially UFAM and FAAM)**
- Category 3: *Research Centre Capability* ~ 10%**
- Category 4: *Training* ~ 3% (CGAM, DIAC and UWERN)**
- Category 5: *Research* ~ 45% (mostly ACMSU, CGAM, DIAC and UWERN)**
- Category 6: *Knowledge Transfer* ~ 4% (all contribute)**
- Category 7: *Infrastructure* ~ 0%**
- Category 8: *Specialist major infrastructure* ~ 0%**
- Category 9: *Major Capital Projects* ~ 0%**
- Category 10: *Science and Society* ~ 1%**

Note that here we have placed NCAS directors/heads, senior scientists and associated administration costs into category 3 and all other research staff into category 5. It is as yet unclear whether this division is appropriate as the precise definition of each category of the Funding Framework is still subject to revision.

Allocation of these resources within NCAS is carried out by the NCAS Management Group, with final decisions being taken by the Director of NCAS. The Director of NCAS delegates responsibility for the budget lines for each of the centres/facilities to their respective Directors and Heads. The majority of the funding for each centre/facility/programme was awarded for the 4-year period to 31 March 2006. In addition the Director of NCAS retains a "small initiatives" and a "partnership agreements" budget line to allow flexibility to respond to developments that require small funding to be allocated. For example in small initiatives we have awarded NCAS research studentships and bursaries for attendance at the Royal Meteorological Society biennial conference 2003. In the partnership agreements we have two (knowledge transfer) projects with the Met Office on mesoscale data assimilation at Reading and a new aerosol module for the climate model at Leeds.

Estimation of value for money is a complicated issue for an organisation that has a variety of outputs including basic research and services. As regards publications we can compare the number of publications with the funding allocated – see Table 7. Note that we show the research-dominated centres separately from the facilities as the latter clearly have less focus on direct publications as outputs. For the three complete years (for publications) 2001, 2002 and 2003, **the cost per publication for the three research-dominated centres included in this analysis, is an average of £22K per paper** (although it should be noted that even these centres have a significant component devoted to services to the community, particularly in the form of modelling support). The figure for NCAS for these three years, including the centres and facilities that contributed to the statistics in Table 7, is £30K per paper. (If we also include the costs of DIAC and FAAM, which have yet to produce papers because they have only just been established, then we arrive at the somewhat unrepresentative figure of £63K per paper.) The facilities, such as BADC, which are service-dominated, also quantify their service provision and these figures are summarised in ToR No. 4 within the BADC report of activities. It should be noted that all NCAS centres also have a service component in supporting their part of the atmospheric science community. Again this is described in ToR No. 4 under each report of activities.

All staff management for NCAS funded staff is the responsibility of the host university and the local principal investigator with overall scrutiny by the Director/Head of each centre/facility. This includes staff development reviews, health and safety arrangements etc. Similarly for research students funded by NCAS the host institution provides their normal processes of evaluation and scrutiny. Communication within NCAS is via the website(s), the atmospheric science email distribution on NERC-Atmos, personal email and directly by directors and heads (see further details concerning

NCAS science communications in ToR No. 6). The total number of staff and students employed with NCAS funding in 2004 is shown in Table 8 below.

The ethos of the way NCAS is structured is that it attempts to include, in a variety of ways, as many of the academic atmospheric science community as possible. Fourteen university groups (and some additional ones in UGAMP) receive direct NCAS funding and others receive NCAS research studentships. The NCAS Affiliated Institutions comprise 26 universities and 10 NERC research and collaborative centres. This inclusivity means that there is no other UK provider of the service apparent at present. Competition occurs as universities and PIs bid for funding as and when it becomes available (e.g., for the initial DIAC contracts). There is also full and open competition for staff posts and studentships as and when they become available within centres and facilities. This competition includes those for the Director and Head positions.

Financial Summary for NCAS

Table 1: Funding allocated to atmospheric science programmes prior to creation of NCAS (in £M)

Pre-2002 Allocated Funding (£M)	2001/02	2002/03	2003/04	2004/05	2005/06	Total 2002/2006
NCAS Directorate	0.10	0.17	0.18	0.08		0.43
CGAM	1.00	0.49				0.49
ACMSU	0.23	0.11				0.11
UWERN	0.50	0.45	0.45	0.45		1.35
UFAM (Post-JIF)			0.40	0.60		1.00
Chilbolton Radar		0.05	0.05	0.05		0.15
COSMAS	1.03	1.00	1.00			2.00
FAAM (BAE 146)	0.10	0.10	0.50	0.50	0.50	1.60
BADC – core	0.46					0.00
BADC - agreed metadata additions from NERC	0.12	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.35
Aberystwyth Monitoring	0.04					0.00
Chemistry Readership, Cambridge	0.05	0.03	0.04			0.08
Pre-2002 Allocation Total	3.63	2.49	2.71	1.77	0.59	7.56

Table 2: Allocation of funding for NCAS I (in £M)

Outcome of NCAS I Proposal (submitted in 2001)	2001/02	2002/03	2003/04	2004/05	2005/06	Total 2002/2006
CGAM		0.25	1.14	1.41	1.43	4.23
ACMSU		0.13	0.26	0.28	0.30	0.97
BADC (Core)		0.50	0.54	0.58		1.62
DIAC - total budget allocated		0.40	0.55	0.60	0.65	2.20
Aberystwyth Monitoring		0.04				0.04
Partnership Agreements (e.g. Met Office)		0.10	0.10	0.10	0.07	0.37
Chilbolton Radar Consortium		0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.24
Small Initiatives		0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.20
UWERN Director		0.00	0.05	0.05	0.03	0.13
Total Outcome of NCAS I Proposal 2001		1.56	2.76	3.48	2.56	10.00

Table 3: Additional allocation of funding to UFAM and to CGAM in 2003 (in £M)

COUNCIL/SISB decisions 2003	2001/02	2002/03	2003/04	2004/05	2005/06	Total 2002/2006
UFAM (aircraft instruments post JIF)			0.20	0.30	0.35	0.85
CGAM (Earth Simulator project)		0.03	0.03	0.20	0.42	0.68
Total Outcome Council/SISB 2003		0.03	0.23	0.50	0.77	1.53

Table 4: Allocation of funding to synchronise NCAS programmes to a single end-date (in £M)

NCAS Synchronisation funds awarded in 2003	2001/02	2002/03	2003/04	2004/05	2005/06	Total 2002/2006
UWERN incl. Director					0.72	0.72
BADC Core					0.65	0.65
Partnership Agreements (e.g. Met Office)					0.05	0.05
UFAM					0.60	0.60
NCAS Directorate				0.12	0.23	0.35
Communications Manager			0.02	0.03	0.03	0.08
Total Outcome of Synchronisation 2003			0.02	0.15	2.28	2.45

Table 5: Capital Equipment Award 2004 (in £M)

Capital Equipment Round 2004	2001/02	2002/03	2003/04	2004/05	2005/06	Total 2002/2006
BDAN computing equipment				0.25		0.25
Total Capital equipment 2004				0.25		0.25

Table 6: Summary of total resources available to NCAS over this period (in £M)

Total NCAS funding 2002 - 2006	2001/02	2002/03	2003/04	2004/05	2005/06	Total 2002/2006
CGAM		0.77	1.17	1.61	1.85	5.40
ACMSU		0.24	0.26	0.28	0.30	1.08
UWERN (incl. Director)		0.45	0.50	0.50	0.75	2.20
DIAC (incl. Aber. monitoring)		0.44	0.55	0.60	0.65	2.24
BADC (incl. metadata)		0.59	0.63	0.67	0.74	2.62
UFAM (incl. Chilbolton)		0.11	0.71	1.01	1.01	2.84
FAAM		0.10	0.50	0.50	0.50	1.60
NCAS Directorate		0.17	0.18	0.20	0.23	0.78
Communications Manager			0.02	0.03	0.03	0.08
Small initiatives		0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.20
Partnership Agreements (e.g. Met Office)		0.10	0.10	0.10	0.13	0.43
Capital Equipment Round 2004				0.25		0.25
Cambridge Readership		0.03	0.04			0.08
COSMAS		1.00	1.00			2.00
Total = NCAS 1 + additions 2002 - 2004		4.05	5.71	5.80	6.23	21.79

Table 7: NCAS Publications and Funding (in £K); also costs (in £K) per publication are given for 2001-2003 and 2001-2004.

Note that: DIAC and FAAM are not included as they have only recently been established; publication figures for 2004 includes information up to July 2004 whereas funding is for the whole year.

NCAS Publications and Funding												
	2001		2002		2003		2004		Total		Fund/pubs	Fund/pubs
	Funding	Pubs	Funding	Pubs	Funding	Pubs	Funding	Pubs	Funding	Pubs	2001-2004	2001-2003
Centres												
ACMSU	230	18	240	12	260	18	280	10	1010	58	17	15
CGAM	1000	50	770	39	1170	41	1610	29	4550	159	29	23
UWERN	500	17	450	17	500	22	500	32	1950	88	22	26
Total Centres	1730	85	1460	68	1930	81	2390	71	7510	305	25	22
Facilities												
BADC	580	4	590	2	630	6	670	3	2470	16	165	150
UFAM	0	3	110	0	710	8	1010	11	1830	22	83	75
Total Facilities	580	7	700	2	1340	14	1680	14	4300	37	116	114
TOTAL NCAS	2310	92	2160	70	3270	95	4070	85	11810	342	35	30

Table 8: Staff and students funded by NCAS in 2004

Note that: research students included are only those directly funded by NCAS and does not include standard NERC quota awards; staff numbers include only those directly funded by NCAS; staff in FAAM are currently being recruited.

NCAS Staff and students 2004

	Directors/Heads	Staff	Research students
Centres			
ACMSU	1	5	
CGAM	1	21	5
DIAC	1	8	4
UWERN	1	14	3
Total Centres	4	48	12
Facilities			
BADC	1	8	
FAAM	1	6	
UFAM	1	11	
Total Facilities	3	25	
Directorate NCAS	1	2	
TOTAL NCAS	8	75	12

2. Response from Director to Staff Survey

**NERC Centres for
Atmospheric Science**
NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

NCAS Science Management Audit

September 2004

The NERC Centres for Atmospheric Science comprises:

ACMSU: *Atmospheric Chemistry Modelling Support Unit*

BADC: *British Atmospheric Data Centre*

CGAM: *Centre for Global Atmospheric Modelling*

DIAC: *Distributed Institute for Atmospheric Composition*

FAAM: *Facility for Airborne Atmospheric Measurements*

UFAM: *Universities' Facility for Atmospheric Measurement*

UWERN: *Universities' Weather Research Network*

**ToR No. 8 – Investment in Capital equipment, facilities,
services and support**

ToR No. 8 – Investment in Capital equipment, facilities, services and support

1. Summary

In this section the following NCAS activities will be described: capital equipment investments, usage of services and facilities.

NCAS has benefited from previous successes of the UK atmospheric science community in acquiring major pieces of capital equipment prior to the establishment of NCAS. These successes have occurred as a result of equipment purchased and/or developed using funding from previous atmospheric science thematic programmes such as ACSOE, IFMA and COSMAS. In addition two major awards were made to this community as part of the Joint Infrastructure Fund, JIF, established by the UK Government to modernise the equipment available to the UK science base. NERC, via NCAS, agreed that for these two JIF awards it would underwrite the future use and development of the equipment. The first of the two awards was to establish a set of ground-based instruments to measure the physical and dynamical properties of the atmosphere and this formed the core of UFAM. The second of the JIF awards was to provide a joint Met Office-NERC research aircraft, including a set of specialised airborne instruments for measurement of atmospheric composition. The aircraft is now operated by FAAM and the specialised instruments are incorporated within UFAM.

NCAS is in the process of fully establishing UFAM and FAAM. In the case of UFAM it has been decided to create a set of instrument scientists' posts to support the use and development of the measurement instrumentation by the community (see ToR no. 4). The support given by NCAS, and NERC more widely, to UFAM and FAAM demonstrates the commitment to supporting and developing major capital equipment acquisitions for the benefit of the community.

As well as this instrumentation for measuring the atmosphere NCAS operates a data centre, BADC, and also various services to the community in modelling and other supporting technologies and techniques. These have been described in some detail in ToR No. 4 and are not repeated here. Approximately 50% of the funding provided by NCAS is in the area of services and facilities for NCAS and the wider community to use in its research.

2. Capital Investments Made

NCAS has made relatively modest capital equipment investments thus far. As explained previously, this is because much of the atmospheric measurement instrumentation now within NCAS was purchased separately under the Joint Infrastructure Fund. Computing investments have been made particularly by CGAM and BADC but these have been individually for relatively small items thus far. Two significant capital investments are about to be made and these highlighted here for completeness.

A sensitive instrument for the measurement of NO_{xy} is currently out to tender by DIAC. The specification is ~ 2ppt for NO. The instrument will be used initially on the ground, but the tender includes an aircraft requirement. The anticipated cost is around £0.22m.

Very recently NCAS has been successful in being awarded a capital equipment grant (£0.25m) by NERC to develop a "Big Data Analysis Network, BDAN". The analysis and interpretation of data is at the heart of atmospheric science. BDAN will provide the computing infrastructure, consistent with eScience/Grid developments, necessary for community analysis of the very large observational and simulation datasets that are, and will be, held at the NCAS/British Atmospheric Data Centre (BADC). The main requirement is to deploy a large data analysis system (i.e. computer hardware) which will fulfil two functions: providing a system upon which users will be able to compare and contrast TB-scale datasets, and provide a system which will be able to process web-based requests for data analysis. This system will differ from other available systems in that it will be optimised for handling very large datasets (so it will be configured with available disk and input/output subsystem performance as priorities). Such a system is necessary for two reasons: observational datasets (including ERA40) are

now TB-scale: the analysis of non-linearity in the climate system needs fine temporal and spatial resolution in the analysis of output (not only during the calculations). As analysis often consists of comparing the data produced on a number of systems, data movement is inevitable. Given that many datasets are held at the BADC and that they are subject to NERC data policies, putting the analysis system under the control of BADC is optimal – this also allows BADC to deploy web-service based analysis tools so that a larger community can utilise these large datasets.

BDAN will support BADC managed storage at the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL, in the BADC machine room), at Daresbury Laboratory (with HPCx), at Manchester (preferably with CSAR, specific negotiations are ongoing), and at Reading University (the NCAS Centre for Global Atmospheric Modelling). Various manufacturers have been approached and possible hardware elements to deliver the system are: an IBM eServer BladeCentre and a Raidtec SNAZ EO NAS 4TB Subsystem (including fileserver, ethernet connections, optical fibre SAN interface, fibre array elite, E3002 JBOD system). The data storage will be federated so that users will be able to easily manage data held at any of the locations, and so that replica copies can be used to provide both backup and higher IO bandwidth. As a result users will be able to transparently store data at any location without knowing of the details of data transfer, and multiple copies of key datasets will be available locally in key locations.

Key characteristics of the system to be installed will be the ability to compare and contrast 2 TB of data within four hours, to move 1 TB of data between sites in 4 hours, to support at least 30 TB of distributed storage, and to provide up to 32 analysis processors. Some existing web based tasks that now take an hour to complete will be performed within a minute, leading to a significant increase in exploitation of large datasets. The net effect of the system will be that “power” users will be able to fully exploit the non-linearity of high-resolution simulations of the atmosphere (such as those produced by the Earth Simulator and the new UK-HiGEM project), and that many other users will be able to carry out web-based data analysis tasks that hitherto would have not been possible centrally because of lack of compute resources in the BADC servers and may have been impossible for them locally too (because of the large disk requirements). It is expected that hundreds of users nationally will benefit from this facility.

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ToR No. 9 – External Funding

ToR No. 9 – External Funding

1. Summary of External Funding

In this section a summary is provided of the external funding awarded to NCAS.

Over the period 2001 to 2008 the total external funding awarded to NCAS centres/facilities, as a result of proposals submitted by NCAS scientists to a variety of funding agencies, is about £16.5M, or about £2.07M per annum over that 8 year period – see Table 1 and the database on the following website for further details:

http://www.cgam.nerc.ac.uk/services/ncas_funding/index.php

The database is searchable and contains information as follows: value of each contract, start date, end date, title of research project and total annual value across NCAS. External contracts arise from many sources including: NERC, European Commission, industry, ESA etc.

For comparison purposes we can examine the situation over the NCAS I period of 2002, 2003, 2004 and 2005 in which the external funding amounts to £12.67M total or £3.17M per annum average. This can be compared with the NCAS core funding awarded over the same period of £21.5M total, or £5.4M per annum average. Therefore of the total NCAS funding, the external funding amounts to an additional 59%. However it is also illustrative to compare the external funding to the NCAS core funding for the four research-dominated centres (ACMSU, CGAM, DIAC and UWERN) that have contributed directly to these figures – this NCAS core funding from these four centres amounts to £10.92M total over the four years and so £2.73M per annum average. Therefore the external funding of NCAS represents an additional 116% compared to the NCAS contribution to these four research-dominated centres.

NCAS external funding										
	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	Total	Annual 2002 - 2005
TOTAL NCAS	1.61	2.97	3.83	3.24	2.63	1.53	0.69	0.04	16.54	3.17

Table 1: NCAS external funding (in £M)

Note 1: DIAC and FAAM not included as they have only recently been established

Note 2: Each grant divided into equal annual contributions

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**ToR No. 10 – Processes of Change; flow of new ideas;
career paths**

ToR No. 10 – Processes of Change; flow of new ideas; career paths

1. Overview

In this section various ways in which new ideas lead to changes in the NCAS programme are described. Also issues relating to training of research students and career development of NCAS staff are discussed.

Organisational change

The organisation of NCAS with funding provided for four or five years at a time means that NCAS is inherently flexible capable of responding to short and medium-term changes. An advantage of this is that the so-called frictional costs of stopping activities in centres with permanent NERC staff do not apply in the same way to NCAS. Staff within NCAS have an expectation that they may be redeployed onto new activities, requiring their expertise, as priorities change. All activities and projects are term-based (e.g., the lifetime of NCAS I) and so NCAS is managed with an expertise-based approach to staff deployment and development. The ethos of NCAS is to be outward looking and to include the widest possible involvement from the UK atmospheric science community.

Financial change - redirection of resources

A prime example of NCAS acting to redirect resources followed the decision by NERC concerning the funding level for NCAS I. The proposal that was submitted was for a portfolio of science costing as requiring £21.6M over five years, additional to the previously allocated funding for pre-existing programmes now taken within NCAS. Because of financial difficulties at that time NERC were only able to award £10M to NCAS. This led to a major redirection of resources and management of the consequently much-reduced expectations of the organisation and the wider community. The Director of NCAS, in consultation with the Chief Executive of NERC, took the decision to spend the allocated resources over four years instead of the originally proposed five-year period. Also the decision was taken not to shelve the creation of a new institute for atmospheric composition (DIAC) but rather start it with a reduced portfolio but with the plan to expand it substantially within the NCAS II period. A decision was taken that research on surface fluxes of atmospheric constituents and the influence of composition on radiative transfer in the atmosphere would not receive support from NCAS I. Instead it was decided that these areas would be developed in partnership with other institutes and scientists already active in those fields with, wherever possible, funding to be obtained by external proposals made supported by NCAS. An example of this is SOLAS, which has been funded by NERC as a directed programme following a proposal made to NERC led by Mike Pilling, Director of DIAC. This major redirection of resources was painful, especially coming at the establishment phase of NCAS, but was managed effectively minimising long-term damage to the strategic development of atmospheric science in the UK.

Management change

Another example of redirection of resources and change of management (admittedly prior to the establishment of NCAS but with the same staff involved) concerned the BADC. Under previous management the data centre was felt by the community to be neither serving that community effectively nor representing value-for-money. Notably, the data centre was being driven and run by computer technologists with insufficient knowledge of users' requirements. The then Atmospheric Science and Technology Board of NERC took the decision to review the management of BADC. The review was led by Julia Slingo, now Director of CGAM, and it recommended a reduced overall budget within a new business plan with increased emphasis on the scientific user requirements and a more streamlined, pragmatic and efficient method for data delivery. As a consequence of this a new Head of BADC (Dr. Lesley Gray, now a senior scientist in CGAM) was appointed to provide more effective scientific leadership. Since that time BADC has been turned round into a nationally and

internationally recognised flagship data centre. Under the current leadership of Dr. Bryan Lawrence it has continued to flourish and is also now at the forefront of NERC's new data management developments such as the NERC DataGrid.

Scientific change of direction

The flow of new ideas from within NCAS, and within the wider atmospheric science community, was recognised by NCAS to be a critical aspect of the long-term health of the organisation and of the atmospheric science community. Consequently NCAS was established with a structure that specifically put in place processes that would ensure such ideas were an integral part of the way change was brought about by NCAS. The NCAS Affiliated Institutions (discussed in ToR No. 5) is the primary forum for the flow of new ideas from the community. In addition the Atmospheric Science Strategy (discussed in ToR no. 2) has been, and will continue to be, developed via national consultation. The NCAS II Proposal is being developed using a wide consultation process involving a wide group of scientists who are drafting components of the text. This group of scientists involves not just the established leaders and PIs but also the younger next-generation of post-docs and PIs.

Role of leadership in change

Another key aspect of the process used within NCAS for change and rejuvenation with new ideas is the role of the seven directors and heads of the centres and facilities. This group of NCAS managers are international-renowned scientific leaders in their fields (including two Fellows of the Royal Society). Their extensive activities on the international atmospheric science stage, ensures that they are exposed to the latest scientific and technical developments whenever and wherever they are occurring. The ability of NCAS to have secured the services of this group of leaders is notable and distinguishes NCAS from many other similar organisations. In addition this group are very successful and active in securing external funding by open competition and this also means that they have a very good perception of new developments in the field. These externally-funded projects take advantage of funding opportunities in the areas of atmospheric science that NCAS has prioritised as of critical current importance. The philosophy employed by the NCAS Management Group is that in the areas of research determined as being of strategic importance the, often seed-corn, funding devoted to these areas by NCAS itself, is complemented by external funding from standard, consortia and directed programme proposals made by and/or with the support of NCAS. An example is the area of precipitation and the water cycle. This is recognised by NCAS as being of strategic importance. NCAS is devoting some resource itself into the area, e.g., via the project on mesoscale data assimilation in UWERN and investigations in CGAM on the role of tropical convection in climate variability. However we have also led successfully the proposal to NERC for a new directed programme into Flood Risk from Extreme Events, FREE. In addition Alan Blyth, Head of UFAM, led a successful consortium proposal to NERC on convective storm initiation. The aim is that a critical mass of both funding and experts will thereby be brought to bear on this scientific problem. NCAS is acting as the catalyst for community-wide development of the science in that topic. There are other examples such as aerosols and high-resolution climate modelling.

2. Training – research students

NCAS centres/facilities have for some time supported research studentships in universities where an atmospheric science faculty member wishes to build up or develop a research topic related to the research programmes of the centres/facilities. For example in recent years CGAM has allocated studentships to: Bristol, Lancaster, Leeds, Oxford, Southampton, St Andrews and UEA. In 2004 we held an NCAS open competitive process for PIs to bid for new studentships and nine NCAS studentships were awarded to six universities. As shown in ToR No. 7, in 2004 we have 12 studentships allocated and this is a significant addition to the pool of atmospheric research students in the UK. For NCAS such training fulfils several functions. It enables the involvement of new Principal Investigators with NCAS research. It helps train the next generation of researchers including those that will work for NCAS. Also it often allows the involvement of NCAS research staff in the

supervision of students and so contribute to their career development. A key goal of NERC is to train the next generation of environmental scientists and NCAS contributes particularly by bringing in mathematicians, physicists and chemists into atmospheric science. NCAS is well positioned to do this as most atmospheric science research is being carried out by individuals or groups within departments aligned to the traditional disciplines of maths, physics and chemistry. This means that in principle we have a good way to encourage those students who might not previously have thought of research in atmospheric science to convert following their first degrees.

3. Career development

A major issue for NCAS is the long-term career development of NCAS staff in universities bearing in mind the short-term nature of the funding that is awarded by NERC. Whilst some thinking has been done on this there is no doubt that this remains as a major issue for NCAS for the future. Whilst NCAS promotes the concept that staff employed by NCAS are flexible and expertise-based rather than project-based, it is still difficult for university employers to translate this into providing a long-term commitment to those staff. Most NCAS staff are on fixed-term contracts (although note that all of those at BADC and some at FAAM have open-ended contracts). The changing employment framework, provided by new European legislation, is being introduced into UK universities, albeit slowly. This should mean that all staff who have worked in a university for 4 years or more be offered open-ended contracts with appropriate redundancy rights. Some universities, such as Reading, have underwritten the employment contracts of senior NCAS staff such that they have permanent contracts. This is a low risk option for such universities as such senior staff are very effective at winning research grant income in their own right and usually therefore more than pay for their position from the overheads associated with these grants. However the number of such positions in NCAS is in the minority. Other senior staff, such as Mike Pilling, Alan Thorpe and John Pyle, occupy established university positions and the funding that NCAS provides is used to compensate the university for the time spent on NCAS activities. The position of more junior staff in NCAS is less secure. Discussions are ongoing with NERC concerning NERC accepting part of the risk implied by the fixed term nature of the funding for NCAS. Currently the staff themselves bear the risk of occupying fixed term positions and the university employers accept the possibility of paying redundancy costs for certain open-ended contracts. For some senior positions the university bears some risk if positions are underwritten. NERC could contribute by possibly underwriting any redundancy costs should it prove necessary to finish particular posts. Discussions are ongoing between the Director of NCAS and the Director of People, Skills and Communication at NERC Swindon office concerning such possible arrangements.

A further issue is the relative employment conditions for various categories of staff funded by NCAS, such as research, administrative, computational scientists, data scientists and secretarial staff. Different universities currently have differing categories of staff with a variety of pay scales. This makes issues such as comparability of pay and conditions across NCAS extremely difficult to deal with. This year a national agreement has been reached that university scales will be integrated into a single unified scale. This should help to enable NCAS staff to feel they all have equal opportunities for recognition, status and promotion prospects. We look forward to using this change to enhance these issues for NCAS staff.

**NERC Centres for
Atmospheric Science**
NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

NCAS Science Management Audit

September 2004

The NERC Centres for Atmospheric Science comprises:

ACMSU: *Atmospheric Chemistry Modelling Support Unit*

BADC: *British Atmospheric Data Centre*

CGAM: *Centre for Global Atmospheric Modelling*

DIAC: *Distributed Institute for Atmospheric Composition*

FAAM: *Facility for Airborne Atmospheric Measurements*

UFAM: *Universities' Facility for Atmospheric Measurement*

UWERN: *Universities' Weather Research Network*

**ToR No. 11 – Funding Duration and Frequency of Bidding
for New Funds**

ToR No. 11 – Funding Duration and Frequency of Bidding for New Funds

1. Overview

The (short) history of how NCAS has been funded by NERC is provided and also the planning for the next phase of funding for 2006 to 2011, NCAS II, is described.

NCAS was initially funded from 1 April 2002 for a four year period, NCAS I, until 31 March 2006. (Note that some of the NCAS science programmes and centres/facilities pre-date the setting-up of NCAS. The financial implications of these existing programmes is made clear in ToR No. 7 finance spreadsheets.) The NCAS I proposal requested funding of £21.6M (over 5 years). At that time, 2001/02, NERC was undergoing a change in accounting procedures to resource accounting in line with other research councils and government departments. This meant that NERC had extremely limited available funding and indeed subsequently the July 2002 grants round had to be cancelled. A consequence was that NERC awarded £10M to NCAS, which was the maximum funding it had available at that time. A decision was therefore taken to utilise the £10 M over 4 years, rather than the more usual 5-year period, to ameliorate the funding problems that NCAS faced.

NERC are to consider the NCAS II Proposal, for funding from 1 April 2006 to 31 March 2011, at the Science and Innovation Strategy Board (SISB) meeting in February 2005. The NCAS II Proposal must be submitted to NERC by 31 October 2004. It will be peer-reviewed by national and international scientists and then a moderating panel of members of the NERC Peer Review College and SISB will decide on recommended grades for the Proposal to be provided to SISB. The NCAS II Proposal has a set of discrete science and technology themes each of which will be reviewed and graded. Each of the referees will see the whole proposal but be asked to pay particular attention to themes within their areas of expertise and otherwise make general comments about other aspects. In Annexes A to G associated with ToR No. 4 we provide a brief summary of the planned science and technology themes that will be included in the NCAS II proposal.

1. NCAS/BRITISH ATMOSPHERIC DATA CENTRE

1.1 Introduction and Background

"The role of the NCAS/British Atmospheric Data Centre (BADC) is to assist UK researchers to locate, access and interpret atmospheric data and to ensure the long-term integrity of atmospheric data produced by Natural Environment Research Council (NERC) projects."

The BADC is funded by NERC as one of a number of designated data centres established to carry out the NERC data policy. This policy is outlined in the NERC Data Policy Handbook, which outlines the responsibilities of both NERC funded researchers and the NERC designated data centres. As one of those centres, the BADC is responsible for

1. Ensuring the adequate physical custody, validation, dissemination and review/purging of data in the atmospheric sciences. (The BADC is not necessarily responsible for the stewardship of all atmospheric data, but it is expected to at least have contact with those who do).
2. Maintaining standards of data stewardship in the subject area.
3. Pro-actively seeking out data in their subject area meriting more active stewardship; encouraging the deposit of datasets by other organisations; and advising NERC-funded academics on whether and where their data should be deposited on completion of their projects.
4. Promoting the case for investment where necessary to facilitate the previous aims.
5. Promoting the use of data in the atmospheric sciences by devising and promulgating catalogues, directories, leaflets and brochures.
6. Formally arranging licenses to control the release of datasets to non-NERC recipients, the uses to which the datasets may be put, and their further dissemination; and to protect NERC from legal liability. Pricing data in accordance with NERC guidelines in order to derive revenue and/or other scientific benefits from NERC data resources.
7. Handling all requests for atmospheric data made to NERC with the specific invocation of the Environmental Information Regulations.
8. Maintaining up-to-date information on data holdings in atmospheric science on the World Wide Web.
9. Acting as a gateway to other NERC custodians of data from all disciplines. Holding and displaying catalogues, directories, leaflets and brochures relating to activities and holdings of other NERC Data Centres
10. Representing the atmospheric sciences within NERC on matters concerning data.

All these points are summarised in the BADC mission statement.

The BADC was established in 1995 when it superseded a previous facility: the Geophysical Data Facility (GDF). In the last decade (or so), the role of the BADC has expanded as it has become the defacto point of contact for U.K. researchers needing access to both meteorological and atmospheric earth observation products from the Met Office, the ECMRWF, ESA and NASA.

NERC and the steering committee responsible for guiding the BADC over the years prior to the establishment of NCAS recognised that the BADC needed strong scientific leadership, along with a resident in-house scientific research programme, to ensure that the BADC was able to recognise strategic opportunities and tactically to deploy relevant solutions.

The BADC is currently funded via a NERC Service Level Agreement (SLA) with the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL). The SLA consists of core funding derived from NCAS and additional funding from the NERC Data Management Advisory Group (DMAG) and NERC "thematic" programmes (now called "directed" programmes). NCAS core funding is designed to support those activities listed above which are not carried out and/or funded by individual researchers and/or NERC thematic/directed programmes as well as to support data management activities within the other NCAS centres. DMAG funding supports the provision of services for the wider community including the maintenance of the NERC Metadata Gateway and the maintenance and development of systems to assist non-atmospheric scientists to utilise atmospheric science data. In addition, BADC receives significant research funding via grants. This report primarily covers both NCAS and DMAG direct funding (hereafter "core"), although elements of support for the other activities are covered where such work impacted on the core activities and/or have long term implications.

1.2 Major Developments

The reporting period covers essentially three years: 2001-2, 2002-3 and 2003-4. During the first year, BADC was operating as a standalone NERC collaborative centre, before joining the NCAS partnership for the last two years.

1.2.1 Staff Movements

Because directed programme funding generally comes in such a way that BADC needs to deploy core staff for much of the work until enough funding has come to employ someone to catch up on the core activities, staff deployed on the core SLA have varied during the period. However, key new staff employed by the BADC in this period who have or will receive significant core funding have included:

- Mr Sam Dean (1 year from mid 2001)
- Ms Sue Latham (since late 2002, half funded by the NERC DataGrid)
- Ms Mila De Vere (since early 2003, a variety of funding sources)
- Dr Alison Pamment (half time since early 2003).
- Dr Wendy Garland (since mid-2003, mainly funded by directed programmes).
- Dr Martin Jukes (joined in late 2001 primarily funded by a NERC Advanced Research Fellowship, now funded on the BADC core).

During this period there has been a steady expansion in funding from thematic programmes and grants, which have primarily funded data management and atmospheric science research respectively, but since the advent of e-science, additionally fund a considerable component of computer-science research which has positioned the BADC to be world-leaders in a number of areas (outlined below). E-science funding now supports:

- Ms Marta Gutterez (100%) and Ms Sue Latham (50%)

as well as two staff in the CCLRC/RAL e-science centre who are working directly on BADC and wider NERC data issues. Further e-science and DMAG funding has arisen as a consequence of the work done thus far (an additional £100K from mid-2004, and a new 0.5 FTE position from mid-2004 respectively).

1.2.2 BADC Computer Systems

Within the reporting period, the BADC has moved from a system based primarily on a central multiprocessor Compaq-Alpha (tornado) to a distributed system based on multiple linux platforms and network attached storage. Total disk storage has increased approximately ten-fold (currently about 30 TB), and a tape library system has been installed which is capable of supporting in excess of 35 TB:

BADC Computer Configuration (May 2004)

Storage Resource Broker technology coupled with changes in network and systems hardware and charging regimes now mean that the BADC expects to start utilising the RAL Atlas Tape Store, a PB capable system, by mid-2004. This will provide additional near-line facility that will scale into the future. Further on-line disk capability and systems for analysis were the subject of an NCAS infrastructure bid in early 2004, the result is currently unknown.

Significant effort has been expended on software systems to manage the influx of data, and this will remain an issue into the future.

1.2.3 Co-Funded Activities

A number of NERC thematic (directed) programmes have utilised and funded the BADC during this period. The data management of most programmes involves standard tasks such as liaison with the scientists and the programme steering committees, provision of data management plans and data protocols, archival, documentation and distribution of data, etc. Where possible development has been aimed at generic use (e.g., the provision of a web-based file uploader, the adoption of metadata standards, rationalised file name conventions, etc.).

More specifically, the work for directed programmes in the review period has included the following.

- **UTLS Ozone** – Attendance and presentations at UTLS science workshops. Data management in liaison with the Programme Manager and Programme Assistant (regular meetings). Reports to Steering Committee every 6 months. Contributions to UTLS Ozone newsletter. Scoping study for 4th round projects. Visits to project investigators and follow-up of project development and outcome. Website update. Archival, documentation and provision of model data (SLIMCAT chemical “climatology”) as a support to all UTLS projects. Links to external supporting archives (THESEO, CARIBIC). Filling gaps in Unified Model (UM) data and improvement of UM data transfer from the Met Office in order to provide a contiguous data set (important for trajectory calculation). Investigation and evaluation of tools to visualise and manipulate UM data. Preliminary work to set up a prototype Live Access Server (LAS) for application to UM data. Expansion of the online trajectory calculator to accept global UM wind fields as an input (object of a presentation at the EGS Annual General Assembly). Work (including liaison with NERC and ESA) towards the provision of satellite data to the UTLS Ozone community (successful proposals to archive and distribute data from MIPAS, GOMOS and SCIAMACHY onboard the Envisat satellite). Support to field campaigns and data providers. Archival of data generated by some of the projects. Provision of collaborative workspace to the ICARTT community. Provision of web interface to forecast products for ICARTT. Set up of website, file uploader, separate protected archive (in agreement with UTLS Ozone, ICARTT and FAAM requirements) and BADC catalogue entry for the ITOP project. Study, discussion and adoption of data format and file name conventions common to BADC and ICARTT. Provision of ITOP-UK Conditions of Use.
- **AARDAOS** – Liaison with data providers. Delivery of Data Management Plan. Website and protected archive set up. Archival of Cambridge assimilated data on atmospheric chemical composition. Archival and documentation of Ozone and Temperature Assimilated Data from Reading. Provision of supporting radar rainfall data (NIMROD) to one investigator. Reports to Programme Manager.
- **URGENT** – Attendance and presentations at URGENT science meetings. Data management coordination in liaison with CEH, BGS and URGENT steering committee representatives. Hosting of URGENT Data Management website until its transfer to CEH. Attendance at Data Management and Quality Assurance (DMQA) Committee meetings. Reports to Quality Assurance Manager and Programme Science Coordinator. Provision of online documentation on data format (NASA Ames) and metadata. Provision of secure archive, BADC data set catalogue entry, web pages including documentation on projects and links to URGENT website. Repeated requests to project principal investigators regarding data submission. Extensive support to data providers. Reformatting, archival, documentation, distribution and release of data submitted by URGENT projects. Provision of online catalogue of URGENT data held at BADC. Presentation of URGENT Air archive at national and international conferences. Provision of thesaurus relevant to atmospheric environmental data. Contribution to URGENT metadata library and data dissemination.
- **CWVC** – Attendance and BADC presentations at CWVC science meetings. Data scoping study. Liaison with investigators of projects awarded in successive rounds. Liaison with CWVC Science Coordinator. Provision of Data Management Plan, Data Protocol and data management budget. Attendance at Steering Committee meetings. Reports to

CWVC Steering Committee every 6 months. Provision of website, protected archive, online data uploader, entry in BADC dataset catalogue, documentation on data formats (NASA Ames, NetCDF, HDF, Hitran), metadata and data submission. Reminders to data providers. Support to data providers. Archival of data generated by some CWVC projects. Acquisition, documentation and provision of supporting data sets (CLOUDMAP, ISCCP, CLAUS, CWAVE, SAGE II). Work (including liaison with NERC and ESA) towards the provision of satellite data to the CWVC community (successful proposals to archive and distribute MERIS data from the Envisat satellite).

- COAPEC - Extraction, documentation and distribution of results from the 100-year and 1000-year control runs of the HadCM3 model from the Hadley Centre. Provision of data conversion and subsetting tools. Work towards the provision of an operational Live Access Server (LAS) to manipulate and visualise HadCM3 data (a test LAS has been produced). Website maintenance and update. Provision of a collaborative workspace. Provision of supporting seasonal "hindcast" datasets from ECMWF. Work towards the provision of additional parameters derived from the HadCM3 dataset. 6-month reports. COAPEC also supports one member of the COAPEC core team based at BADC with the main aim of facilitating wider participation by the scientific community in coupled ocean-atmosphere modelling. Alan Iwi provides expertise on the use of coupled ocean-atmosphere models on Beowulf clusters and high performance Linux based PCs for the community, provides properly validated versions of the Unified Model are available for use on these systems, and works on aspects of coupled ocean-atmosphere modelling.
- Polluted Troposphere – Attendance and presentations at Polluted Troposphere science meetings and workshops. Attendance at Steering Committee meetings. Liaison with Programme Officer. Liaison with all project investigators, including visits to universities. Data scoping study. Provision of Data Management Plan, Data Protocol, data management budget. Provision of collaborative workspace. Provision of website, secure archive, file uploader, documentation on projects, data format and metadata, file name conventions, submission directions. Support to first TORCH campaign (retrieval of near real time and forecast ECMWF winds and update of online trajectory code to allow scientists to compute forecast trajectories, support to data providers regarding format, etc.). Archival and documentation of TORCH data from the first campaign. First annual report to SC.
- RAPID Climate Change – Attendance at kick-off and science meetings. Provision of preliminary study of data issues to support the joint BODC/BADC proposal of data management. Visits to project investigators. Data scoping study including cost assessment. Liaison with Programme Science Coordinator and with the BODC (regular meetings). Provision of access to ERA-40 and HadCM3 model data to some project investigators. Successful investigation of the possibility to provide Hadley Centre model data to the programme participants.

The long term maintenance of datasets acquired under the auspices of these programmes has (or will when the programme terminates) become the responsibility of NCAS core funding.

The following NERC grants have directly impacted on BADC activities (as opposed to stand-alone research grants which are not covered here).

- Jukes: Advanced Research Fellowship. This fellowship has supported Jukes for most of the duration of this report and has effectively doubled the atmospheric science research effort available to core BADC activities.
- Lawrence: The NERC DataGrid (NDG, from September 2002). BADC has and continues to provide intellectual leadership to this project, as well as some core resources in the area of metadata development. The NDG project is based primarily on the development of distributed solutions to provide transparent access to data holdings in the atmospheric and oceanographic sciences. A working prototype exists based CGI-scripts, and is being evolved to web-services and other grid paradigms. NDG is leading the development of standards based metadata structures for environmental grids. In 2003-04, NDG produced four refereed contributions and three other significant papers.
- Grainger: Global Retrieval of ATSR Cloud Parameters and Evaluation (GRAPE) (BADC Co-Investigator: Lawrence). BADC is hosting the computational cluster and providing expertise to support the data handling (this is multiple tens of TB-scale project). Key work has involved solving IO bandwidth problems in the cluster as well as the development of data handling software. The project is about to produce it's first coherent multi-year global cloud products at 3-km resolution.
- Allen: *climateprediction.net* - distributed computing for global climate research (BADC Co-Investigator: Kettleborough). The key strength of the BADC in this project has been to provide staff with a knowledge of climate science, general circulation modelling, and computer technologies. This has meant the BADC has had the pivotal role between climate science and computer science. This has involved identifying the problems unique to a distributed climate model ensemble and how these problems can be solved by the available computing technologies. The BADC has been involved in the design and development of the prototype for managing the distributed ensemble, and is currently helping to define the data analysis problem. In 2003-2004 this work has resulted in co-authorship on 3 climate science publications in press, and 3 computer science publications.
- Slingo: UK-HIGEM (BADC Co-Investigator: Lawrence). The BADC is providing data support for high resolution earth system modelling. This includes development and support systems for the exchange of knowledge and data between the project partners. The volumes of data involved in the context of a collaborative high resolution modelling project will involve new software and possibly hardware solutions to aid the analysis of model data.
- Thorpe: Earth Simulator (BADC Co-Investigator: Lawrence). One of the difficulties involved in utilising the Earth Simulator is the transfer of data from the Japanese facility to back to the United Kingdom. The BADC is involved in identifying pathways and implementing methods for enabling this data transfer. Management of the data shares much in common with the UK-HiGEM and over the next two years progress made on these projects will mean the BADC is one of the world leaders in data management of large earth system model datasets.

The U.S. NOAA has supported Dr Jo Murray in the development of new sea-surface temperature analysis algorithms. (It will be seen below that the development and deployment of analysis and assimilation algorithms are key components of the BADC research programme).

From mid-2003, DEFRA has been funding the BADC (approximately 0.5 FTE), in partnership with the University of East Anglia (~0.5 FTE) to provide the Climate Impacts LINK programme – a service to provide Hadley Centre climate data to the impacts community.

2. OUTCOMES AND PROGRESS (2001-2004)

BADC core tasks are divided into ten core work packages. Each work package is described in a BADC technical annex to the SLA between NERC and RAL, and quarterly reports are produced for NERC which require approval from the Director of NCAS before SLA funding is released. Annual reports have been produced based on the material in the quarterly reports, and these are summarised here. (To help interpretation, the text in shaded box is what appears in the current technical annex and essentially describes what the BADC is required to do).

2.1 Routine Activities

CWP01. Acquisition of observational meteorological data

- Continue to acquire and distribute observational data from the Met Office.

The list below shows the verity of datasets covered by this package. In general these data have separate extraction methods and Met Office contacts. A great deal of effort has gone into coordinating these diverse data flows. The only major break in this service was during the Met Office move to Exeter in July/August 2003.

- GOSTAplus SST and sea ice.
- European Synoptic stations data (1990 - 1996)
- Global Radiosonde Data
- Global Mean Sea-Level Pressure
- GISST/MOHMATN4/MOHSST6 - Global Ice coverage and SST
- HadISST 1.1 - Global sea-Ice coverage and SST (1870-Present) [New 03/04]
- Global Radiosonde Gridded Temperature Anomalies
- Central England Temperature Data
- Northern Hemisphere Geopotential Height (1945-present)
- Northern Hemisphere Mean Sea Level Pressure fields (1873-present)
- Rain radar products (NIMROD) [New 02/03]
- TOVS Stratospheric Analyses
- UK High Resolution Radiosonde Data
- UK Land Surface Stations data (1900-present)

- Wind Profiler data (1998-onwards) [New 03/04]
- Meteosat Images of Europe

The most popular dataset (1300 registered users) that the BADC distributes is the Met Office UK Land Surface Stations data (1900-present). Much effort has been expended ensuring that the ordering service for this data works smoothly.

Through extensive negotiations with ECMWF and the Met Office the BADC obtained permission to distribute the 40-year long observation dataset that was assimilated into the ERA-40. These data are now nearing release.

CWP02. Acquisition of NWP from the Met Office and ECMWF

- Continue acquisition of both ERA40 and operational analyses from ECMWF and make available to the user community with a new interface.
- Provide access to Met Office NWP data at global and mesoscale resolution.

ECMWF operational data continues to be extracted daily. This data includes data streams designed to be the same resolution as the ERA-15 and ERA-40 archives to facilitate use of the data. Monthly means of the data are also available.

ECMWF ERR-40 data is now archived at the BADC. This includes 6-hourly analysis, monthly 6-hourly means and monthly diurnal means. A caching system was devised to allow conversion to regular gridded products. Aggregated metadata files have been created to allow users to access all 40 years of data from one file.

The BADC has been providing ongoing near real-time ECMWF data in support of research projects (VINTERSOL, CLOUDMAP2, HIBISCUS, TORCH, TROCCINOX).

Met Office NWP data from global and mesoscale models has been extracted on a regular basis. At the start of the review period this was done via tapes sent in the post, but this was later upgraded to FTP transfers. The extraction of the Met Office Unified Model (UM) data has been disrupted due to the MO move, the failure of the met office MASS system and other technical difficulties. This has left the archive with big gaps. However, we are hopeful that a new method based on the "METVIEW" software will be far more efficient and effective than the previous system, and we are in the process of filling the gaps.

In 2003 the BADC Live Access Server was introduced. This provides a web-interface with tools to manipulate an archive of terabytes of data. Plots, animations and data files can be easily extracted without accessing files directly. While is at present connected to the ERA-40 and COAPEC data sets, and will soon be connected to the UM data, there have been significant technical difficulties associated with access control. These, coupled with worries about long term maintenance, have meant that we have developed an alternative system, which we expect to deploy shortly.

CWP03. User support

- Provide "data services" to BADC users, including user information on BADC and other relevant data sets and a directory of WWW links.

- Provide support to NERC scientists from outside the atmospheric community who require Met. data for their research.
- Continue to provide a prompt and effective user support service to the atmospheric science community, primarily for UK scientists.

2469 identifiable users downloaded 13 TB of data in 10 million files over this period.

At the start of the review period there were 1400 user registered for one or more datasets or services. At the end of the period this has risen to over 2700. The total number of registered users now stands at about 4900.

Approximately 3000 user queries were answered this review period.

In 2003 we implemented a new user query management system (footprints). This distributes, tracks and analyses queries more efficiently, and we expect to be able to utilise it to support some NCAS wide activities as well as BADC only issues. It is being used with our LINK project to coordinate queries between BADC and the University of East Anglia.

CWP04. System infrastructure

- Provide an online catalogue of all BADC data sets to help users to find the data they require.
- Continue to develop and enhance the infrastructure of the BADC, including the development of underpinning work for e-science activities.

The BADC has provided an online catalogue of all BADC data sets to help users to find the data they require.

In order to efficiently plan storage hardware purchasing and commissioning a data volume plan has been created. This details the likely data sources and volumes over the next 3 years. This plan is updated regularly and the current technology examined to ensure cost effective storage solutions.

The BADC hardware infrastructure consists a number of servers, disk storage devices and tape libraries, along with a machine room to house these and associated networking. The main changes within this review period have been:

A move from direct attached storage (DAS) to network attached storage (NAS). We now have about 20 TB of this type of storage.

Replacement air conditioning has been installed in the main BADC computer room.

We moved our services from a single Compaq server to a cluster of Linux machines. The BADC services are split amount these servers in order to manage load and reduce the interdependence of services. This has improved reliability and performance, will be easier to upgrade and have a greater availability of software.

Software infrastructure:

- The new BADC website was launched at the end of April 2002. The new website had many new features including, improved layout and navigation, better help information,

a simplified dataset registration procedure and better facilities for searching BADC web pages.

- The BADC FTP server was replaced with the ProFTP server. This enabled us to reduce the number of users who have login accounts on our Unix server. Users can now access our services via 'virtual' account. This makes our services less dependent on the underlying operating system, more secure and easier to administer. It also permits the use of a different access control mechanism that is easier to control and more flexible.
- Significant improvements been made in user registration system. The improvements make it easier for users, reduce the workload on the BADC team members and reduce the possibility of errors being made.
- As mentioned in the User support section, new helpdesk management software was installed and is now operational. This will help us manage user queries in a more efficient manner and provide better monitoring of the query handling process.
- The BADC has proactively maintained its expertise at the forefront of storage technology by seeking advice and attending meeting such as EU DataGrid and Grid Global forums. Most significantly the BADC is the major partner in The NERC DataGrid, an e-science funded project to transparently couple the NERC data holdings.
- One of the most potentially useful e-science tools to be developed is the Storage Resource Broker (SRB) produced by the San Diego Super Computer Centre. This offers virtualised storage across media and thus improves manageability of data greatly. We are have been tracking its development for the last few years and are now developing a pilot project for its use within the data centre.
- We are currently developing software to extend the capabilities of the PCMDI CDAT package to allow binary "PP" format files to be read directly. This will enable a number of large Met Office datasets (such as NWP) to be served via a dedicated LAS server.
- A new lightweight prototype "LAS-like" server has been developed which will be easier to couple into our existing systems than the LAS, and easier to the migrate to NERC DataGrid.

CWP05. Data Support Activities for NCAS

- Provide advice to the Director of DIAC about data issues for the new centre.
- Provide both technical and management advice for existing data activities in the NCAS centres.
- Transition to a regime where the BADC is responsible for (but not necessarily funding) data activities within the constituent NCAS centres.

In the first year, this package was called "Programme Support" and contained items about support for old thematic programmes. These activities are now reported in the Data Archaeology section.

The BADC has finalised a Data Management Plan and Data Protocol to UFAM that may be extended to other observation types.

The BADC provided Data Management support for the UFAM field campaign NAMBLEX (North Atlantic Marine Boundary Layer EXperiment). This work involved acquiring third party

data, producing a data protocol, delivering guidelines, documentation and cataloguing, and providing a CAST discussion forum for data sharing.

The BADC data holdings from the Chilbolton observatory has acquired and extended to complement UFAM and UWERN programmes. This includes data from the radar, radio links, meteorological sensors, UV lidar and rain gauges.

The BADC has received a GPS Integrated Water Vapour dataset located at the Aberystwyth MST radar facility.

The Hadley Centre NetCDF Climate and Forecast (CF) Metadata Convention checking programme has been converted into a service available via the Internet by the BADC. Users, in particular instrument scientists, can now upload files to check their compliance with the CF convention.

The FAAM data protocol was written by the BADC and was accepted by the Operations Committee on the 8th of September 2003

Following a demand from the manager of the MRF Facilities, a workspace has been set up in 2003 for the FAAM scientists involved in the BAE 146-301 aircraft test flights, to allow temporary storage of output from the tested instruments. Access to the site is via FTP and is password protected.

As part of its support for UFAM and other instrumental datasets the BADC has created a web-based file format converter from Excel spreadsheet form to NetCDF. This will be advertised to the wider community after trial users have given feedback.

The BADC has set up a file naming convention for instrumental data files in order to standardize filenames across projects, avoid potential duplication and improve clarity and future access to the data.

The BADC hosted the NCAS web site until April 2004. This site gives contact information, news items, reports and documents relating to NCAS, as well as links to the NCAS component centres.

CWP06. Services and CAST

- Provide integrating services for NCAS, including the NCAS web site and evaluate network-based tools for distributed document management and video conferencing etc.
- Continue to provide existing CAST tools including: the collaborative workspaces, poster heaven, and the trajectory service.

The Collaboratory for Atmospheric science and technology (CAST) was absorbed into the BADC five years ago, and since then BADC has had responsibility for providing collaboration and other services for the UK atmospheric science community. In 2003 NCAS decided to drop the brand CAST, but to continue the work. In the future, the new work package will be renamed "Community Services". Services include:

- News and upcoming conference and meeting information.

- Email distribution and discussion lists – These are community based lists to facilitate communication.
- Meetings tools – We offer a “Meeting registration service”, to collect details from the participants and Meeting Date Organiser, a tool to pick meeting dates. The Meeting registration service was used successfully for the NERC FREE and QUEST and the NCAS Framework 6 Town meetings.
- Links and Highlighted sites – providing information about external sites of interest to atmospheric science. These have been updated continually over the review period.
- Workspaces and Project Spaces - Document and data sharing for communities. This has been particularly popular and has been used by COAPEC, NAMBLEX, Solar Variability Polluted Troposphere, CEH, the NERC DMAG, and the NERC DataGrid.
- The *Who's Who* service - enabling users to find details of other users whose work may be of interest to them. Several different ways of searching the *Who's Who* database are available, including searching by research description and searching by registered dataset.

CWP07. Data archaeology

- Continue to provide support for access to historical atmospheric chemistry data, including the maintenance of the primary archive for ACSOE data.
- Continue to be proactive (within the available funding) about acquiring datasets from within both the NERC community and the wider atmospheric sciences community.

Supporting old data

Many of the datasets held at the BADC are updated with new information and data as it becomes available. The examples below illustrate these activities

- The public release of the ACSOE data programme data.
- In conjunction with the NERC Data Grid project, NASA-Ames (NA) data is being examined for compliance to new semantic standards as well as stricter compliance to the NA format. New versions of non-compliant file will be produced to facilitate ongoing curation.
- Following the discontinuation of availability of Meteosat data from Nottingham University a new source of has been established and images are now received directly from Eumetsat in Darmstadt, Germany.
- External web site capture to document the ISAMS dataset has been carried out.

New acquisitions

- Substantial effort was put into the acquisition of high-resolution radiosonde data from the Met Office. This data was not properly archived within the Met Office and was inaccessible and in danger of being lost. After extensive negotiations and technical challenges we acquired the data and now receive annual updates.

- The BADC houses a production release of the Cloud Archive User Service (CLAUS) Project data was supported by the European Union under the IVth Framework Programme (Environment and Climate) and ran from April 1997 to December 1999. The UGAMP community has requested this data.
- The Berlin Stratospheric Dataset containing stratospheric temperature and geopotential height data from radiosonde data and rocket observations has been added to the BADC archive.
- The Met Office boundary layer wind profilers dataset has been added to the archive. This dataset will complement other radar data from UFAM and the MSTR data.
- The Bolton Experiment Dataset has been received, catalogued and added to the BADC archive. This was a joint NERC-Industry funded project.

CWP08. Liaison and publicity

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| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote the BADC through regular representation at scientific meetings and the provision of appropriate publicity materials. • Continue to liaise with atmospheric data centres elsewhere and data centres from other disciplines within the U.K. |
|--|

Science meetings

BADC staff regularly attend and present at science meetings and conference in order to interact and obtain feedback on BADC services. These included:

- **2001-2002:** URGENT annual meeting, EGS (Middle Atmosphere and Urban Atmospheres sessions), Academic seminars at Leicester and Imperial College, UTLS workshop, MODAS-2001 meeting, Symposium of NDSC and Royal Meteorological Society meetings
- **2002-2003:** EGS (Nice), PRISM (Hadley Centre), URGENT, 6th HDF-EOS meeting (San Francisco), ERCA (Grenoble), HIRDLS (Reading) and NOMADS (Boulder).
- **2003-2004:** UWERN modelling workshop, Royal Met Soc meeting, Computing in Atmospheric Science meeting, and an Earth Sciences Portal Meeting, plus numerous e-science meetings.

NERC Programmes and data centres

Liaison with scientists (science coordinators, principal investigators, graduate students) took place in the context of the data management associated to NERC thematic programmes (URGENT, Data Assimilation, CWVC, Rapid, UTLS, etc) and core strategic activities (UWERN/UFAM, FAAM).

The BADC is represented as the NERC Data Management Advisory Group (DMAG) and is in regular contact with Mark Thorley, the NERC data coordinator

Data suppliers

- Ag Stephens was appointed as the BADC-Met Office Coordinator at the end of December 2003. He has been based at the Met Office in Exeter from the 1st of April 2004. He recently attended the Met office systems and products course, which has proved a rich source of information.
- A tripartite meeting was held between Met Office, ECMWF and BADC staff in November covering a range of issues of mutual interest. This meeting formed the first of the focus group meetings foreshadowed in the 2002-03 strategic aims.

Data centres

- Many discussions between NCAR and the Max Plank Institute for Meteorology in Hamburg have been undertaken with a view to provided integrated access to some data holdings in the three institutions (initially by bilateral agreements).
- The BADC was represented at the ERPANET/CODATA International Archiving Workshop on the Selection, Appraisal, and Retention of Digital Scientific Data, Lisbon, 15-17 December 2003.
- The BADC has contributed to the final bid for the CCLRC consortium bid to become part of the UK Energy Research Centre (UKERC). Regrettably, BADC pulled out of the consortium when the funding became too small to provide adequate requirements definition to the BADC.
- Prof. Evgueni Gordov (Institute of Atmospheric Optics, Tomsk) visited as part of the BADC involvement in the INTAS funded ATMOS project.

Other

- Bryan Lawrence has been appointed to the Joint Information Systems Committee subcommittee in support of Research.
- A leaflet including the BADC data set catalogue has been produced and distributed at meetings.

CWP09. Research

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| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintain validity and relevance of BADC activities by carrying out an active research programme in gravity wave parameterisation, cloud parameterisation, and data assimilation research. |
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The BADC research activities have previously been aimed at primarily ensuring that BADC staff are well plugged into the atmospheric science research community (computer science research funded by the NDG activity is reported elsewhere). During this period, we have begun to add an emphasis on how existing data can be exploited to produce new datasets and/or diagnostics. In the reporting period SLA funding has supported one FTE, who has variously been Sam Dean, Alison Pamment and Martin Jukes (Alison continues to be supported on this contract as Martin is now always charging his time to the SLA, and Alison is 50% FTE).

Martin Jukes is an assistant editor for the Quarterly Journal of the Royal Met Society and convened an open session on the lower, middle and upper atmosphere at the joint assembly of

EGS and AGU, which was well attended and attracted a high standard of presentations on a wide range of topics. He is also acting as secretary to the dynamical problems specialist group of the Royal Met Society.

The main research activities fall into three areas: model development and evaluation, dataset synthesis and evaluation, and diagnostic and dynamics work.

Model Development and Evaluation.

In the model development and evaluation area we have concentrated on two strands: the exploitation of novel computational environments (beowulf clusters), and the influence of orographic processes on both dynamics and cloud cover.

- A Beowulf cluster was commissioned, and with co-funding from COAPEC, the Unified Model was ported to the beowulf environment. This work has been so successful that both the COAPEC programme and the Met Office both obtained their own beowulf clusters. COAPEC funding has directly supported this activity since soon after its inception.
- Sam Dean developed a new parameterisation of orographic cirrus in the Unified Model. This parameterisation is based on using linear theory to predict subgrid-scale temperature perturbations as a function of height, this information is then fed into the cloud parameterisation scheme. As part of this he obtained the ISCCP cloud climatology and negotiated the redistribution of this data via the BADC for research purposes. Dean successfully completed his doctorate and moved to Oxford University. Two publications are in preparation (one submitted).
- From October 2003, a graduate student is being supported by a CAST studentship at Oxford University. This student (Jonathan Flowerdew) is working on techniques to evaluate cloud parameterisations by direct comparison with satellite observations, and in particular the ATSR2 cloud retrievals from the GRAPE project. An initial comparison of ERA40 cloud with ISCCP and the "old-UM" cloud scheme has been completed, as has the software to produce ATSR2 sampling of model variables at runtime. A simple nudging scheme within the UM to force the climate model to follow real meteorological events has been implemented.
- Alison Pamment joined the BADC, and began work on the MPP version of Bryan Lawrence's coupled orographic and spectral gravity wave scheme (a variation of the "Hines" scheme). The coupled scheme has been previously employed in a single processor stratosphere and mesosphere model, but not in a full GCM running in MPP mode. This scheme will allow an evaluation of the impact of the importance of coupling on both tropospheric and middle atmosphere dynamics. As of mid-June 2004 the work has progressed to evaluation of numerical instabilities associated with the large accelerations involved (rapid progress has been held up by coding errors introduced by a former graduate student who worked on the project as well as the numerical problems).

Dataset synthesis

The main thrust of BADC data assimilation activities is exploring methodologies for constructing coherent analyses of observational datasets. While ERA40 and the like exploit assimilation schemes based on NWP codes, BADC has concentrated on techniques to exploit the fact that all the data is available a priori.

- The Lorenz chaotic attractor has been used to explore fundamental aspects of data assimilation. In particular, it has been used to explore problems associated with combining data and complex non-linear dynamical equations. Initial work began using a single level isentropic tracer advection model of the stratosphere to start applying the theory to satellite measurements of ozone and nitric acid. The work with the Lorenz model demonstrated the capability of the new algorithm, which was developed to derive information about variables that are not directly observed. The algorithm, termed the "Direct Minimisation Algorithm" can be applied to a moderately large problem without incurring significant computational costs and has been shown analytically to be equivalent to a Kalman Smoother. (The current implementation is dependent on an external dynamic assimilation to provide winds).
- The simple harmonic oscillator has been analysed in detail to understand how assimilation systems are influenced by empirical approximations to error covariance matrices. This work has demonstrated the superiority of solutions using the full range of observations over sequential methods which only use observations prior to and within a limited analysis window.
- Application of the direct minimisation algorithm to data has included work on GOME, where data from both ESA and RAL algorithms has been included with MIPAS, HALOE, SBUV, POAM III and SAGE. Significant differences between these data have been identified using "nearly coincident" observations, and the assimilation approach gives significant added value. While only limited amounts of RAL GOME data and MIPAS are currently available, 8-years of the ESA GOME data (using a KNMI algorithm) are now available (via a new direct collaboration with ESA), and the BADC is about to acquire the entire historical MIPAS data set at both levels one and two. Analyses constructed in this way can provide better estimates of chemical state than those done with NWP systems because they do not thin the data, and they can use all the data in the assimilation period (although they are dependent on an NWP system to provide best estimates of winds). The algorithm has considerable potential for further development as it dramatically reduces the cost, relative to operational an experimental algorithms being developed elsewhere, of calculating an optimal analysis from a large observational dataset. The challenge in the coming year will be to extend the current implementation to include assimilation of temperature retrievals to infer winds in the stratosphere.

A number of papers are in preparation discussing both the techniques and their application to data. The work has been presented at a number of meetings both nationally and internationally.

As described above, BADC is involved in the construction of sea surface temperature analyses from a variety of space-based sensors. This work has been entirely funded by the U.S. National Oceanographic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), but BADC have contributed project management and technical advice.

Diagnostics and Dynamics

Juckes has been working on mixing and transport in the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere in mid-latitudes. An invited review on this topic was presented at the joint AGU/EGS conference in Nice. This work has shown that there is mean equatorward motion in the lowermost stratosphere in the ERA40 data. This line of work will now be extended to examine the energetic structure of the circulation in the troposphere and lowermost stratosphere. The mean circulation has been calculated in thermodynamic variables (pressure and temperature), instead of the usual height/latitude formulation. This gives a direct

illustration of the link between the meridional overturning of the atmosphere and the conversion of potential energy to kinetic energy which drives weather systems. The thermodynamic cycle is characterised by a single overturning cell, with air rising in the tropics and descending in the winter polar region (this resembles the isentropic meridional mass circulation). The annual cycle and interannual variability of this flow structure will now be analysed. The changes in the energetic cycle between the warm years since 1990 and the earlier years will be analysed and linked to other measures of the meridional circulation.

Lawrence and Stephens have been involved in the Solve2 project, where we have been evaluating the use of ECMWF data in the prediction of low stratospheric temperature regions using the US NRL prediction codes (one paper, submitted).

Graduate students working in New Zealand, under the (remote co-) supervision of Lawrence have completed new techniques to;

- Evaluate mesospheric electron densities and their dynamical impact (one paper in print, one submitted)
- Evaluate the impact of Antarctic Ozone Depletion on mid-latitude ozone (one paper in print, one further accepted for publication).

CWP10. METADATA GATEWAY

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| <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Maintain the NERC metadata gateway, including the addition of links to new data sources at other NERC centres and the development of technology refreshes.• Provide technical support for the other NERC data centres. |
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- At the start of the review period the NERC Metadata Gateway was installed on the ageing machine on which it was developed. This was moved to the BADC primary server and upgraded to use the latest version of Isite software on which the service is based. After these changes the NMG ran smoothly for the review period.
 - The search forms have been updated and simplified.
 - The BADC catalogue is now searchable from the national Gigateway search page. Ongoing discussions with AGI continue on relevant search technologies.
 - Assistance was provided to BAS when their *zserver* stopped functioning. The server is now back up and running.
 - BADC Z39.50 expertise was used by the NERC DataGrid project during the design phase.

2.2 Project Management and Current List of Services

Day-to-day management of BADC activities now revolves around “the project database”, which is used to manage, describe and report against both short-term projects, and the long term services which are deployed. The development and deployment of this database was a major achievement in 2003, and along with the footprints database used to managed user queries has

contributed significantly to better internal communication, and more effective use of staff time and resources.

By way of summary of the breadth of specific current services, the following is a listing as of late May 2004 (note that short term projects are not listed):

Review services	
[Overview]	
32: [Edit] [Reports] BADC Storage	service Mila De Vere
33: [Edit] [Reports] Web pages maintenance	service Anabelle Menochet
34: [Edit] [Reports] Maintance of FTP service	service Andrew Harwood
35: [Edit] [Reports] Maintain the Data Browser	service Andrew Harwood
36: [Edit] [Reports] User Support	service Anabelle Menochet
37: [Edit] [Reports] Met Office data extraction	service Anabelle Menochet
38: [Edit] [Reports] Maintain a News service	service Anabelle Menochet
39: [Edit] [Reports] Who's who service	service Chris Harrold
40: [Edit] [Reports] Conference list maintenance	service Anne De Rudder
41: [Edit] [Reports] Links search engine	service Andrew Harwood
42: [Edit] [Reports] Maintain highlighted sites	service Anne De Rudder
43: [Edit] [Reports] Maintance of the web trajectory service	service Jamie Kettleborough
44: [Edit] [Reports] Maintainance of the BSCW Workspaces	service Andrew Harwood
45: [Edit] [Reports] Maintance of the discussion forums	service Andrew Harwood
46: [Edit] [Reports] Email lists service	service Andrew Harwood
47: [Edit] [Reports] Poster Heaven	service Chris Harrold
48: [Edit] [Reports] Meeting registration service	service Andrew Harwood
49: [Edit] [Reports] Maintain NERC metadata gateway	service Andrew Harwood
50: [Edit] [Reports] Met office stations search service	service Andrew Harwood
51: [Edit] [Reports] Maintain a Dataset catalogue	service Sam Pepler
52: [Edit] [Reports] File uploader	service Andrew Harwood
53: [Edit] [Reports] Statistics and reporting	service Bryan Lawrence
54: [Edit] [Reports] Advice to data providers	service Anne De Rudder
55: [Edit] [Reports] Support to NERC thematic programmes	service Anne De Rudder
56: [Edit] [Reports] Website hosting	service Sam Pepler
57: [Edit] [Reports] Data sets maintenance	service Sam Pepler
58: [Edit] [Reports] Maintaining the ACSOE catalogue	service Andrew Harwood
59: [Edit] [Reports] Maintain the web server	service Andrew Harwood
60: [Edit] [Reports] Maintaining user registration system and user database.	service Andrew Harwood
61: [Edit] [Reports] Zserver	service Andrew Harwood
67: [Edit] [Reports] System support	service Sam Pepler
68: [Edit] [Reports] ECMWF data extraction	service Ag Stephens
89: [Edit] [Reports] Support to the NCAS	service Anne De Rudder
90: [Edit] [Reports] Data and metadata formats	service Anne De Rudder
108: [Edit] [Reports] BADC Backup	service Mila De Vere
110: [Edit] [Reports] Research	service Martin Juckes
111: [Edit] [Reports] Training	service Sam Pepler

Figure 1: BADC Services in the Project Database

2.3 Use Statistics

This section presents key BADC usage statistics over the last three years, and the current distribution of BADC users.

As of June, 2004, the BADC has over 5000 registered users, of whom nearly 3000 have registered for access to restricted datasets. Of those, approximately half are NERC funded, and half are non-NERC funded – demonstrating that BADC contributes significantly to knowledge transfer out of the NERC regime. This is further illustrated by the figure below, which demonstrates how atmospheric science data from BADC is used by other disciplines.

If we look at the geographical usage of BADC data, we find that nearly 1600 users have given identifiable foreign addresses.

BADC users are mainly found in universities and government laboratories, which reflects the fact that most BADC data is restricted for research use only.

In the reporting period, the number of active users in any given month has steadily grown from an average of 225 in 2001 to an average of 300 in 2004:

Most BADC users get small subsets of data regularly, but download volumes reflect the activities of large users:

A more accurate reflection of BADC activity can be seen in the number of files downloaded per month. We expect these numbers to fall as we provide better tools for users to download graphics rather than data.

2.4 User Feedback

In April/May 2004, the BADC surveyed users who were registered for one or more datasets (i.e. active users). An email questionnaire including 10 questions was sent on 15th April 2004. Within the same day, a 4% response rate was received. Within a week, 7.5% responded, within a month, 8%. The questionnaire consisted of ten simple questions, covering

1. How the user found about the BADC
2. How often they used the BADC
3. How they used the BADC (e.g. small subsets of data versus entire datasets)
4. Whether they would use a software tools and library if one was provided
5. If so, what they would want to see
6. Experience with the BADC User Service
7. Overall Assessment
8. Would they recommend the BADC to colleagues
9. User perspective of BADC strengths
10. User perspective of BADC weaknesses.

A full analysis of the returns including verbatim answers to the textual questions is available on request from the BADC, but the following summarises the key points.

- Users normally find out about the BADC by word of mouth (60%) or a web search engine (20%), which corroborates with the 99% of users who would recommend the BADC services to colleagues. However, one of the weaknesses highlighted by some users was the lack of publicity for the BADC services, especially in universities.
- BADC services are generally used on a monthly basis (49% of respondees), primarily for downloading small subsets of data. In accordance with this, many users felt that providing subsetting tools would ease the download process. Roughly half (55%) of users would like to see a software archive at the BADC, with subsetting tools, file format libraries, and graphics packages most in demand. A number of users mentioned GIS.
- Approximately 40% of users did not interact with the helpdesk, but of those who did, all thought that the helpdesk was useful and prompt in response.
- 93% of users assess the BADC as providing very good or excellent services. Key strengths are range and quantity of data; coupled with fast network response, and prompt human response when needed.
- Key weaknesses identified included: access restrictions, lack of tools (subsetting, formatting etc), update frequency, and a variety of issues surrounding metadata (quality control, data analysis, "links to ecmwf pages not good enough", "more information about data sources" etc).

Nearly all the weaknesses have been previously identified, and efforts to address them are underway, including negotiations with data suppliers to remove or loosen access restrictions.

2.5 Key National and International Activities

International

- The BADC is currently working with the World Data Centre for Climate at the Max Plank Institute for Meteorology (MPIM, Hamburg) on methods to make data held at MPIM and BADC available to users of both data centres.
- The BADC is currently one of the co-leaders in the development of the Global Organisation for Earth System Science Portals (GO-ESSP, see www.esportal.gdfl.noaa.gov). This is a confederation of key software developers and data providers whose main aim is to provide better community access to scientific data.
- BADC is likely to be a key player in the development of long term support of data for the European PRISM federation.
- BADC is a member of the European Network for Earth Simulation (ENES), and was asked recently to present options to the ENES federation on how to use grid technology for Europe-wide access to key simulation and observational data sets.

National

- The NERC DataGrid. Described more fully below.
- The BADC is providing advice for the Met Office re-engineering project.
- The BADC is providing advice for the National Digital Curation Centre
- The BADC was asked to provide advice on the establishment of a data portal for the Marine community.
- BADC staff contribute to the membership of a significant number of national committees.

3. PUBLICATIONS

The main BADC output is data management and science support; however, the core research programme contributed to the following papers in the period under review:

2004:

- Grant, J., R. G. Grainger, B. N. Lawrence, G. J. Fraser and H. A. von Biel, 2004. Retrieval of Mesospheric Electron Densities Using an Optimal Inverse Method. *J. Atmos. Sol. Terr. Phys.*, 66, 381-392

2003

- Ajtic, J., B. J. Connor, C. E. Randall, B. N. Lawrence and G. E. Bodeker, 2003. Antarctic Air over New Zealand Following Vortex Breakdown in 1998. *Ann. Geophys.*, 21, . 2175-2183
- Lawrence, B. N., R. Cramer, M. Gutierrez, K. Kleese van Dam, S. Kondapalli, S. Latham, R. Lowry, K. O'Neill, and A. Woolf, 2003. The NERC DataGrid Prototype. *Proceedings of the U.K. e-science All Hands Meeting*, S.J.Cox (ed). ISBN 1-904425-11-9.
- Lowe D, MacKenzie AR, Nikiforakis N, Kettleborough J, 2003. A condensed-mass advection based model for the simulation of liquid polar stratospheric clouds. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 3, 29-38.

- O'Neill, K., R. Cramer, M. Gutierrez, K. Kleese van Dam, S. Kondapalli, S. Latham, B. N. Lawrence R. Lowry, and A. Woolf, 2003. The Metadata Model of the NERC DataGrid. Proceedings of the U.K. e-science All Hands Meeting, S.J.Cox (ed). ISBN 1-904425-11-9.
- Rutledge, G.K., J. Alpert, R.J. Stouffer and B. Lawrence, 2003. The NOAA Operational Model Archive and Distribution System (NOMADS) in Realizing Teracomputing. Proceedings of the Tenth ECMWF Workshop on the Use of High Performance Computing in Meteorology, Zwiefelhofer, W. and N. Kreitz (ed).
- Woolf, A., R. Cramer, M. Gutierrez, K. Kleese van Dam, S. Kondapalli, S. Latham, B. N. Lawrence, R. Lowry and K. O'Neill, 2003. Data Virtualisation in the NERC DataGrid. Proceedings of the U.K. e-science All Hands Meeting, S.J.Cox (ed). ISBN 1-904425-11-9.

2002:

- Juckes, M.N., 2002. Wave Mean-Flow Interaction. In: Encyclopedia of Atmospheric Sciences Edited by J. R. Holton, J. A. Pyle and J. A. Curry Academic Press
- Plagmann, M., B. N. Lawrence and G. J. Fraser, 2002. Gravity Waves in Fabry Perot measurements made at Mt John (44S, 170E), New Zealand. J. Atmos. Sol. Terr. Phys., 64, 367-376

2001

- Gray, L J., E. F. Drysdale, B. N. Lawrence and T. J. Dunkerton, 2001. On the interannual variability of the Northern Hemisphere circulation: the role of the quasi biennial oscillation. Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc., 127, 1413-1432
- Juckes, M.N., 2001. A generalization of the transformed Eulerian-mean meridional circulation. Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc., 127, pg(s). 147-160
- Lawrence, B. N., 2001. A Gravity Wave Induced Quasi-Biennial Oscillation in a three-dimensional mechanistic model. Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc., 127, pg(s). 2005-2021
- Osprey, S. M. and B. N. Lawrence, 2001. A possible mechanism for in situ forcing of planetary waves in the summer extratropical mesosphere. Geophys. Res. Lett., 28, pg(s). 1183-1186

4. ESTIMATED FUNDING USED

BADC Core and Supplementary Funding (from thematic programmes) arrive via a Service Level Agreement (SLA) between RAL and NERC. BADC is only one of many activities covered by the SLA, and while overall NERC/RAL spend/income balances in year, individual projects need not. However, income/expenditure for projects are expected to balance within the lifecycle of each project. In practice for the BADC, this means that it attempts to keep long term running mean income and expenditure in balance. This long term approach is necessary to handle the income from the thematic programmes, which generally comes in chunks which are not amenable to new recruitments. As a consequence BADC tends to deploy (NCAS funded) core staff for a while on thematic data management, and then catch up on core activities when enough income has been received.

Prior to the advent of NCAS, BADC core and supplementary projects were handled as one activity, however, to ease reporting lines and make clear the financial relationship between core strategic funding and thematic programme funding the two were split. In practice, this means the figures which follow have a discontinuity at the end of the 2001-02 financial year:

Overall BADC SLA Position			
	2001-02	2002-03	2003-04
Core Spend	629,417	615,763	708,148
Core Income	-686,100	-676,114	-704,689
Sup Spend	0	112,820	175,257
Sup Income	0	-95,000	-53,000
			Three Year Net

Net	-56,683	-42,531	125,716	26,502
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A further discontinuity appears at the end of 2001-02 associated with the definition of capital. Because BADC has chosen to purchase computing systems based primarily on commodity hardware, most computing purchases are reported by the accounting system as "recurrent". To understand better and control the BADC computing budget, computing was split out as a separate account code at the advent of NCAS, and so it has been chosen here to report the computing budget instead of capital, but for the 2001-02 year it is only possible to report the capital/recurrent split as recorded by the accounting system.

	BADC Core			BADC Supplement		
	<i>2001-02</i>	<i>2002-03</i>	<i>2003-04</i>	<i>2001-02</i>	<i>2002-03</i>	<i>2003-04</i>
Spend						
<i>Staff</i>	500,170	498,295	554,318	0	112,325	169,156
<i>Recurrent</i>	61,148	29,341	24,579	0	495	6,093
<i>Computing</i>	68,099	88,127	129,251	0	0	8
<i>Total Spend</i>	629,417	615,763	708,148	0	112,820	175,257
Income						
<i>SLA</i>	-686,100	-627,000	-637,000	0	-95,000	-53,000
<i>other</i>	0	-49,114	-67,689	0	0	0
<i>Total Income</i>	-686,100	-676,114	-704,689	0	-95,000	-53,000
Net	-56,683	-60,351	3,459	0	17,820	122,257

It will be seen that there is considerable inter-year variability in spend, primarily associated with recruitment timing and difficulties in knowing when income from the thematic programmes would arrive.

Since the split in core and supplementary funding (at the advent of NCAS) it has become clearer how the ebb and flow of core support to thematic programmes occurs between years. It can be seen that as of the end of 2003/04 the thematic programmes "owe" NCAS – significant funding is due in the 2004-05 year. It is expected that a significant portion of this will balance out over the next two years, but note that in general over the long term significant amount of NCAS core funding is required to support thematic programme data management – which reflects the difficulty of convincing the programme scientific steering committees of the true cost of their data management activities.

It can be seen that most of the BADC budget is spent on computing (hardware, software, maintenance) and on staff. It can also be seen that the computing budget has been increasing year on year, and this reflects the increased requirements to store large datasets (but this increase has been offset primarily by invoiced income, reported as "other" above).

In terms of staff, the full time equivalent for the three years is reported in the following table:

	<i>2001-02</i>	<i>2002-03</i>	<i>2003-2004</i>
Core	9.8	8.7	9.1
Supplement	0.0	1.8	2.9
Total	9.8	10.5	12.0

5. HIGHLIGHT – NERC DATAGRID DEVELOPMENT

In 2002, the BADC was awarded an e-science grant – The NERC DataGrid (NDG), and work began on the project in September 2002. The NDG is aimed at building a grid which makes data discovery, delivery and use much easier than it is now, facilitating better use of the existing investment in the curation and maintenance of quality data archives. Further, it intends to make the connection between data held in managed archives and data held by individual research groups seamless in such a way that the same tools can be used to compare and manipulate data from both sources. The NDG research team is a partnership of the BADC, the British Oceanographic Data Centre (BODC), and the CCLRC e-science centre, along with the Programme for Climate Model Diagnosis and Intercomparison (PCMDI) from Lawrence Livermore in the U.S. While the NDG will be aimed at the UK environmental community, the software produced will be of wider applicability.

In June 2004, the NDG demonstrated it's new metadata structures behind a discovery portal which exposed data from the BODC, the BADC, and from the U.S. National Centre for Atmospheric Research, NCAR. While the prototype portal only exposed a very small amount of observational data, it did expose the full ECMWF ERA40 dataset via a new interface – the NDG data extractor (similar to the Live Access Server, but based on a web service architecture). Underlying the portal, a new semantic data model allows user defined datasets to be extracted in a variety of formats.

The NDG is being built in a standards compliant manner, and makes use of Digital Library protocols as well as web services and International Standards Organisation (ISO) compliant metadata structures. NDG is currently attempting to identify and rectify deficiencies in Open Geographical Information Systems (GIS) consortium (OGC) systems, so that they will be able to fully support complex atmospheric and oceanographic data structures. When this is done, NDG will also support export to GIS.

6. SHAPE OF THINGS TO COME: THE NCAS II BID

Introduction.

BADC will aim to both ensure quality of service, and a wider breadth of service during the NCAS II period. To do this will require coping with expansion both in volume of data and types of data at the same time as maintaining rapid response to user queries and developing new techniques to manage the data.

The curation aspects of the NCAS II bid are split into three main areas:

- Atmospheric Services, where the prime emphasis will be on data acquisition on behalf of the community, and support for the NCAS centres, including Met Office Liaison.
- Archival Services, where the emphasis is on systems to acquire data (automation, ingestion, quality control), ensure data integrity, and provide data to the users, as well as provide a user support service and collect and interpret statistics of data use.

- Information services and Infrastructure development. Here the emphasis will be on providing tools to make use of the data effectively, to support collaboration in the NCAS community (via the development and management of appropriate software tools), and to ensure that the interfaces to the BADC develop with the general development of the Internet.

There will be a slight enhancement in the size of the research group to take on computational research as well as atmospheric science research. In particular, BADC will be taking an active role in the development of semantic web tools (to provide new ways of obtaining information from the data and metadata held at the BADC), and in the development of computational environments suitable for the exploitation of massive distributed archives. Existing research activities will be more accurately targeted to exploit BADC data and to ensure relevance and integrity of BADC holdings.

The research activities will then concentrate in three main areas:

- Digital Curation and E-science. The BADC expects in the next period to move from being a relatively small data archive (order tens of TB) to a large archive (order hundreds of TB). It will be necessary to devise new computational environments to exploit datasets of the expected size and complexity, and it will be necessary to make use of new techniques in collaborative working – both in terms of distributed data sharing and distributed information sharing. BADC will continue to work on a full range of research and development activities aimed at ensuring NCAS scientists have state-of-the art access to their data and information.
- Dataset Construction and Data Assimilation. In order to address the NERC strategic objective to exploit NERC data holdings, BADC will be endeavouring to continue to work on developing and exploiting data assimilation and other techniques to construct new combinations of existing data that will be of scientific relevance.
- Quality control and data exploitation. As well as the routine quality control activities, the internal research programme will concentrate on issues associated with evaluating the general circulation, and, clouds and orography in models and observations. Both activities will be carried out in conjunction with other parts of NCAS, and should exercise BADC systems fully.

NCAS SMA Visit

13 – 16 September 2004

Timetable

The SMA team will be divided into two groups and each group will focus on different scientific programmes within NCAS. There are seven centres/facilities that carry out the research and technology programmes within NCAS:

Climate variability and change – CGAM
Chemistry-climate interactions – ACMSU
Small-scale processes and weather – UWERN
Atmospheric composition – DIAC
Data Centre – BADC
Specialized measurement instruments – UFAM
Aircraft facility – FAAM

Of these seven programmes the following four are undergoing an SMA – CGAM, ACMSU, UWERN and BADC. Previous SMAs were carried out in 2000 (BADC) and 2001 (CGAM and ACMSU). The remaining three - DIAC, UFAM and FAAM – are providing a progress report as they have only recently been initiated.

Group A of the SMA team are: **Alan Apling** (ex Dept for Transport & Defra, recently retired, Chairman of the SMA Team), **Oystein Hov** (Director of Research at the Norwegian Met Service and a member of NERC's Science and Innovation Strategy Board), **Huw Davies** (Professor of Meteorology at ETH Zurich and Chairman of the NCAS Advisory Group), **Jo Haigh** (Professor of Atmospheric Physics at Imperial College) and **David Andrews** (Professor of Atmospheric Dynamics at University of Oxford). They will focus on CGAM, UWERN and UFAM and will be based at the University of Reading.

Group B of the SMA Team are: **Mike Ashfold** (Professor of Chemistry at University of Bristol), **Akkihebbal Ravishankara** (Senior Scientist at NOAA Aeronomy Lab, Boulder), **Jean-Pierre Pommereau** (Atmospheric chemist at CNRS Paris), **David Parkes** (retired ex Head of Research at Shell) and **Roland Kallenborn** (Senior Scientist at the Norwegian Institute for Air Research). They will focus on ACMSU, BADC, DIAC, and FAAM and will be based at the University of Cambridge. In addition **Howard Cattle** (Head of CLIVAR) will be joining the visit for the BADC presentation as he is also looking at the review of the BODC.

The SMA team as a whole will meet in Reading for dinner on Monday 13 September. On the morning of Tuesday 14 September, Group A will travel to the Department of Meteorology at the University of Reading and Group B to Cambridge where they will stay overnight Tuesday. Group B will leave Cambridge late morning on Wednesday 15 September to travel to Reading. The whole SMA team will meet in Reading from 15.00 on 15 September and stay overnight in Reading. The SMA team will depart on morning of 16 September.

Monday 13 September: NCAS Overview presentation (AJT)
SMA team dinner
overnight in Reading

Tuesday 14 September: 08.00 – 10.30 travel to Cambridge/Reading (AJT at Cambridge)

Group A: Reading		Group B: Cambridge	
09.30 - 10.45	CGAM overview (JMS) and computational support (LSC)	10.30 - 11.30	ACMSU overview (JAP)
10.45 - 11.15	Coffee and SMA team discussion	11.30 - 12.00	Coffee and SMA discussion
11.15 - 12.45	CGAM science outputs (JMS, MB, LG, JG)	12.00 - 13.00	ACMSU science outputs (PB, OM, PY)
12.45 - 13.45	Lunch and SMA team discussion	13.00 - 13.45	Lunch and SMA discussion
13.45 - 15.00	CGAM research training and career development (DB, TO, ML, HS)	13.45 - 15.00	Tour of labs (PG)
15.00 - 15.30	Tea and SMA discussion	15.00 - 15.30	Tea
15.30 - 16.30	UWERN overview (PJM)	15.30 - 16.30	FAAM progress report (RJ)
16.30 - 17.00	Met Office collaboration (PC)	16.30 - 17.00	Science Communications (LW)
17.00 - 17.30	SMA team discussion	17.00 - 17.30	SMA team discussion
Dinner incl: JMS, PJM, AB, LSC, CC		Dinner incl: JAP, MJP, BNL, RJ, LW	

Wednesday 15 September: (AJT at Reading)

Reading		Cambridge	
9.30 - 10.30	UWERN science (SEB, CC)	9.00 - 10.00	DIAC progress report (MJP, GM, JL)
10.30 - 11.00	Coffee and SMA discussion	10.00 - 10.15	SMA team discussion
11.00 - 12.00	UWERN science (SDM, RP)	10.15 - 11.15	BADC (BNL, SP, AM)
12.00 - 12.30	SMA team discussion	11.15 - 12.00	Coffee and SMA discussion
12.30 - 13.30	Lunch	12.00	Travel to Reading, lunch en route
13.30 - 14.15	UFAM (AB)		
14.15 - 14.30	SMA team discussion		
15.00 - 17.30	Whole SMA team to discuss SMA report		
Dinner at Reading			

Thursday 16 September:

09.00 – 10.00 Feedback to Director of NCAS, by SMA chairman, on outcome of visit.

End of SMA visit

Key to NCAS contributors:

Alan Thorpe (AJT)	Stephen Belcher (SEB)
Dan Bernie (Reading)	Mike Blackburn (Reading)
Alan Blyth (AB)	Peter Braesicke (PB)
Ian Castro (IC)	Peter Clark (PC)
Chris Collier (CC)	Lesley Gray (LG)
Jonathan Gregory (JG)	Paul Griffiths (PG)
Rod Jones (RJ)	James Lee (JL)
Matthieu Lengaigne (ML)	Paul Mason (PJM)
Gordon McFiggans (GM)	Anabelle Menochet (AM)
Stephen Mobbs (SDM)	Olaf Morgenstern (OM)
Tom Osborne (TO)	Sam Pepler (SP)
Mike Pilling (MJP)	Robert Plant (RP)
John Pyle (JAP)	Julia Slingo (JMS)
Hilary Spencer (Reading)	Lois Steenman-Clark (LSC)
Louisa Watts (LW)	Paul Young (PY)